

Name: Quazi Zafar Ahmed
Banner ID: B00311968
Course: DBA
University: University of West of Scotland
Cohort:13

Psychological Stress and Violence in workplace

An analysis on the consequences in a company

Abstract

"Psychological Stress and Violence in the Workplace - An Analysis of the Consequences in a Company," is the title of the study. The main goal of this study is to look into the many aspects of workplace stress that employee's experience. Employees are unable to execute to their greatest efficiency and quality as a result of their stress. The financial and marketing industries are the focus of this study. Through many approaches such as research philosophy, data collection technique, data analysis technique, research approach, research design, sample method, and so on, I have gathered accurate and reliable information about the study. I also employed data collection and analysis procedures to gather accurate and reliable information about the influence of psychological stress and violence in the workplace. I reflected by describing my experience while collecting data from the target respondents. The focus of the research report is on workplace stress and violence as related constructs that have a negative impact on the organization and will have negative consequences such as less employee involvement. Workplace violence occurs when employees are attacked or harassed at work, and it is one of the most common harmful practices that can be observed within an organization and can also have a negative influence on the business. After analysing the collected data, by interpretation, it has been determined that workplace stress and violence have a variety of effects on an organization's operations and profitability.

Associated organizations will acquire insight of their organizations and workers' positions as a result of the above research so that precautionary measures can be taken by the organization to provide appropriate insights to employees and develop such healthy behaviors for employees. Using the data from the previous researches, such dimensions are examined, causing the company to face issues related to business productivity and efficiency. Aside from that, stress can cause an imbalance of personal characteristics within an individual's psyche.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

Stress is increasingly being recognized as a workplace problem that is affecting an increasing number of employees all around the world. Workers are under increasing stress as the economy becomes more global and rivalry for market share and survival grows. With high levels of crime and violence in society, workplace violence manifests itself in the form of robberies and attacks, particularly against front-line employees and service providers. As pressures rise, workplace violence may rise as well, making worker-on-worker violence more likely.

1.1 Background of the research

Psychological stress at work encompasses many factors, including excessive workload, job instability, insufficient resources, interpersonal conflicts, and lack of control over one's work. This stress can lead to various physical and mental health problems, such as anxiety, depression and burnout, significantly harming the employee's performance and overall quality of life.

Additionally, persistent stress can promote negative emotions and escalate conflict, potentially contributing to a hostile work environment and, in extreme cases, escalating into workplace violence. Workplace violence refers to any act or threat of physical violence, harassment, intimidation or other disruptive behaviour that occurs in the workplace. This includes verbal abuse, threats, physical attacks and even acts of terrorism. The impact of workplace violence goes beyond the direct victims, affecting employee morale, damaging an organization's reputation and creating a financial burden through costs. Additionally, the psychological impact of being a victim or witness of workplace violence can be long-lasting, leading to post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) and other psychological disorders.

This research is to determine the and investigate the complex relationship between psychological stress and workplace violence, elucidating the mechanisms through which stressors contribute to the escalation of violent incidents in diverse professional settings. By comprehensively analysing the nexus between psychological stress and workplace violence, this thesis endeavours to shed light on the underlying mechanisms and implications of these phenomena.

1.1.1 Psychological stress

Psychological stress is pressure and strain. Stress causes most psychological suffering. Employees may want less stress. Positive stress also boosts athletic performance. It affects motivation, response, and environmental adaptation. Additionally, high-stress levels affect an employee's thinking. It may cause heart attacks, ulcers, strokes, and depression (Bell, Berry and et al., 2013). Psychological stress is also the psychological and emotional emotions an employee or individual has when expectations or needs exceed their coping capabilities. Workplace stressors include nepotism, salary mishandling, unanticipated job pressure, and

low team spirit. Psychological stress might result from an unethical or unpleasant atmosphere. It also affects company performance.

1.1.2 Violence

Violence is referred to as a behaviour that is intended to injure, hurt, or kill people. Violence in the working environment is one common factor that highly impact workers and the company but not necessarily physical. Workplace violence is mostly psychological. In the workplace, such an issue introduces a cluster of behaviour or actions, referred to as harassment, bullying, abuse, victimisation, intimidation, threats, and many other violent behavioural descriptors. Psychological stress and violence are characterised by non-verbal and negative verbal behaviours that may manifest the work site as false accusations, criticism, screaming, harmful eye contact, unprofessional conduct, work overload, unrealistic expectations, excessive monitoring etc. Additionally, workplace violence includes physical assault, intimidation, harassment, and other threatening disruptive behaviour by workers.

It includes verbal abuse, threats, physical attacks, and murder. Thus, it affects consumers, employees, and tourists. Any company's primary stakeholders improve employee performance.

1.1.3 Developing psychological stress and violence in the workplace:

In the working environment, psychological stress and violence may be developed differently, such as improper communication, lack of motivation, and unhealthier environment, and many others. All these factors directly impact the company's productivity and performance level and decrease reputation in the marketplace and customer's mind. In other words, violence in the working environment also impacts the satisfaction and trust of all workers working in that enterprise, bringing down the power of profit earning. There are many causes of workplace violence, such as threatening behaviour, verbal or written threats, verbal abuse, harassment, physical attacks, mobbing and bullying. Therefore, workplace violence is not limited or controlled to incidents in a traditional working environment (Büschi, 2014). It creates a risk that may be greater at sometimes of the day, year, or night. There are some primary examples of the threat of violence with the company, including paydays, during the holidays, performance appraisal, tax return season, overdue utility bill cut-off dates, parent interviews or report cards, early hours of the morning or late hours of the night etc. (F. Yousefi Rad 2021).

According to the HSE Survey of Work-related Illness reported by Smith (2000), 500,000 workers are suffering from stress connected to their jobs in the United Kingdom. This is a 30% increase from 1990. 15-20% of people in the Bristol Stress and Health at Work Study (Smith, 2000), which employed a random community sample with a total of 7,069 participants, were found to be very or severely stressed, while 40-45% of people were found to be moderately stressed. 23% of respondents reported having an ailment that was either caused or made worse by their employment. Both the Labour Force Survey (1995) and another survey based on self-reporting and using large-scale representative population samples found that 31% and 26.5% of respondents suffered from work-related stress or related illness. Both of these surveys were conducted in the United Kingdom.

1.2 How these issues are affecting on company's performance:

Employee's Psychological stress and workplace violence affects the company directly in its performance as these issues are related with the work performance. It also affects employee's morale and motivation level. It might seem like a problem for an individual. But the organization has greater setbacks because of these issues.

Cooper et al. (1996) highlight stress's well-known effects on illness absenteeism, performance, and turnover. There is a correlation between exposure to violent assaults or physical attacks and an increase in the number of sick days taken (Warshaw & Messite, 1996). The spells can be long-lasting in some situations, and the person may never be able to return to work and must retire as a result of their traumatic experience. A violent occurrence, on the other hand, does not always necessitate the recipient taking time from work.

Psychological Stress and workplace violence is also likely to result in lower job satisfaction and organizational commitment, both of which would be unfavourable to businesses (Barling, 1996). When combined with the behavioural impacts outlined above, workplace violence can affect an individual's productivity, whether they are violently attacked or simply witness to such incidents. Furthermore, it is not unrealistic to assume that employees who have not personally been attacked or witnessed others being attacked may be affected.

Bullying seems to have a variety of less obvious repercussions, including a reduction in work satisfaction and a lessening commitment to the organization. In addition, it has often been hypothesized that bullying will likely affect the organization by stifling inventiveness and originality in its employees (e.g. Bassman, 1992).

Sexual harassment increases absenteeism, transfers, and turnover (e.g. Barling et al, 1996). One in ten sexually harassed employees departed their jobs (Gutek & Koss, 1993; Her Majesty's Inspectorate of Constabulary, 1993).

Extreme stress or violence may lead to lawsuits in certain countries, depending on the culture. The such lawsuit includes physical attacks, bullying, and sexual and racial harassment. Claims in the US and UK may be expensive. Public relations harm may cost the claimant more than compensation (Knapp & Kustis, 1996).

For this study I have researched on two organizations and tried to focus on the effects of the issues on their performance.

ChopCut Limited is a medium-size enterprise that operates in the UK. The company mainly specialises in manufacturing and supply of better-quality products of Chopcut wheels / tires. Effects of the company are made from high and effective quality advanced technology and raw materials. Such type of products is available in different sizes and shapes in the market. All these are made from high and good quality raw material manufactured in its main factory located in Manchester Industrial Centre. The company is facing many troubles regarding the

mentioned situations above. Especially the work performance of the factory of Chopcut is facing a hard time because of workplace violence.

On the other hand,

Bank ABC Europe is an essential component of the Bank ABC Group. It serves as the central location for trade and investment activities that take place between Europe and the Middle East, North Africa, and Turkey area, and it provides assistance for these activities. The ABC International Bank, a Public Company Arab Banking Corporation House can be found at 1-5 Moorgate in London, United Kingdom EC2R 6AB. This location serves as the company's registered office. Registered Number 2564490. Registered in England. They provide service to customers both directly and via our Paris-based subsidiary from their office in London. The subsidiary's headquarters are located in Paris and have operations in Milan and Frankfurt. In addition, there is a representative office for them in Istanbul. Bank ABC Group is the only owner of each location and provides ongoing assistance. Bank ABC provides global transaction banking, corporate treasury and financial markets, Islamic financial services, real estate finance (exclusively for properties in the UK), and specialized finance (Bank ABC in London).

This organization faces workplace violence of stress mainly in the customer service department. However, the inter department conflicts and internal organizational politics also results in stress causing low performance of the bank.

1.2.1 Justification on choosing the organizations

Bank ABC is a financing company where most of the employee's social status or demography falls under one segment. For example, minimum requirement of getting to work there is to at least finish college with a relative major. This class of the people belong to the literate group and have a well standard lifestyle. However, the company is facing some definite issues like staff turnover and absenteeism. On the other hand, ChopCut being a manufacturing factory based workplace, there are versatile workers working on different pay range. The workplace has a versatility and workplace chaos is a regular scenario in here. Lack of moral, motivation and affected productivity was identified by the management for a long time. All these factors has a possibility to be the result of workplace violence or stress. Hence, it makes these organizations to be a perfect study area for the proposed research.

1.3 Rationale for the proposed research

Even though it has an inbuilt propensity to bring about outcomes that are detrimental to the organization's goals, the phenomena of organizational stress nevertheless seem to be regarded much too lightly by many leadership positions (Wright, 2007). On the other hand, it is becoming abundantly evident that it is in the best interests of both the person and the organization to identify strategies to minimize stress and, along with it, the likelihood of violent behaviour. (Crampton et al, 1995).

This can be an essential part of a research study that supports analysing the basic requirement of organising any investigation. To identify the main reason behind preparing this thesis, there are some essential questions which are given as under:

1.3.1 What is the research issue?

The present issue or problem identified in this research is to explore the influence of workplace violence and psychological stress on the company's performance. Both physiological stress and workplace violence are two foremost aspects that highly impact the sales of an organisation and workers' physiological stress and violence are a practical issue because it reduces employees' productivity and sales. Moreover, such problems also influence the reputation and performance of the organisation in customer's mind and the market (Cheung and Yip, 2017).

There are a different number of ways that defined Physiological stress and violence as an issue for an organisation; some are determined as under:

Moral and motivation: Physiological stress directly influences the motivation and morale of workers, both in terms of workers who are troubling with stress or workplace violence and the employees at entire states in the enterprise who must yield their duties (Ram, 2018). Thus, lack of motivation and morale among employees reduce the performance of the company directly.

Productivity and efficiency: Physiological stress highly impacts the efficiency and productivity of employees directly (D'Cruz, 2015). Therefore, staff turnover, low motivation, and morale will negatively influence the overall organisation and business efficiency and performance.

Communication and relationship: Highly stressed employees influence relationship and communication in the selected organisations. Employees who are stressed can be withdrawn, irritable and angry. Thus, less morale and motivation and high employee's turnover affect on productivity of workers. (Richards and Freeman, 2012). In addition, it can negatively affect team dynamics, communication outside and inside the organisation, and external and internal relationships.

Staff turnover, recruitment and training: The employee's turnover may be maximised, and experienced workers may leave the company (Garbarino and Magnavita, 2015). The company will then have to hire new workers with the given costs and time of the recruitment and training.

Customer services: It is more difficult to keep customer services with employees' absences, high employees' turnover, motivation and morale problem and common inefficiencies and productivity (Houmanfar, Alavosius and et al., 2015). Therefore, psychological stress and

violence can output in customer services problem, with client's complaints and likely loss of customers.

Absenteeism, presenteeism and ill health: The physically stressed workforce maybe not present from work or activity due to stress. As they may come to perform but not be capable of doing their responsibilities properly. Such an issue creates different problems related to health, such as mental health, long-term chronic, potential addictions, and many other conditions (Root and Brown, 2014).

These factors will highly influence Chopcut ltd. and ABC Bank for this research due to lack of resources, inadequate experience and knowledge, and other workers' influence. Furthermore, because of physiological stress, health and safety incidents are also considered main issues and further reduce company sales.

Therefore, above mentioned all issues described, workplace violence and physiological stress, are the most significant issues and impact on performance and market share of the company. Furthermore, these issues also influence employees by reducing morale and motivation, increasing the high turnover of workers, and many others.

1.3.2 Research Gap

Workplace violence and stress today has shifted from a company's internal problem to a more environmental experience. This has amplified the constant drop in manufacturing effectivity and even to a company's sales growth. According to Heliyon, 2019, workplace violence is defined as an act where violence occurs in physical abuse, bullying, harassment of employees, customers, or staff. It may arise due to assaults or other violent acts such as stalking, intimidation, Etc. According to Ram (2018), Work-related stress also impacts the performance of the organisation. However, most of the researches on the topic was based on working environments in the United States. The lack of empirical evidence on the effect of workplace violence on a company's performance inside United Kingdom was not thorough. Moreover, researchers have determined that some of the reasons behind workplace violence are anxiety, chronic depression, post-traumatic and stress disorder. Therefore, these factors may be interlinked. But despite this, not many academic studies have focused on addressing these factors' impact on the linkage between violence and performance of an organization. This is a critical research gap.

1.3.3 What could this research shed light on?

The current study is emphasised on ascertaining different factors or ways that negatively influence employees and organisation. It is needed for organisation and employees to resolve such a problem by establishing a friendly and effective working environment in which staff

members feel more comfortable and stress-free. Physiological stress and workplace violence are the main problems employees face due to a lack of motivation and morals. In this type of problem, employees feel demotivated and overly stressed in nature (Itzhaki et al., 2015). Thus, it is essential and significant for the researcher should follow different ways to overcome stress on employees and increase performance.

Workplace violence is identified as another variable in this dissertation that supports analysing critical aspects of such problems as physical abuse, mental harassment, Etc. These aspects can support making accurate solutions for problems that are related to workplace violence (Schnall and et al., 2018). The primary researcher of this study is known as a company facing the same issues of low performance or sales due to violence within the working environment. With the help of this research, they can find out better and accurate solutions for their problems and can even create a good understanding regarding employee's satisfaction and its significance. Thus, this thesis will finally benefit the company and their workers. Each research topic has dependent and independent variables that will highly impact the organisation and their workforce by reducing performance and productivity.

1.4 Aim of the research

The entire activity of the dissertation mainly depends on the research aim as it is considered a practical and foremost part of the study, which helps an investigator analyse research outcomes. The aim of this research proposal is "To analyse and interpret the impact of psychological stress and workplace violence on the performance of manufacturing and financial industry." This research should be able to determine the consequences of psychological stress and violence in workplace and can also help in developing workplace regulations to mitigate any probable affects.

1.5 Objectives of the research

The research objective here is based on two types of variables as dependent and independent. Both variables are essential in completing each activity of research within a given period. According to the research topic, company performance is considered a dependent variable because it is directly dependent on employees' productivity. In this physiological stress and workplace violence reduce productivity and performance of workers. Thus, it orders to improve workers' morale and motivation to help them overcome physiological stress and violence within the working environment. This research aims to evaluate the impact of workplace violence and psychological stress on the business of Manufacturing industry and financial industry.

The objective is to identify the effects of workplace stress and violence in individual companies.

- To evaluate different factors which contribute towards employee stress and violence.

- To examine the impacts of workplace stress and violence on the performance of the organisation.
- To identify the role of the organization in overcoming workplace violence.

1.6 Structure of Report

This part of the report is essential for the researcher because it helps them identify the entire dissertation's framework. It is also significant for an investigator to efficiently complete research activities within the given time. The report structure is divided into different parts, which will be helpful for a researcher to ascertain issues in research. (Cheung and Yip, 2017). It will also support in identifying effective results for future research. For example, psychological stress and violence are identified as the most significant issue in the working environment. Also, it is a significant problem in an organisation and highly influences its performance.

Moreover, this is also affected by the goodwill and image of the company in the marketplace. Report structure is helpful for an investigator to research in a more significant and effective manner (Author2020). Therefore, the structure of the report is determined as under:

Chapter 1: Introduction

This section is the first and essential chapter for the thesis because the aim, objectives, questions, rationale, hypotheses, purpose, and importance of research or topic are covered. These are considered essential and valuable elements of the dissertation for the investigator to complete this well-planned and effective way. With the help of this chapter, a researcher can easily find out overview or summary of the entire work (Daudt, van Mossel and Scott, 2013). In this chapter, the researcher can analyse the background of the study and the main reason for choosing this research or topic. These are identifying essential and central aspects for doing research activities more effectively and adequately. (Baldwin, Fehrenbacher and Eisenman, 2015). With the assist of this chapter, the investigator can systematically perform each research activity, and it will also help them accomplish better and effective outcomes for future study (Brannen, 2017). According to the topic, the role of a researcher is to investigate the influence of psychological stress and violence on firm performance. It is a significant issue that arises in the working environment of the company. Therefore, this chapter is essential for researchers to ascertain issues and identify different ways to overcome them more effectively. The first introductory chapter is vital for the researcher to finish this and gain practical outputs for future study.

Chapter 2: Literature Review:

The literature review is the second chapter of the thesis, which will help an investigator complete research activity effectively and accurately. A literature review is considered a survey of publications, including books, authoritative websites, journals, sometimes conference papers, Etc. All these sources are helpful and valuable for the researcher to collect in-depth information about the topic. It is a detailed summary of a previous study on a research topic. In addition, a review should describe, enumerate, summarise, clarify, and objectively evaluate this previous research. It should provide a theoretical base for the study

and assist the investigator in ascertaining the study's nature (Nielsen and et al., 2015). As a result, it is a clear, repeatable, and systematic process for analysing, synthesizing, and recognizing the existing body of work that has been documented and finished by academics, researchers, and practitioners. There are different elements in a literature review, such as it explores existing information, ascertain critical researchers working on this topic, show relationship between previous studies, identify gaps in past research, notice primary methodologies & research techniques, find out main ideas, theories, and conclusion establish similarities and differences Etc.

All these are primary and practical elements and support a researcher to analyse gaps and conflict in the previous study (Munn et al., 2014). The literature review aims to provide a theoretical framework, deep understanding of the requirements on the intended audience, background for all aspects of the topic, Etc. Thus, it is a significant chapter for the researcher to efficiently perform each study activity within a given time duration (Cheung and Yip, 2015). It also helps researchers do further research more effectively and accurately (Hannula, Suoranta and Vadén, 2014). In this part, all research questions explained in a proper and well-planned manner. It is also an introductory chapter for the investigator to gain better results in each time duration.

Chapter 3: Research Methodology:

This chapter clearly describes the research methods applied to conduct the study (Park, Choand Hong, 2015). The investigator explains how the valuable information and data to address the study questions and objectives was gathered, presented, and analysed. It is an introductory chapter for conducting research activities systematically and effectively (Vaiolati, 2013). Research methods encompass design, data sources, instruments, presentation, collecting, analysis, philosophy, methodology, and more.

These are necessary for researchers to get reliable data on ChopCut Limited & ABC Limited's workplace stress and violence (Fox and Alldred, 2015). Thus, all these methods are practical and valuable for the investigator to gather appropriate information or data about the effects of workplace violence and psychological stress. Thus, research methodology is valuable for the investigator to collect reliable and valid data about the study.

Chapter 4: Data analysis and interpretation/findings:

Data analysis introduces an effective evaluation process following logical and analytical reasoning to analyse each given data element. It may be described as a crucial process involving evaluating, changing, cleaning, and modelling data or information to identify relevant information that supports decision-making and informs conclusions (Sansbury, Graves and Scott, 2015). It has different approaches and facets that help an investigator analyse accurate information about the study (Patten and Newhart, 2017). There are mainly two types of methods, including primary and secondary. Under primary, the questionnaire will assist an investigator in analysing relevant data, whereas secondary research, literature review, books, journals, and many other relevant articles used by the researcher to gather accurate information or data about the study (Grossoehme, 2014). In the questionnaire, a different number of questions will vary by the researcher, which will help identify

respondents' response about the impact of workplace violence and psychological stress (Lushey and Munro, 2015). Along with this, interpretation will be the help of each question mentioned in the questionnaire. Thus, it will be more effective and valuable for the investigator to analyse the response of respondents.

Another essential and essential chapter that will help an investigator collect appropriate outcomes from the field of study. Findings or results of the research will be on primary and secondary data (Psacharopoulos, 2014). Under primary data, the questionnaire will provide effective outcomes. In secondary data, research outcomes are on literature review information (Park, Cho, and Hong, 2015). Thus, both primary and secondary data sources are essential for the researcher to gain appropriate and effective outcomes within a predetermined time duration (Hickson, 2016). Along with this, research outcomes mainly related to workplace violence and psychological stress in the working environment of ChopCut Limited & ABC Limited. It is a significant issue that highly impact on performance of an organisation.

Chapter 5: Reflection and recommendation for future alternative research methodology:

It is another essential and effective chapter and in which an individual describes their opinion about the topic or research (Vaiolati, 2013). To define personal experience during the field of study, Gibbs reflective cycle model used (Sansbury, Graves and Scott, 2015) helps a person describe their overall experience, Issues, Etc. For identifying issues, some relevant recommendations about overcoming such issues easily (Carspecken, 2013).

It will also help a researcher to do research activities or tasks systematically and more effectively. The case study method is considered the best alternative research method for this research, which will also help to collect accurate data or information about the study. Thus, it was needed to complete each activity of research within a given time duration.

Chapter 7: Conclusion:

It is the last chapter that describes the complete summary or detail of the dissertation. The last chapter includes detail of each chapter and helps an investigator find out the research results (Spence Laschinger and Nosko, 2015.). Thus, the investigator needs to accomplish better outcomes within a given time duration. This part of the research will support an investigator to study further and gain better outcomes for the study (Munn et al., 2014). In addition, the conclusion introduces a summary of the entire project, which assists a researcher to accumulate proper response from the respondents. It summarises introduction, literature review, research methodology, data analysis and interpretation, reflection, and recommendation (Daudt, van Mossel and Scott, 2013). Therefore, the conclusion chapter is essential for the investigator to do each research activity more effectively and information manner (Lushey and Munro, 2015).

Chapter 2: Literature Review

2.1 Stress and Violence in the workplace : A review

The main goal of the literature review is to identify what information already available that can be related to this research and helps an investigator identify inconsistencies, including, conflict in previous studies and gaps in research. (Fox and Alldred, 2015). My objective here is to collect accurate and in-depth information about the impact of psychological stress and workplace-violence in working environment of an organisation.

2.2 Method of Review

I am following an Argumentative Review to address all issues identified in the previous studies. The motive here is to create a literature review body that establishes a contrarian opinion.

2.3 Justification:

Among all the types, Argumentative reviewing technique can be helpful or informative towards the literature review and may help to gather in-depth and reliable data about the effects of physiological stress and workplace violence on the performance of an enterprise. However, after a careful screening process, it is now determined that the **Argumentative review** will be more effective to collect appropriate data about the impact of workplace violence and psychological stress on performance and success in selected organizations.

2.4 Conceptual framework

Illustration 2.4: Conceptual framework of workplace stress and violence

From the above conceptual framework this can be analysed that workplace stress and violence are two different concepts which are associated with minimising workplace involvement and justification of workings. Also the variables are of two types. Workplace conditions and workplace stressor and two independent variables which affects the other dependable variables such as psychological stress or health outcomes. Sometimes workplace stressor can either be a dependable variable or independent variable.

But as both variables arise from similar reasons, they are interlinked in some context. Sometimes violence is this is being analysed that workplace stress and violence both are regarded as negative aspects which are leading to develop minimised working and under balanced activities within the organisation. One can arise because of the other factor in a workplace. In this manner several challenges can be faced by the organisation which are restricting the way to earn profit and market credibility as well (*Chosewood and Tamers, 2021*). In the context of business need of appropriate atmosphere is needed so that employee may work with higher efficiency and involvement as well. Workplace stress and Physiological violence are two difference concepts which are leading the way to develop such aspects in which an employee may feel pressurised and unhappy with organisational culture so that this would develop in minimising involvement of employees.

From the above demonstration this is concluded that due to workplace condition situation of work place stress and violence may arise. Psychological stress may lead into developing of such atmosphere within workplace developing of burnouts within workplace. This is analysed that there are various reasons due to which workplace stress and violence may be seen and working environment is the major among all. Due to workplace situations employee may feel stress and direct implication is seen over employee productivity and efficiency. Besides this there are various outcomes related with mental stress such employee feels mental illness due to which they are not able to concentrate over their working in appropriate manner.

Employee feel situation of anxiety when they are not getting appropriate environment of working and resultantly serious impacts are seen over mental and physical aspects of individual so that they are not able to concentrate over their working so that appropriate wellbeing is not created (*Dimitriadis, 2021*). For an organisation this is imperative to hold a degree in which employee may feel to have not being involved. In this manner an organisation is required to use such measures in which appropriate business insights cannot be seen. For an organisation keeping of significant edge is mandatory so that they can get higher employee motivation and involvement as well. For wellbeing of employee keeping such measures are necessary in which employee do not feel valued to work and associate with keeping degree of involvement. This is beneficial for employee for maintain such degree of involvement so that proper working in such a way that they may deal with business working in appropriate manner.

2.5 Factors which contribute towards employee stress and violence in an organisation

Due to healthcare patients, workplace violence is common. Multiple research indicated that workplace violence stresses healthcare and public health, employees. This may be due to patients' severe diseases, stress, and family interactions at a tough time. Further, *dine et al. (2021)* mention that a large number of violent actions that occur at work are not reported. This leads me to assume that companies may not want the bad repercussions of reporting this difficult issue that occurs in healthcare institutions. Understanding the diverse factors

contributing to employee stress and violence within an organization involves an exploration of various psychological and sociological theories. Several prominent theories shed light on these complex phenomena, elucidating the multifaceted interplay of individual, organizational, and societal factors.

The social exchange theory dictates that the importance of reciprocal relationships in the workplace. Employees' perceptions of fairness and equity in their interactions with colleagues and supervisors play a crucial role in shaping their behaviour and emotional well-being. When the social exchange is characterized by favouritism, discrimination, or unequal treatment, it can create feelings of resentment, mistrust, and alienation, fuelling interpersonal conflicts and, in extreme cases, acts of violence.

The Organizational Culture Theory states that an organization including its norms, values, and management practices, significantly influences employee well-being. A toxic culture characterized by excessive competition, bullying, and a disregard for employee welfare can foster a highly stressful and volatile work environment. Such a culture can normalize aggressive behaviour, leading to the acceptance of workplace violence as a means to resolve conflicts, perpetuating a cycle of stress and aggression.

Agnew's general strain theory highlights how various strains, such as work-related frustrations, conflicts, and perceived injustices, can lead to negative emotions and behavioural reactions, including violence. In the context of the workplace, these strains can manifest as job dissatisfaction, role ambiguity, and unfair treatment, fostering a sense of injustice and powerlessness among employees, potentially triggering aggressive responses and violent behaviour.

2.5.1 Authority Violence

The majority of cases, conflicts with management-employee communication are what causes workplace violence. Employees seek to seek vengeance for what they believe to be unfair or unjust treatment by the company. Employees' dissatisfaction with their bosses may also be related to work assignments, how they are generally handled, or how they are spoken to. Additionally, workers murder because they are not promoted. An employee who kills a boss because they feel they have been wronged is known as an authority killer. The target of the attack could be a person or people, or a place of power such as a building, structure, or organization. As a result of their real or perceived involvement with the authoritative figure or institution being assaulted, random victims are frequently harmed and/or killed during the assault (Burgess, et al., 1994). On June 4, 1991, one of the scariest incidences happened in San Diego. On that day, Larry Hansel went back to the Elgar Corporation electronics plant where he had worked before being fired three months before. The 41-year-old father of two, who investigators said had a gun obsession, but no violent history, turned Elgar into a catastrophe zone. The former technician wrecked the plant's telephone network, detonated

two radio bombs that filled the corridors with smoke, and murdered two executives with a 12-gauge shotgun and rifle. He surrendered miles from the crime. (O'Boyle, 1992).

According to Adele Burney, 2019, stress and violence is a way of reacting to any demand and may include the intention to hurt, damage, or kill someone. It can be both good and bad experiences. Stress and violence are often related to work; when there is a significant burden of work on employees, and it becomes so overwhelming, then violence erupts mainly.

Another researcher included a case study that stress may build the main factors: lengthy working hours, tedious work, job insecurity, poor relationships, changes within the organisation, Etc. Stress can cause anxiety, aggression, isolation, mood swings, irritability, depression, Etc. Workers at every level are experiencing increased tension and uncertainty. Because of rapid changes and increasing competition in the global economy, it has become inevitable for all profession (Sonya Budeva, PhD 2021).

Another case found where some organisation created stressful workplace situations, which they use to lay off within the company, which reflected in building stress among the remaining employees who may worry about their jobs. The reduction of work staff can lead to an increased workload for the remaining employees, which will increase stress as they struggle to meet deadlines (Judith E. Arnetz 2020).

Another information found stress may build because employees may feel bullied by their managers or co-workers and may feel helpless to do anything about it. Loss of a job affects every part of life, from when they wake up in the morning to whom they see and what they can afford to do. Not all signs of stress mean an employee is about to commit a murderous rampage (Ms Courtney Goetz 2020).

Workplace violence may occur in many forms, i.e., from verbal abuse to physical bullying among employees, between staff and customers, and between managers and subordinates. Work without stress might be impossible to find, so more sensible choice should be made to adopt more effective strategies to reduce stress at work. Sometimes violence may arise due to a noticeable change in behaviour of an individual, any physical sign of exhaustion, a reduction in the quality of work and increase in days missed or lashing out at other employees due to which an employee might commit a murderous rampage.

2.5.2 Discrimination and sexual harassment

In addition, psychological elements like discrimination and harassment may build up over time and eventually cause someone to break. Therefore, repeated traumas can frequently lead to violence. Psychological and physical microtraumas are also possible. A mental cumulative trauma disorder (CTD) frequently causes violence in the workplace (Lindsey, 1994). Additional factors contributing to workplace violence include stressful working circumstances, poor security, and disappointed client complaints. These factors collectively could make going to work harmful to your health.

Assaults, stalking, bullying, and intimidation cause workplace violence. These indicators imply sickness and overwork but must be monitored over time. It may be averted by advising workers not to attend risky locations and offering safety education to know what is unacceptable and how to defend themselves (Kristin Natalier 2020).

Carmela Mento 2020 included the workplace in her statement. It has been determined that an act of violence is one in which a person is harmed, threatened, attacked, or intimidated in some way, and the effects of such an act may be disastrous. Any worker or the workplace can be impacted by it. It can result in psychological as well as physical health issues. The intensity of an occurrence determines the spectrum of possible physical effects, which may vary from minor injuries to fatalities.

2.5.3 Co-worker violence

Because everyone wants to be able to trust their co-workers and be loved by them, workplace violence is the most terrifying and upsetting for many employees. However, co-workers who believe they were treated unfairly out for termination, passed over for a promotion, rejected in a close connection, or denied a fair wage rise may be candidates to engage in violent response (Ramsey, 1994). Early in 1994, a male employee of Kraft General Foods in Illinois shot and murdered a female co-worker at one of the company's plants. The victim later ended her relationship with her murderer (Anfuso, 1994). According to K.A. Francis, 2019, *Work Stress* is defined as stress due to conflicting demand in an individual's job. It is a relative factor that every individual cannot experience in the same way—experiencing stress triggers emotion such as anxiety, fear, pressure, panic and other feelings. Stress is a normal part of every individual's life, and every individual has to deal with it in some or another way. It can even work as a helpful motivator if handled well. Sometimes it may come from inside rather than outside. One can stress himself just by worrying about useless things.

According to M. Abedini, 2021, stress may arise due to performance pressure on employees that they have to give their whole and soul at work, the physical environment and uncertainties like lack of feedback on an individual's performance which should be given so that an individual can keep track of how well he is performing in the organisation, which if not given will not make an employee work well, if an individual does not work well it may result in job loss, Etc (M. Abedini 2021).

2.5.4 Stress in the workplace

According to (Adele Burney, 2019), Stress can cause such physical ailments as anxiety, headaches, and depression. Due to the hostile working environment, Stress due to tight deadlines, maximum hours, and concern regarding the economy. In addition, workplace stress harmfully impacts on emotional and physical responses of employees. Job or workplace stress can lead to bad health and even injury. Workplace stress is a significant issue that highly affects an organisation's performance and productivity. It will also impact

the company's performance by decreasing the number of employees in the organisation and reducing motivation level among workers. Work stress can be a primary challenge to employees' health and effectiveness worldwide. Stressed or pressured employees are more likely to be unhealthy, less productive, less motivated, and less safe on the job. Consequently, stress may be caused by demands at work and home. Managers often cannot shield workers from the stress that develops outside of the job, but they cannot help employees with stress that develops at work. Stress at work may be a major concern for the business and its workers (Author 2020).

In another case study Lauren Hollywood DNP, PMH-NP 2020, mentioned that Workplace violence could overcome by creating the right environment for the employees and making them feel like an essential asset of an organisation, by talking to the employees, by providing regular workplace violence prevention training to know how to act when there is some workplace violence.

2.5.5 Downsizing/rightsizing causing stress

For many people, US culture has transformed into a pressure cooker of repressed stress and frustration. When employees believe there is no legitimate way to handle their anger, violence occurs. A world with limited opportunities has fostered an environment of "hopelessness" for many people. Workplace pressures can take many different forms. For example, enforced early retirement or enforced downsizing may make employees feel abused, victimized, or overburdened.

According to Lauren.M 2021, poor working conditions, pre-employment screening of employees, stress at the workplace, staff shortages, and bullying at the workplace. In addition to the adverse impacts on health, exposure to violence may result in negative views about one's employment, which may manifest in negative behavioural consequences such as employee absenteeism and decreased task performance, among other things.

2.5.7 Underprepared workers

Budget cuts affect training and development departments during difficult economic times. One of the effects will be a rise in the proportion of workers in the company who are poor to handle the evolving demands of their positions. This will make the workplace extremely stressful, which makes it likely that insecure workers may lash out violently in response to their displeasure (Elliot and Jarrett, 1994).

In addition, another author added. When addressing the issue of the potential for violence in the workplace, employers are faced with the difficult challenge of striking a fine balance between the rights and safety of their workforce. Violence and stress can lead a company in ruining its image. Moreover, once the image is ruined, the company has to bear huge losses, no other organisation will want to work with us, and create conflicts between employees. There will be lousy decision-making and will reduce the market share (Anne-Marie Brady 2020).

2.5.6 Relationship between Employees and managers

The information found in another case study, suppose there will be stress and violence in an organisation. In that case, there will be a negative relationship between employees and managers working there, reflecting in reduced employee performance since proper motivation is not given to them by their leaders and managers. Physiological, psychological and behavioural symptoms of stress can cause immense organisational distress. By having stress and violence, neither employees nor managers will live happily, so some strategies must be adopted to overcome stress and violence in the organisation (Laura Tarzia 2020).

The European Commission defines workplace violence as "incidents when workers mistreated, threatened or attacked in conditions related to their employment including traveling to and from work, constituting an implicit and explicit challenge to their safety, health or well-being," Albadry AA 2020 reports. This term emphasizes power, which may be utilized against anybody. The combination of individual interactions, workplace factors and personal factors contributes to violence at the workplace (Albadry AA 2020).

According to Mansi wang (2020), the factors that cause workplace violence are poor relationships between employees, increased mood swings, decreased productivity, overreaction to company policies, Etc. These causes can prevent by providing additional security measures that may help detect possible violence from occurring.

2.5.8 Negative work environment

According to Baldwin, Fehrenbacher and Eisenman, (2015), stress and violence, the workplace is conceived as the pressure from the work environment, then as strained within the person. The interaction between the individual and the situation can undermine the achievement of goals both for individuals and for organisations.

According to Michael Notaras 2020, stress reflects an individual's change in behaviour, i.e., acute responses in feelings, such as anxiety, fatigue, irritability, Etc. The factors that found to be associated with workplace stress are lengthy working hours, time pressure, complex

Another expert advised that workplace stress prevention and management need organizational involvement as organizations induce stress. Allowing workers to engage in workplace design and transformation may avert it. Employment should also enable individuals to learn and advance their careers. tasks, lack of breaks, Etc. (Simon Wilson 2020).

According to Vic Benuyenah 2020, the workplace should comprise some area of decision-making that an individual can call their own and build cooperation, social contact, and coherence between different working conditions. Violence defined as the emphasis that a person or group must intend to use force or power against another person in order of an act.

2.5.9 Lack of Policy

Another Author added that notifying authorities whenever needed and taking corrective actions, educating employees on policies and procedures and possible working signs of workplace violence and adopting a zero-tolerance policy towards workplace violence. Employers must treat terminated employees in an organisation to avoid the feeling that they are a victim (R. Beckers 2021).

According to Bell, Berry and et al., (2013), stress refers to harmful physical or emotional body's way of responding to actual and perceived situation an individual face and violence refers to the use of physical or psychological act which threatens the people with assault, abuse or harm from within or outside the workplace. Stress and violence at the workplace put employees at risk, hinders productivity and hurts the company reputation.

Bond, S. A. et al. (2010) explain that businesses must create a supportive culture with genuine rules, procedures, and metrics to aid workers. This entails giving managers and organizations tools to change organizational climates to reduce workplace bullying and improve employee health, happiness, and support. (Pihl-Thingvad et al., 2019, p. 554) Emphasises the importance of exposure frequency in building a complete framework to prevent workplace violence. Recognising the Occupational Safety and Health Act of 1970 may assist in building a policy that requires employers to “operate a place of work free from known dangers that are causing or likely to cause death or severe bodily damage to his employees.” Hartley et al. (2015, p. 83) recommended multi-level collaboration to reduce workplace violence. It would allow preemptive intervention before major occurrences or staff trauma responses. Each research above provided a foundation for workplace prevention.

2.6 Effects of stress and violence in an organisation

Stress and violence within an organization can have wide-ranging effects, both positive and negative, influencing various aspects of the work environment and employee well-being. Understanding these effects is crucial for implementing effective strategies to manage and mitigate the adverse consequences while harnessing any potential benefits.

2.6.1 Positive effects on work output

Whilst stress and violence is being emphasised as a positive force in the coping process, the presence of stress may also impact negatively on the situation by adding pressure, due to being a source of distraction or irritation.

Increased Motivation: Moderate levels of stress can stimulate employees to perform better, promoting a sense of urgency and encouraging proactive problem-solving. This heightened motivation can lead to improved productivity and creativity, fostering innovation and efficiency within the organization.

Heightened Awareness: Stress can prompt individuals to be more attentive and detail-oriented, enabling them to identify potential risks and challenges more effectively. This heightened awareness can contribute to a culture of vigilance and responsiveness, enhancing organizational resilience and adaptability.

Conflict Resolution and Growth: Constructive resolution of workplace conflicts, even those stemming from stress, can foster improved communication and stronger interpersonal relationships among team members. When managed effectively, these experiences can promote personal and professional growth, leading to enhanced teamwork and collaboration.

2.6.2 Negative effects on mental and physical health

According to Khairunesa Isa (2020), when individuals have much stress, they may find it hard to concentrate, feel confident, and decide. Some physical sensations like tense muscles, sweating, and a racing heart may be experienced during stress and may have some long term impact on physical health. It may arise due to overload of work, lack of appreciation, isolation at the workplace, lack of training, Etc.

The effects of stress on individuals have been the subject of investigation in a great number of research (e.g. Quick, Murphy, & Hurrell, 1992; Murphy & Cooper, 2000). We will present a high-level summary of existing research because the consequences of stress are very well documented. The research conducted by Cooper and colleagues is given here, along with some of the most significant impacts (1996).

- Mental illness
- Coronary heart disease
- Certain types of cancer

A series of minor health complaints of a physical or psychological nature, e.g. psychosomatic symptoms, migraine, stomach ulcers, allergies

In terms of both the short-term and long-term impacts of stress, the outcomes of sexual harassment for the person are comparable to those of bullying, with health problems and a general decline in well-being being regular results of both types of behaviour. (Schneider et al, 1997). It is common for those who are the objects of sexual harassment to suffer from mental health issues such as sadness and anxiety (Richman, et al., 1999, Koss, 1990). By the model of stress provided earlier, effects certainly have the potential to differ depending on the specific targets (Stockdale, 1996).

Violent incidents in the workplace also have wider ramifications than the person/s directly involved. Recent research has shown that witnessing violence may lead to fear of future violent incidents and as such has similar negative effects as being personally assaulted or attacked (Rogers & Kelloway, 1997; Leather et al., 1998).

Some other author (Onochie, Lawrence 2020) mentioned that various factors such as management style, work hours, and interpersonal relationships can impact an employee's stress levels. Dangerous stress's level often shows physical warning signs, such as heartburn, tension, headaches, fatigue, and occurrence in body weight.

According to Chevette Alston, 2017, workplace violence identifies as a significant occupational health problem that workers of an organisation face violence in the workplace. This type of violence mainly includes physical abuse as well as mental abuse of threatening. Psychological abuse can be explained as the proper and systematic usage of malicious manipulation via non-physical acts in opposition to an intimate partner or dependent adult. Psychological abuse can happen before sexual, physical or many other cases of abuse. Violence against female can cause long term mental and physical health issues. Abuse and violence affect not just the female involved but also their families, children, and communities. These impacts cover harm to personal health, possibly long-term injury to children, and damage to societies such as homelessness and lost work.

2.6.3 Behavioural and attitudinal effects

Research shows that stress may affect behaviour and attitude. Cooper et al. (1996) believe that stress may lead to decreased work satisfaction and commitment, dangerous behaviour and higher accident risk, and "bad lifestyle habits", including smoking, drinking, and poor eating. Violence causes poor attention, self-confidence, and personal disengagement, frequently leading to social isolation. (Brady, 1999). According to Brady (1999), when confronted with such circumstances, victims of abuse are often unwilling to accept any assistance provided, making therapy and rehabilitation more challenging.

Bullying may have a negative effect on a person's ability to concentrate, which can result in an increased risk of error as well as the possibility of being involved in an accident (Hoel & Cooper, 2000b). Researchers also mention increased alcohol and cigarette use. Finnish research indicated that male "interpersonal disputes" victims drank heavily, passed out, and used cigarettes and tranquillizers. Female victims also fainted after excessive drinking (Appelberg, 1996). (Many health and well-being consequences are behavioural. Violence may cause social retreat and irritation, hindering job productivity and social connections at and beyond work (Warshaw & Messite, 1996).

It's possible that people who are driven out of their jobs, decide to quit on their own, or are fired because of their suffering will be unable to find new employment, and in some cases, they won't even try (Gutek & Koss, 1993). The event will undoubtedly impact earnings and career possibilities.

After long absences, some of the worst-affected targets will never work again. Health may impede their comeback. In other circumstances, the escalating intensity of their disagreements takes them into severe opposition to their organisation, which in some cases, chooses to terminate their job (Leymann, 1990). Bullying situations seem to be more likely to involve protracted periods of legal wrangling and litigation (Earnshaw & Cooper, 1996). The victims of bullying who have had their employment contracts terminated as a direct

consequence of the dispute have, in the end, discovered themselves to be unhirable. This is the case in a significant percentage of situations (Leymann, 1992).

Another author recommended that This stress can be overcome d by doing meditation to soothe one's mind, by indulging in physical activity, metabolising the excessive stress hormones, and talking to someone, be it a friend or colleague, by doing so all those things which make one happy. In context, workplace violence involves employees, customers, clients and visitors (Abdul Hameed P.V 2020).

According to Laurie Erdman, 2015, Workplace stress is the main subject that impacts an individual's performance and productivity indirectly and in a hostile manner. There are two types of stress effects as short term and long term. In a short duration, its impact on employee's health, including headaches, anxiety, shallow breathing, upset stomach and difficulty sleeping. On the other side, workplace stress also impacts an employee's long-term, such as it increases the risk for back pain, depression, heart disease, lasting muscle aches and pains and many other issues. All these are significant issues that impact employee's performance and productivity negatively.

Stress also can affect an employee's mind by impairing imagination and concentration. It also increases the chances when an employee will make mistakes because they not thinking clearly. Constant stress can also affect workers' behaviour and emotion by making them impatient, grouchy, less excited regarding their work, and even depressed (Van Bussel 2020).

Stress at work may be caused by various factors, including but not limited to long hours, job uncertainty, high workloads, and disagreements with supervisors or coworkers. In addition to this, symptoms of stress caused by work include a decrease in work performance, anxiety, depression, trouble sleeping, changes within the organization, changes to duties, a lack of autonomy, tedious work, insufficient skills for the job, an inadequate working environment, few promotional opportunities, and crisis incidents such as a workplace death or armed holdup (Santiago, Joanna Carla (2021).

Thus, workers must recognise their job-related stress as an essential safety and health issue.

2.6.4 The effects on the organisation

Cooper et al. (1996) highlight stress's well-known effects on illness absenteeism, performance, and turnover. Here we will examine how workplace violence affects comparable and other organizational outcomes. Exposure to violent assaults or physical attacks may increase illness absence. (Warshaw & Messite, 1996). Due to their unpleasant experience, some people never return to work and retire. However, a violent occurrence does not inevitably lead to the receiver needing to take time off work. Health care, where physical

violence or fear of violence is common, seldom causes recipients to miss employment. (Boyd, 1995).

Plenty of anecdotal data suggests that victims of bullying report inferior job performance compared to those who were not abused. Recent research has shown some empirical support for this theory by comparing the self-rated performance of those who have been bullied to those who have not (Hoel & Cooper, 2000a). On the other hand, there was not a particularly clear connection between bullying and performance at work. It has also been argued that bullied persons may be eager to exhibit skill and dedication when their organizational status and self-esteem are failing. This is because bullying may have a negative impact on both of these factors (Hoel et al., 1999).

Bullying seems to have a variety of less obvious repercussions, including a reduction in work satisfaction and a lessening commitment to the organization. In addition, it has often been hypothesized that bullying is likely to have an effect on the organization by stifling inventiveness and originality in its employees (e.g. Bassman, 1992).

Extreme stress or violence may lead to a lawsuit in certain nations, depending on the culture. The such lawsuit includes physical attacks, bullying, and sexual and racial harassment. Claims in the US and UK may be expensive. Public relations harm may cost the claimant more than compensation (Knapp & Kustis, 1996). The British Retail Consortium Survey of 1995/6 (Standing & Nicolini, 1997) indicated that physical assault incidents might raise insurance rates and require security upgrades. Whilst a rise in incident rates does not always lead to an automatic increase in premiums, it may be more difficult for the organisation to reinsure (Standing & Nicolini, 1997). The survey also implicated that the introduction of new safety devices is likely to carry an additional training cost for the devices to become efficient. It is worth noting that, despite the high costs to organisations and society resulting from violence at work, our knowledge of violence, particularly about non-fatal acts of violence is still limited (Castillo, 1995). Any attempt to put a monetary value on the cost needs to take this fact into consideration.

Dealing with unstable individuals may cause it. Workplace stress and aggression cause image damage, disruption, accidents, turnover, and more. These dangers reduce an organization's performance and competitiveness. Sick leaves, absenteeism, turnover, productivity, service quality, motivation, and professional unhappiness influence almost all sectors and personnel, affecting the organization's performance and efficiency. Stress may create workplace violence, but workplace violence will produce stress. (Timothy D 2020). Both employers and workers feel the effects of stress and violence in the workplace. It can lead to low morale and a negative image of the organization, making it difficult to attract and retain workers. It can inflict anguish, misery, incapacity, or even death on the employer. As a result, companies must show sensitivity to workplace violence's repercussions and create an atmosphere that encourages open dialogue. (Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health 2020).

Within the organization, certain problems have been identified as having the potential to constitute stresses in the working environment of the corporation. The organisational culture, the job content and expectations, poor management practices, the physical work environment, a lack of support, role conflict, change management, and trauma are all primary stresses associated with work. (Annick PhD; Marchand, Alain PhD 2020).

According to Laretta Claussen (2011), work-related stress is a global problem that affects employees' health and the company's productivity. Work that exceeds an individual's ability to cope is stressful.

2.7 The role of government in overcoming workplace violence

According to Blanck, Hyseni and Wise (2021), government plays an important role in overcoming workplace violence, they have formulated various policies and laws related to violence which helps in eliminating the harassment and violence in Organisation. In order to prevent from threat or harassment in Organisation there are various laws which is designed by government so that employees can work comfortably without facing any threat or violence. There are various types of violence and aggression which includes threats, antisocial behaviour, verbal and emotional abuse, physical attacks, lack of respect and intention to injure. It could be happen between colleagues, superiors or member including pupils, patients or clients. The Violence behaviour includes spitting, rude gestures, sexual assaults, robbery, written abuse and malicious damage to property of customer. Staff or business. Violence also includes behaviour like stalking, verbal abuse, harassment, threatening behaviour and intimidation. The precaution through which policy can be reduced is making policy, procedures, risk assessments and actions that need to be put into practice. Policy must be framed in order to reduce the case of violence and aggression (Draganić and Arefin, 2021). Government has made various policies and laws which focuses on reducing the violence and aggression in Company they are Health and Safety at Work Act 1974, Management of Health and Safety at Work regulation 1999, Reporting of Injuries, Disease and Dangerous Occurrence Regulations 2013, Equality Act 2010 and various other laws which helps in preventing the violence in Company. Through creating these acts government is supporting to reduce the aggression and harassment in Organisation due to which employees can work with effective and efficient manner without feeling threaten. The Management of Health and Safety at work regulation act focuses on identifying potential hazards to employee safety and health. Through implementing this act in Company, employer and employee can report to dangerous situation and also take care of their own health and safety while working in firm. Health and Safety at work act provide procedures and policies related to employee's health and safety. The Organisation must ensure that their employees must get training so that they can understood the health and safety policies. Main objective of health and safety act at workplace includes protecting non employees against health and safety risk which arises through working activities, use of explosive or highly flammable or dangerous substances and ensuing staff health, safety and welfare at work. Health and safety act includes various laws which can prevent employees from any hazardous or dangerous equipment that can affect their life (Dule, 2021). Government is also focusing on creating a team that main purpose is to reduce the violence and develop positive

working environment in Firm so that workers can work in effective and efficient manner without feeling harassed or threaten. So, Government plays an important role in eliminating the aggression or violence from Companies in order to make employees feel comfortable and stress free.

According to Michael Roberts, 2019, *Workplace violence* is defined as a frustrating act in which an individual is threatened, assaulted, abused, harassed, intimidated and can be caused due to working with volatile people. Sometimes, it may arise due to noticeable behaviour change, reduced work quality, or any physical sign of work. An employee might commit a murderous rampage. Workplace violence can affect both the worker and the workplace to lead to reduced organisational performance. It should be avoided so that a feeling of security amongst workers and better relationships can build between workers-managers. Exposure to violence may lead to adverse job attitudes and may reflect in some behavioural changes such as reduced task performance, employee absenteeism, Etc.

Another information has found that to avoid workplace violence. The government has to take some actions to build a comfortable working environment. As the government provides a legal framework for a market economy to operate effectively, they can request an inspection of the workplace to see records of work-related injuries and provide some helpful feedback to employees to prevent workplace injuries (Kirstin PhD 2020).

According to Pranab Bardhan 2020, Registering with the state government establishes the company's financial capacity. Through this registration, the government may monitor firms' business operations to gain a competitive advantage. The government might ban workplace violence. This policy covers employees, customers, contractors, and other contactors.

Adopting such a policy will protect employees from violence, but it will also protect employers if violence occurs. Government can make some changes in the policies of the company and can make them in favour of employees working over there; the policies may be like employers cannot make deductions from the worker's wages if an employee is affected by the workplace violence (Louit-Martinod and et al., 2016).

The organisation can help the employees in training regarding the company's policy, ways to mitigate the risk of violence and how to handle violent situations to protect themselves when violence occurs. The appropriate course of action may differ in handling violent situations, depending upon the company. The government may create a support team for workplace violence and harassment victims. Doctors will treat affected personnel. Government initiatives also advance an economy's infrastructure.

The development infrastructure involves economic and social overhead capital necessary for the company's growth and optimum utilisation of resources (Aeschbacher and Addor, 2018).

During a marketing transaction of an organisation that impacts a third party other than marketer and purchaser, the effect is known as an 'externality. Thus, it is the role of the government to protect the public from environmental externalities (Author 2021).

According to Steve Greece, 2019, Workplace violence refers to frustrating incidents that consist of physically and psychologically damaging actions that can have a significant short-term or long-term impact on an individual (Jensen and van der Voort, 2019).

It can be any incident where a person is harassed, abused, assaulted, and has devastating consequences. Nowadays, violence has become a crucial part of every work environment and can lead any business to affect an organisation's overall capacity, which will reflect in a bad image, productivity, turnover, accidents of the work environment.

It also negatively impacted the organisation's efficiency and performance, including sick leaves, absenteeism, dissatisfaction with services, motivation, Etc. To overcome these factors, the government did some acts to avoid workplace violence, including the health and safety act, consumer protection act, commodities act (Geiger, 2016).

The health and safety legislation promotes safer workplaces, reduces dangers, and implements employee and employer safety and health initiatives. This statute outlines everyone's health and safety responsibility to make the workplace safe and complaint-free.

Employers that fail to prevent workplace violence may be cited. A workplace with more than five or more employees or employers must keep a written record of health and safety policy (Gustin, 2020).

In order to promote and defend the interests of customers against shortcomings in defects in products and services. Sometimes violence may occur because of selling defective goods, so this act was enacted to secure a consumer's rights against unfair trade practices. This act involves various rights for a customer. They have the right to be heard, the right to be informed, the right to consumer education, the right to seek redress, and the right to get the success that is guaranteed to them (Hwang, 2017).

The minimum wage act was enacted to set the minimum wages, which must be paid to employees in certain employments. This act was made to empower the government to take steps to determine the minimum amount of wages and to revise the wages within every five years. This act helped employees build satisfaction with their job since they will be paid a minimum wage in every situation. Enforcement of this act helped motivate employees, improved productivity, and more efficiency of firms (Sherman and Mitchell, 2017).

Workplace violence is affected employers by building poor image and poor morale of the company and affected employees by causing distress, pain, disability or even death. By implementing the DOL workplace violence program, an organization may create a working environment where a violent scenario can be properly dealt with an emphasis on prevention by raising employee awareness of workplace violence, how to react to it, and how to avoid it. (Jackson and Fransman, 2018).

K.A. Francis (2019) defines violence as the intent to use force or power against another person. Workplace violence may include verbal abuse, physical assault, murder, and more. Employers may promote reporting and educate workers on unacceptable behaviour to protect their interests.

Personal, workplace and interpersonal variables cause workplace violence. Workplace stress, bad working conditions, pre-employment screening, personnel shortages, and bullying may cause it. The factors which cause violence at the workplace are increased mood swings, decreased productivity, poor relationships between employees, overreaction to the company's policy, Etc. The government have an essential role to play in overcoming workplace violence. They did various acts in order to protect the interest of employees. They are the equality act, the harassment act, working hour act.

The Equality act (2010) approved to protect people from discrimination in the workplace and broader society. This act says that all the employees working at every level must be treated fairly in an organisation; they should not be treated based on an individual's characteristics and ensure consistency in what employers and employees need to do to make their workplace fair. Treating an employee unfavourably or refusing to hire a qualitative prospective candidate just because they are too young or too old is considered unlawful and is against this act. Rules for men and women are similar in this act; they cannot be different. Mistreating a female employee is against this law. Salary, leaves, and other rules everything will be similar for both men and women. Under this act, it is illegal for employers to differentiate between employees and job seekers just because of their religion.

The Protection from harassment act (1997) enacted for protecting individuals from harassment and similar conducts. Harassment refers to unwanted, unwelcomed, and uninvited behaviour that offends, demeans or threatens the victim and puts an individual in fear of their safety. When on the ground, a race of disability, sexual orientation, religion, belief, an employer engages in unwanted conduct. Harassment is the most common event faced by employees these days; it may occur when one employee cases abuse or insults another employee and shares poor relationships while working in the same environment. The civil harassment law says that harassment is unlawful violence, like assault or stalking or a credible threat of violence or any threat which seriously scare, annoy or harass someone without a valid reason. 'Credible threat of violence refers to intentionally saying something or pretending in a way that would make an individual afraid of his or her safety or that of their family. It includes following someone, stalking someone, making harassment calls or texting someone over some time.

2.7.1 There are some laws in the context of working hours:

- Every adult (an individual who has completed 18 years of age) cannot work for more than 48 hours a week and not more than 9 hours a day, and if the companies make them work more, the employee could file a case against that company (Carspecken, 2013).
- There are some restrictions made on women related to working hours, the factories act (1948) restricts employment of women to work between 6.00 a.m to 7.00 p.m., and (Psacharopoulos, 2014)
- A rest of at least half an hour should be five, in such a way that no period of work shall exceed 5-1/2 hours (Hickson, 2016).

According to Heliyon, 2019, workplace violence is defined as an act where violence occurs in physical abuse, bullying, harassment of employees, customers, or staff. It may arise due to assaults or other violent acts such as stalking, intimidation, Etc. So government should make some changes in the company's policy as they provide a legal structure to operate effectively in a market (Grossoehme, 2014).

They establish legal rules that control relationship among business, resource suppliers and consumers. Workplace violence occurs when individuals working in an organisation are not satisfied with the work culture or their superior employees. It can be prevented by restricting employees from entering those areas where they feel unsafe and educating them about their safety when a miss happens (Patten and Newhart, 2017).

Many organisations created a stressful work environment for the employees as they used to lay off the employees, which built stress among workers working there. Government can restrict an organisation to have a specific workforce, which will help the company improve employee performance and lead to organisational success wherein case the amount of workforce is not fixed, there will be an intervention of government in organisational policy (Gabriel, 2015). The government can make some new policies for employee working within the organisation in terms of improving the working culture and a practice performed in a company (Fox and Alldred, 2015). These policies will promote a positive environment at the workplace where employees can work freely without being stressed (Vaioleti, 2013). In turn, this benefits both parties, that is, the company and employees, as organisations will retain their loyal workforce for a more extended period by providing them with a positive and motivational environment. On the other side, employees will get a faithful environment so that they can work properly and enhance their skills and capability, which will help in their further development (Lushey and Munro, 2015). Hence, with the help of government support, employees will be able to increase their productivity, leading to improved performance of the organisation (Author 2021).

2.7.2 The concept of workplace stress and Physiological violence

According to (Adele Burney, 2019), Stress can cause such physical ailments as anxiety, headaches, and depression. Due to the hostile working environment, Stress due to tight deadlines, maximum hours, and concern regarding the economy. In addition, workplace stress harmfully impacts on emotional and physical responses of employees. Job or workplace stress can lead to bad health and even injury. Workplace stress is a significant

issue that highly affects an organisation's performance and productivity. It will also impact the company's performance by decreasing the number of employees in the organisation and reducing motivation level among workers.

Work stress may also be a global health and productivity issue. Stressed workers are also less healthy, productive, motivated, and safe.

Thus, job and home demands cause stress. Managers cannot help workers deal with work-related stress, but they can help with outside stress. Workplace stress may affect the company and its workers. (Author 2020).

According to the Mary Gormandy White, 2018, Work stress is defined as a type of stress due to conflicting needs and demands in an individual's job. Work-related stress is more harmful in that workers have physical and emotional reactions to job needs that are difficult to control.

On the other hand, work stress plays a vital role in keeping the workers aware of the workloads and efficiency on many occasions. It is also necessary for some employers to get the job done on time (Author 2020).

Some stress that employee experience in an organisation's working environment to the physical surroundings in which they work (Sarah Smith 2018). This form of stress can be related to workplace safety problems, the configuration of an individual's work area, type of furniture and many other types of equipment that must be applied to do job functions, activities, and other variables.

It is also related to the workplace stress faced by employees and impacts their physical and mental health. Along with this, this problem can be tied to the anxiety of job loss, lack of feedback on an individual's performance, hoping for acknowledgement or promotion, or any other issues (Ian G. Buckle 2020). Due to uncertainty, one of the significant issues in business is high employee turnover, which will impact an organisation's business performance.

2.8 Types of Violence

Violence is a complex and multifaceted phenomenon that can manifest in various forms, impacting individuals, communities, and societies at large. Understanding the different types of violence is essential for developing effective intervention strategies and promoting a safer and more secure environment. There are different types of violence including physical violence, sexual violence, emotional violence, psychological violence, spiritual violence, and cultural violence.

2.8.1 Physical violence

Physical violence occurs when someone controls another with their body or an item. Forced sexual activity is sexual violence. Emotional violence happens when someone degrades another. Finally, spiritual violence occurs when someone manipulates, monitors, and controls another's spiritual beliefs (Laura Tarzia 2020).

It is a kind of physical abuse that can directly affect the person's life, inner thoughts and feelings. It creates such a situation for people to feel very uncertain about their lives and do not feel safe in their own house (Naomi Drew 2018).

It is very dangerous as it destroys relationships with others. Sometimes, it is also found in children, which severely affects them by stopping them from being healthy adults. Some of the reasons behind this nature are anxiety, chronic depression, post-traumatic and stress disorder. It is sometimes also related to the imbalance of power in a relationship, including bullying other people, gaslighting and abusing at the workplace (Author 2020).

2.8.2 Cultural violence

Concerning the information above another, some data have found in another case study that, Cultural violence happens when a person is harmed as an output of practices that are part of his or her religion, culture, or traditions. Psychological violence occurs or occurs when someone uses causes, and threats fear in a person to gain control. All these are the primary type of violence that negatively impact employee's health and mind. Along with this, there are different examples of psychological violence or abuse: isolation from others, threats, verbal aggression, control, intimidation, harassment or stalking, humiliation, insults, and defamation (Kare S and Wampler 2020).

2.8.3 Psychological violence

Threatening to hurt someone or their family if they leave, self-harm, abandonment, Harassment/stalking, personal property destruction, verbal hostility, social isolation, denying phone access, not letting a competent person make choices, inappropriately regulating the person's activities, treating a person like a kid or a servant, withholding friendship or love, etc. (Geo. Wash. Int'l L. Rev. 2020).

According to Andrea Borghini, 2019, psychological violence may be determined as that kind of violence that covers psychological harm on an agent who is being violated. It is compatible with verbal violence or physical violence. The harm caused to an individual by a sexual attack is not only the injury deriving from the physical damage to his or her body; it affects an individual psychologically too.

It was also found in some other case study that, Brainwashing is also fallen under psychological violence as it manipulates the person's emotion. This type of violence affects the working environment of the business organisation and create an unhealthy working situation that affects the performance of an entire enterprise. In return, employees or staff get demotivated, directly affecting their activities, and the ratio of employee turnover will also increase (Jonathan Riedel 2019).

According to Natasha Tracy, 2019, psychological abuse is common, but some know psychological violence. Physical abuse may hide for a while. It may govern employees' lives

and inner thoughts. Workers may worry about the world and their homes. Thus, it may ruin a close connection, relationship, or self-bond.

This is not the end; many other examples have found from similar case studies that, there are different symptoms and signs of psychological violence. For example, name-calling, yelling, insulting the person, imitating or mocking the person, ignoring, isolating the person, swearing at them, excluding them from meaningful activities or events, threatening the individual or threatening to take away something essential to them. Psychological abuse is also known as emotional abuse (Grenville-Cleave and et. al., 2021).

Psychological violence does not only affect a person's mental health, but it also takes them away from future opportunities and developments. Some of the more examples related to the issues are threatening other people, showing verbal aggression, showing control over others, harassing others, stalking people and humiliating someone without reason (Nichola Jones and Kate Pincock 2020).

Referring to violence and according to Laurel Dunn 2021, this violence is further divided into other abuses like verbal attack or threat, putting down, making isolated, being jealous, restricting a person's freedom, etc. Some of the abusive behaviour that affects the victim internally and emotionally are blaming them, shaming and name-calling. Therefore, psychological stress and work-related violence highly impact the individual and an organisation by decreasing their performance and productivity. It will effect on market share and performance of the organisation in an addressed manner.

2.9 The impact of workplace stress and violence

Workplace violence causes stress. Johnson and Indvik (1996) study workplace violence reasons, costs, and types. Hans Selye, a 1930s endocrinologist, invented "stress" after observing rats develop ulcers under intense stress. This study shows how a hazardous workplace may dramatically affect workers' stress, contrary to workplace violence and stress research. The article describes how a toxic workplace may cause psychological damage, including stress. Employers suffer from stress-related absenteeism, employment churn, and lower production. Chronic stress may disrupt sleep, create headaches and backaches, and change your life. These results effectively generate perspectives on probable reasons directly connected to numerous elements impacting workplace violence in a company.

Bond, S.A.etal. (2010) relates organizational environment, workplace bullying, and post-traumatic stress symptoms in a research case study. Workplace bullying and violence caused post-traumatic stress symptoms, and the organizational environment was linked to workplace bullying. According to Bond et al. (2010), workplace violence may take several forms. Threats to professional standing, personal insults, work-related harassment, and rumor spreading are examples of workplace bullying. Workplace bullying is a persistent stressor, but it affects the company and individuals needing crisis management.

Perrucci (2017) defines job-related stress as the stress that individuals experience when confronted with work pressures and expectations unrelated to their talents and expertise that

test their ability to deal with them. Stress may be brought on by a wide variety of work or activity conditions; nevertheless, when it occurs regularly, it can lead employees to believe that they lack support from their coworkers and superiors and some degree of control over their work processes.

Thus, challenge and stress often must be clarified and used to justify bad management. Due to modern job expectations, pressure is inevitable. Acceptable pressure or force may keep personnel awake, encouraged, and capable of accomplishing work and learning, depending on resources and personal traits. Stress may affect employees and the company. (John S. Marcie C, Martin 2020).

According to Root and Brown (2014), Work-related stress or pressure reasoned by a flawed work enterprise. There are different reasons for work-related stress within a working environment of an organisation. Some are poor work design, poor management, lack of control over work processes, unsatisfactory working circumstances, lack of support from supervisors and colleagues. Apart from this, there are different stress-related hazards at work classified into work context and work content.

Work context: Some other researcher highlighted in their research that there are different aspects related to the work context, which increase pressure among all employees. In which some are: career development, status and pay, i.e. lack of promotion opportunities, job insecurity, work of low social value, under or over-promotion, unfair or unclear performance evaluation systems, piece-rate payment schemes Etc. Along with this, the role of organisation, interpersonal relationship, work-life balance, poor leadership, poor management also consider significant issues of increasing work pressure (Camila Burning 2018).

In another case study, there are different ways to increase pressure or stress among employees. It includes job content, i.e. under-stimulation, monotony, lack of variety, meaningless tasks, Etc. Working hours are also central to maximising stress among employees, i.e. long and unsocial, strict or inflexible, poorly designed shift systems, unpredictable. Along with this, participation and control also consider increasing violence and stress within the working environment (Kristin Ryba 2019).

According to Stavroula Leka, Pr Amanda (2016), Work stress is thought to negatively impact an individual's physical and psychological health and the effectiveness of an organisation. Stress is high affects different people variously (Groton and Radey, 2021) Experience of work-related stress can originate dysfunctional and unusual behaviour at the workplace and contribute to bad mental and physical health. In extreme cases, traumatic events or long term stress at work may track to psychological issues and be conducive to psychiatric issues resulting in lack of work and avoiding the employee from working again. Under stress, employees do not find it easy to maintain an effective or healthy balance betwixt work and non-work life.

According to Griffiths, Pr Tom Cox (2016). Due to this, they may engross in an unhealthy program or activities like drinking, smoking and abusing drugs. Work-related stress may also impact the immune scheme, impairing employee's capability to fight infections. Work stress makes employees unable to relax or concentrate, distressed and irritable, unable to think logically and make decisions, tired, depressed, anxious, have trouble sleeping, enjoy their work less and feel less committed to it, and experience severe physical issues like heart disease, high blood pressure, headaches, digestive disorders, and musculoskeletal disorders.

According to Ram (2018), Work-related stress also impacts the performance of the organisation. Suppose crucial staff and a large number of employees, stress in work may challenge the performance and healthiness of the enterprise. Unhealthy enterprise does not acquire the best from their employees, which may impact their productivity in the progressively competitive market and even their survival.

Work-related stress affects organizational performance differently. It includes absenteeism, lack of dedication to work, hurting performance and productivity, raising staff turnover, influencing staff recruitment, increasing liability to legal claims or actions by stressed workers, and degrading the enterprise's internal and international image. (Dina Alexandra 2021).

Another author Joao Miguel (2021), added. Thus, work-related stress is negatively or adversely impact business performance. Stressed workers are not able to do all activities or tasks within the given time and systematic manner. They cannot complete work systematically and adequately, which negatively impacts the reputation and market share of the company. The organisations have different employees and require proper motivation and satisfaction in a different number of ways.

According to Lowers & Associates, 2016, violence in the workplace undeniably impacts the directly attacked employees. The impact of workplace violence also extends far beyond this straightforward victim to clients, co-workers, shareholders, executives, and even out of society. There are direct losses by diminished productivity, negative publicity and low morale. These are a high impact on the reputation and brand equity of the organisation for a long duration.

Luciyana Y. Philaw (2020) added that there are different victims of workplace violence, including family members, co-workers, community, company executive, shareholders, Etc. All these are considered one of the primary victims that creates violence within an organisation's working environment.

There are mainly three stages of workplace violence: early warning signs, escalation, and further escalation, requiring emergency response. Under the early warning signs stage, verbal abuse, lack of cooperation, disrespect, and intimidation are the main factors that highly impact employees and the performance of an enterprise negatively (Bullying.co.uk. 2019).

An Author Anon 2019, mentioned in a case study research that, under escalation stage, argues with customers, refuses to obey policies, sabotages equipment, steals property, seeks revenge, verbalises intent to harm, distributes threats by note or email, sees self as the victim are consider main aspects for increasing violence within the working environment of those organisation. Under the last stage, which is further escalation, requiring emergency response, different aspects included physical fights, suicidal threats, raging, destruction of property, and weapons to harm. All these are significant factors that create violence among employees and impact the productivity of employees and companies (Anon 2019).

Therefore, workplace violence is negatively impacting workers, which leads to less performance and productivity of an organisation. It will also impact on reputation and brand image of the company.

Workplace violence is a threat to employees. Internal and external workplace issues may produce threats, verbal abuse, physical attacks, and murder, one of the main causes of job-related fatalities. Workplace violence is an increasing problem for businesses and workers everywhere (Mastracci, Guy and Newman, 2014).

Judith Arnetz, Lydia Hamblin, Sukhesh Sudan, and Bengt Arnetz (2018) define intimate relationship violence as physical aggression, sexual coercion, psychological abuse, and dominating behaviour. Frustration, exposure to violent media, family or neighborhood violence, and a tendency to view others' acts as hostile even when they're not may all lead to violence.

Drinking, insults, and other forms of provocation, as well as environmental conditions such as heat and congestion, all contribute to an atmosphere that is more likely to result in aggressive behaviour (Krieger, 2016).

Violence is a significant issue in society and an organisational premise; thus, it significantly impacts society and employees. In this modern environment, people are very much conscious about their image, so they try to avoid the causes that create violence. However, organisations are also concern about creating an excellent environment to reducing the chance of violence and work stress (Krasikova, Gree and LeBreton, 2013).

According to research, workers' morale gets down by around 44% when they face this issue. One cannot ignore the connection between morale and productivity. If employees are highly motivated, then their productivity will also be high. However, if they are not happy with the surroundings or have a doubt related to self-esteem, then undoubted their output will below. Psychological stress is considered a prime reason behind poor concentration at the workplace (Khamisa and et al., 2015).

Organisations put performance pressure on workers to increase their productivity, but sometimes it backfires, and employees fail to deliver their natural performance. Sometimes performance management creates value in developing the operations and functions of an organisation through the satisfaction of employees. People face social, cognitive, and physiological pressures every day. Stress is a reaction to biological needs regardless of the stressor. Threat-related stressors may cause stress (Itzhaki et al., 2015).

Stress stimulates the HPA axis and releases hydrocortisone. Psychological homeostasis stress. Thus, stress causes arousal and hyper mobilization of the body's typical activation and emotion system. Physiological stress causes unpleasant sensory, emotional, and subjective experiences connected to substantial tissue damage and physiological hazard. Another major workplace concern is stress. Employees worldwide face stress. Stress has become the most common issue for employer significantly in developing nations in which the employer or higher authority does not recognise the influence of stress on employee's performance. Thus, an organisation needs to maintain an environment to reducing stress and workload (Houmanfar, Alavosius and et al., 2015).

As per the opinion of Subha Imtiaz, 2019, stress is a common aspect that has a significant impact on an individual's life and living. Now a day's employers and higher authority of the firm.

In this modern business environment, each business organisation's potential motive is to attain higher growth and success within the commercial centre. These organisations deliberately work and take crucial decisions without considering the comfort zone of employees (D'Cruz, 2015).

For attaining higher growth and successful organisations are effectively concerned with merger, acquisition, and developing economic interdependence among various geographical areas due to globalisation; thus, this creates value for the firm in expanding business. Over the last few decades, technological development and restructuring have changed the organisational work that resulted in time pressure, excessive work demand, role conflicts, ergonomic insufficiencies and problematic customer relationship are causes of stress. Workplace violence and psychological stress harm the productivity and performance of employees within the workplace, thus high work pressure (Cheung, T. and Yip, P. S., 2017). Violence creates demotivation for workers and thus may decrease employee performance and overall organisational productivity.

Employees working in different sectors and organisations have to deal with stress which is a significant issue in today's modern business environment and has a massive impact on the living of people and the organisational operations (Cheung and Yip, 2017).

According to Eva Gorgenyi-Hegyes 2021, Business workers, especially bank employees, are among the group of workers under a great deal of stress due to many preventative measures. Stress contributes to reduced organizational performance, decreased overall employee performance, high error rate and poor quality of work, high staff turnover, and absenteeism due to health problems such as anxiety, emotional disorder; work-life imbalance; depression and other forms of ailments such as frequent headache; obesity and cardiac arrests.

In research on the business environment, violence and stress have increased due to the high pressure of work, resulting in lower productivity and performance of employees. However, in the workplace, the violence has caused due to high frustration. During high work pressure, employees get frustrated and try to reduce their work by providing extra operations

to their subordinates, which results in high pressure and develops the situation of violence, which affects the working of employees within the workplace. In the banking sector and this segment of business, the level of pressure on employees is high. In the banking sector, the political level is high. This management is based on employee favouritism, and skilled people do not get opportunities as per their ability (Mansi Wang 2021).

The above-discussed matters may result in lower performance of employees. Workplace stress encompassed various aspects like Lack of administrative support; excessive workload and work demand; problematic customer relations; co-worker's relationship; family & work-life balance and associated job risks Etc (Author 2021).

These all aspects may cause high dissatisfaction among employees, resulting in lower employee performance and productivity (Bell, Berry and et al., 2013).

The primary aim of this particular study is to explore the issues related to stress within the workplace and examine the interrelationship among employee's performance and workplace stress or the influence of stress on employee's performance (Author 2021).

Psychological stress refers to stress, which may decrease the ability to work or interact effectively with other individuals and be less able to make good decisions. Stress has also known to play a part in anxiety and depression. Psychological stress is a vast term that may impact an individual's personal and professional work (Bernaldo-De-Quirós and et al., 2015).

Due to psychological stress, people feel depressed and anxious. They thus may result in low morale and non-effective decision-making; thus, in this situation, the mindset of people are not stable, and people cannot take proper decisions and activities within the workplace. However, employees' performance decreases, which may cause an issue in the performance of an organisation (Berry et al., 2016).

Stress has a massive influence on the company and people performance, impacting the health condition and living of employees (iu and Jie, 2017). The particular study conducted has shown that the sources of stress known as Occupational Stress Cause are negatively interconnected to the well-being and job satisfaction of employees within the workplace (Burke, 2013).

The study showed that workplace stress and employee performance have negative relation; thus, collectively, these two aspects may result in lower firm performance. In today's business environment, employees are recognised as the vital aspect of an organisations growth; thus, the level of employee's contribution may cause the higher performance of the firm. However, the success and growth of a business are based on the total contribution of employees within the workplace environment (Büschi, 2014).

For developing organisational operations, businesses provide rewards and extra benefits like compensation, extra pay Etc. Moreover, these are prominently positively correlated to employee efficiency as expected (Allen, Muñoz and de Dios Ortúzar, 2019).

The study found a negative relationship between job stress and job performance. However, the male employees were found to be affected more than their female counterparts. The interrelationship between work stress and organisational performance has found to be harmful due to various issues like home-work interface, workload pressure, performance pressure, relationship with others and role conflicts on one side and job performance. On the contrary, "role conflict" and "role ambiguity" positively relate to stressors against the public notion. At the same time, the connection is found to be negative between other stressors and job performance (Hopper, 2019).

Imrab et al. (2013) found that stress is responsible for decreasing the performance of bank employees. The investigation in a proper manner has found a negative correlation between stress and job performance, i.e. as the stress develops, the job performance goes down and vice-a-versa. There are various causes like High workload, role conflict, and inadequate monetary reward are recognised as the prime reasons of causing stress in employees that may assist in decreases employee efficiency or working ability within a workplace environment (Hopper, 2019).

Various critical components of employee job performance are mainly affected by stress or violence, which involved Productivity, Job Satisfaction, morale, Absenteeism, Decision-Making Abilities, Accuracy, Creativity, and Attention to Personal Appearance, Etc. Organisational Skills, Courtesy Cooperation, Initiative, Reliability, Alertness, Perseverance and Tardiness. Violence in the workplace environment was virtually unheard of until the 1970s. Thus, violent events have been determined with work throughout human history and have developed in complexity as civilisations have become more advanced (Singh and Behera, 2016).

In this modern era, societal exposure to all aspects of violence is much frequent than in previous decades due to news broadcasts, videos, movies, television, and books that vividly portray violence. Workplace violence is proportionally creating a vast influence on the overall operations and performance of an organisation; thus, these influences are causing through physical, psychological, and financial problems to victims, co-workers, families, businesses, and others who are considered as the essential part of an organisation (Ratcliff, 2017).

The potential right of an Employees is to expect a work environment that gives protection and promotes safety from harassment, threats, and violence. However, the Occupational Safety and Health Act (OSH Act) of 1970 "ensures every workplace is free from known hazards". In this modern business environment, people are aware of their rights and norms favouring or against them, so they prefer a good and friendly work environment in respect to improvising their operation and organisational production properly. High stress affects the mindset of an individual, and people are not able to keep themselves in a particular area.

These may affect the productivity and performance of employees within the workplace (Cockayne, 2018).

Employees are the critical aspect of a firm, and organisations must provide them with a good culture and environment in respect to sustain them for the firm's long-term operations. A high level of stress and violence within the workplace causes a high level of dissatisfaction among employees, and they are focused on left out the place and switch their profile. Thus, people search for new opportunities and not stay for a long time in a stressful environment (Coleman, Pincus and Smyth, 2019).

Employee's stability is a positive aspect for the growth and success of a business, and violence and stress have a substantial negative impact on the productivity and performance of employees. Each minor and extensive business enterprise must provide a good and healthy environment for their employees to retain their sustainability within the workplace (Furnham and MacRae, 2017).

2.10 Impacts of workplace stress and violence on the organisation performance

Based on the viewpoint of Mary Gormandy White (2019), work stress is the stress that developed because of conflicting the demand in one job. Under this, amount of the control on staff members has an impact on the work stress. The stress on the employees is harmful to them and develops the physical and emotional reactions to the demand of jobs that are challenging to control.

Another piece of information has found that stress develops a negative impact on the performance level and productivity of the staff members and organisation (León and et. al., 2020) . While some of the workplace stress is excessive and normal and can interfere with the productivity and performance of the employee, it can negatively impact emotional and physical health (Prof. Olawumi D. Awolusi 2020).

On the other hand, stress is not always bad, but minimum stress can help stay focused and deal with the new challenges at the workplace. Under this, if the employees feel more stressed, it will cause absenteeism and not perform the job effectively (Gema Albort-Morant 2020).

According to Amanda W. G. van Loon 2020, the impact of the stress is to reduce the effectiveness as well as productivity. Its effect of absenteeism is noticeable and minimise productivity, and employees will be under press and stress. In context to this, staff members under stress feel less inclined to channel energy into solving issues and also make continuous improvement. To address the issues related to stress, the organisation can spend money and time, and it will help identify the arisen problems effectively

According to Dr Jermaine M Ravalier 2020, due to more stressed staff members being absent from work because of the stress, they cannot bale to perform their work or duties to usual standards and suffer from other health-related issues can develop stress. Significantly, these factors affect the business operations due to the lack of resources and loss of experience and knowledge, which can also affect the other staff members. If the employees are absent, then in this case productivity of the company will be impacted negatively. It will also develop a negative effect on the profit level of the company.

According to Taryn White 2020, Morale and motivation are the main factors that positively impact the performance and productivity of the business. These factors are related to enhancing productivity as they make the employees more stressed at all levels. If an employer cannot provide a positive working environment to employees, then, in this case, the employees will not be able to perform effectively, and it will reduce their motivation level at the workplace. It may harm the profit level of the organisation.

According to Joungyoun Kim 2020, staff turnover many enhance and experienced the staff members who may leave the company. The employees leave the company because they feel more stressed at the workplace, which negatively impacts their work. It is a primary reason to enhance staff turnover.

On the other hand, recruitment is a primary process of an organisation, and it is the responsibility of the recruiter or human resource management to hire well qualified and capable employees so that they can able to perform the job responsibilities effectively. At the time of peak load, the company hires low skilled employees relatively over low pay scale so that they would be able to complete their targets without expanding much over employees. It develops a negative impact on business development along with its performance (Nikeeta Sunil Bhosle 2020).

Another author added that training is one of the most significant parts of a company because it helps enhance staff members' skills, knowledge, and core competencies to perform better. Due to high cost, firms cannot provide the proper training to staff members, and they feel low, and it negatively impacts the performance (Townsend, McDonald, and Cathcart, 2017).

According to Spence Laschinger and Nosko 2015, the staff members who feel stressed and coming into the work are less productive and efficient than usual and combined with the staff members' absenteeism and low motivation and morale. It will negatively impact the productivity as well as the performance of an organisation. Under this, if the employees will not be motivated, they cannot perform in a better manner, and it negatively affects the organisational performance and profit level.

An author mentioned in a case study that It is complex to maintain a better customer service level with absence of the staff members, high turnover, motivation and morale issues, inefficiencies, and a low productivity level. Therefore, the stress can result in issues related to customer services. If a company cannot resolve customers' issues, it will develop a

negative impact on it and will not visit again. It will negatively impact the business and its productivity level (Sommerlad, 2016).

In an organisation, communication is essential at all levels. If the communication among employer and employees will not be positive or better, then, in this case, their relationship is negatively impacted. On the other hand, the main reason for making the relationship harmful is not to include the staff members in decision-making at the workplace (Sinclair and Cheung, 2016).

According to Shuman 2013, those employees who feel angry, withdrawn, and irritable have low motivation and morale. It develops a negative impact on the team dynamic and communication. If the communication among employees will not be proper, then, in this case, they are not working with each other in a team and from this, conflict will arise. It develops a negative impact on the relationship between employer and employees.

Workplace violence refers to threat or violence against employees. It can occur inside and outside the workplace, ranging from verbal abuse and threats to physical homicide and assaults. Workplace violence is a developing concern for staff members and employer nationwide. It is a kind of violence that is usually in the form of a physical threat and creates a risk to the health and safety of the staff members. Based on National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health, a worker, criminal intent, customers, and personal relationship intent all the violence categories at the workplace (Schnall, Dobson and et al., 2018).

According to Sansbury, Graves and Scott, 2015, Workplace violence can be related to the incidents where the employees are assaulted, threatened, and abused by other people. It may have a severe negative consequence for employees affected and their families. Violence is a heterogeneous and complex phenomenon. The stress and violence at the workplace both impact the productivity and performance of the organisation. The firm can provide a better workplace to work effectively and focus on attaining the specific aims and objectives significantly.

The organisations should pay more attention to workforce engagement and the morale of staff members. In case most staff members are experiencing a negative stress level, then in this case, communication and teamwork can suffer (Root and Brown, 2014).

The organisations should pay more attention to workforce engagement and the morale of staff members. In case most staff members are experiencing a negative stress level, then in this case, communication and teamwork can suffer (Root and Brown, 2014).

Another author added, the organisations can conduct a survey related to the employee opinion to measure the engagement, regarding the employee's absenteeism and stress from disability management point, duration of the stress too often more than the absences from the other causes. At the workplace, violence impact employees who attack directly (Martins, Nico2020).

Workplace violence is a kind of threat against workers. It can occur outside the workplace, from verbal abuse to physical assaults (Richards and Freeman, 2012). It is one of the leading causes related to job deaths. It can impact and include the consumers, staff members Etc.

Violence is a kind of demerit and disadvantage for an organisation. If, at the workplace, violence will be arising, then employees will not work effectively, and the chances of absenteeism will be enhanced (Ram, 2018).

They will not perform better, and conflict will arise among the staff members at the workplace. So, the manager must develop a positive working environment and determine the issues which arise at the workplace. A manager should identify the positive or better solutions to the arisen issues efficiently. On the other hand, a manager can communicate with its employees and ask them about any violence and misshapeness. In this kind of issues, employees feel demotivated and stress. The violence can be related to mental harassment, physical abuse Etc. In context to this, these aspects can help make the practical solutions concerned with the firm. These impact on productivity as well as profit level of the firm in a significant manner (Perrucci, 2017).

On the other hand, to prevent the workplace from any violence, management should develop effective procedures and policies and respond to incidents of any violence. The manager should develop a workplace violence prevention programme and a manual of standard operating procedures. In context to this, it is complex to assure that all the staff members know about policies and understand all workplace claims that will need to investigate promptly. An employer should encourage all the employees to log and report all the threats and incidents of workplace violence (Park, Cho and Hong, 2015).

On the other hand, a company should provide post-traumatic counselling services and stress debriefing sessions which will aids workers to overcome violent incidents (Oh, Uhm and Yoon, 2016).

Violence is the activity that impacts the performance of the organisation negatively. The organisations analysed to ascertain the impact of violence can be divided into physical and emotional violence (Offer, 2012).

According to Luis C.deBaca Griffin and Thomas Black 2020, Physical violence includes physical abuse of the employees from the employer side on the happening of any misshapen. These kinds of activities are prohibited as per the directions given by the government and the different legislation required to follow by an organisation.

More information has found that Physical abuse on employee mistake is unethical and results in the levy of hefty fines on such situations. Also, it will result in loss of the performance of an organisation and finally diminishes the goodwill of an organisation (U. Ill. L. Rev 2020).

Another author mentioned that such acts directly negatively impact the operations of employees and reduce their productivity and will be led to the overall decrement of the product and sales, which negatively affects the performance of an organisation due to selling of the smaller number of products in comparison to demand in the market (Nielsen and et al., 2015).

Another kind of violence within an organisation and impacts performance is emotional violence. It can be ascertained as the pressure created from the employer side to complete the work on time or even lose their job. It has two kinds of negative impacts upon an organisation, but both have their influence over an organisation's financial strength. It diminishes the image of employer and organisation in front of their stakeholders, and last, this will negatively impact the number of intangible assets. Customers and employees both do not want to associate with such a company that indulges in these activities. This will result in financial loss in the future period (Netterstrøm, 2012).

Another negative impact that can be ascertained from this kind of violence is the strict action from the tribunals against the organisations. In this regard, they must pay the fines, which impacts their performance as a large amount of money will be paid to employees in compensation. Loss of investors and government support impacts the overall strength of an organisation (Meyer and et al., 2015).

2.11 Workplace-violence policy development:

An organization must have a policy that reduces workplace violence and threats. Thus, an organization must overcome workplace violence and boost performance and sales within a specific timeframe (Mao, J. and Wu, Q. 2020).

Documenting policies and processes may help prevent workplace violence. These policies may include organizational programs and policies for developing co-worker and leadership practices for dealing with workplace violence and behavioral adjustments such as training in violence management, risk assessment, and follow-up (Bentley et al., 2013, p. 363). In a study by Mohamad et al (2021), the absence of regulations limiting workplace violence might have adverse repercussions. The hospitals evaluated the lack of violence prevention and management. 87.31% of resident physicians indicated implementing additional standards and procedures to safeguard doctors as the greatest option to minimize workplace violence. A violence reporting system that incorporates security guards and security video systems should be required to reduce workplace violence danger. Aytaç & Dursun (2012) agree with organizational policies and processes to prevent workplace violence and hostility. Policies may improve employee well-being. This shows staff that management supports

them in providing excellent patient care. According to Aytac and Dursun, a productive working environment may be created by implementing organizational policies and procedures geared toward reducing aggressiveness and violence in the workplace (2012).

According to Farmer (2020), throughout the last ten years, legislation has been submitted that encourages efficient actions against aggressive kids to assist instructors. Sadly, these proposals have yet to garner the backing of a significant portion of the parliamentary body. In healthcare institutions, implementing a zero-violence policy might prove beneficial as it prepares the ground for a limited conflict between staff members and patients and emphasizes the significance of avoiding abusive and aggressive behaviour.

Bond, S. A. et al. (2010) explain that a business must assist workers by building a culture with honest rules, practices, and metrics. This entails giving managers and organizations tools to change organizational climates to reduce workplace bullying and improve employee health, happiness, and support. (Pihl-Thingvad et al., 2019, p. 554) Emphasizes the importance of exposure frequency in building a complete framework to prevent workplace violence. Recognizing the Occupational Safety and Health Act of 1970 may assist in building a policy that requires employers to “operate a place of work free from known dangers that are causing or likely to cause death or severe bodily damage to his employees.” Hartley et al. (2015, p. 83) recommended multi-level collaboration to reduce workplace violence. Mohamad et al. (2021) add that monitoring based on violence frequency may reveal a progressive symptom worsening even after symptom development stops. It would allow preemptive intervention before major occurrences or staff trauma responses. Each research above provided a foundation for workplace prevention.

Threat Assessment:

Company should consider the spectrum of possible violence and the likelihood of those issues. It will also assist an organisation to reduce or overcome violence in the company's working environment and achieve better results within a predetermined time (Loss prevention crime 2020).

Security surveys and measures:

It introduces an effective and essential way an organisation can reduce the negative impact of workplace violence. In this, the leading role of an organisation is to maintain an environment that increases physical safety and reduce negatively. Thus, it is the most effective way which helps both organisations to increase their performance (Ibrahim Alrammah 2021).

Incident management:

A multi-disciplinary team of administration and many other resources work with each other to diffuse, mitigate, and prevent incidents of threats or violence. Therefore, this way also supports the organisation to overcome violence in the working environment and achieve better results. Without this, the company cannot satisfy their employees and not retain workers for a long time (Lila de Tantillo 2021).

Crisis response plan:

Plan that described procedures and distributed to team members during an existing incident. Thus, it will support the organisation in retaining workers for a long time and accomplishing better outcomes within a given time duration (Patrick Brandful Cobbinah 2020).

Whistleblower programs:

In this way, each worker knows that workplace violence is not tolerated, and the proper action will be taken if violence or threats occur. It will also be a practical and essential way an organisation can overcome the effects of violence on employees and their performance (Robbie Bishop-Monroe 2021).

Training:

It introduces as a primary and most significant way to support an organisation to retain employees by providing accurate training section to them. The company's primary role is to educate workers on techniques designed to deal with conflict resolution and stress reductions (Andrew J. Beamish 2020).

As per the point of view of Bob Turner, 2016, the effect of these kinds of confrontations of violence can be broad spread within an enterprise. For instance, there is an actual cost related to these types of incidents. In 2012 a survey conducted by the Society of HRM, that approximately 37% of the organisations reported a loss of performance and productivity, while around 34% of the businesses noted employee's replacement costs as an output of the clash. Over half of the organisations claimed that there was an extra cost related to these circumstances regarding management time and expenditure (Guillory, 2021). Thus, work-related violence is a significant impact that negatively affects performance and reputation.

According to Matt McClellan, 2011, Partner violence is also known as domestic violence that negatively impacts performance and success. Such violence or threats are commonly viewed as an individual problem and related to someone's home life. It is the biggest issue in the workplace because the behaviour of employees influences the workplace and is expensive to workers. It introduces a pattern of abusive activity or behaviour that an individual completes controlling a partner. This behaviour can be sexual, emotional, psychological and physical. A wrongdoer is often a male, and the individual being mistreated is a female, but women wrongdoers M. J., & Enright, R. D. (2021).

Furthermore, domestic violence occurs in all kinds of relationships, including married, heterosexual, unmarried, gay, bisexual, transgender and lesbian, and it touches all economic groups. Thus, workplace violence is classified into different parts, adversely impacting the performance and growth of an organisation (section 14 of the Equality Act 2006).

2.12 The ways to overcome workplace violence and psychological stress:

According to David Quezada (2018), workplace violence is related to any threatening act or threat of physical violence, disruptive behaviour, and harassment at the company's workplace. It negatively impacts the employee motivation and encouragement towards the operational activities.

In addition to this, it includes workers and consists of visitors, clients to job sites within the organisation (Hannula, Suoranta and Vadén, 2014). Usually, it is a form of physical abuse or threat that directly create a risk in relation to the health and safety of employees at a workplace, which may reduce their motivational level within the organisation (Munn and et al., 2014).

In the Humphries, B., 2017's context, the HR manager of the company plays a significant role in reducing and developing a positive environment within the organisation to motivate workers so that they can effectively perform their duties and attain their set targets. Although workplace violence occurs anywhere and to anyone, that may increase the risk factors at the workplace. Apart from this, the manager needs to ensure that workers perform their duties in a healthy and positive working Humphries B., 2017 environment so that they can quickly improve their protection and at the same time also make all the workers able to handle any violence. If workplace violence arises at the workplace, it negatively impacts employees' mind set and organisational image. This is the main reason that number of employees left the organisation and increase employee turnover. For reducing this, the manager is responsible for making policies and strategies to build a positive work environment (Daudt, Mossel and Scott, 2013). This may lead to reducing the chances of any violence at the workplace and with employees as well. In this context, employees' best protection can establish a zero-tolerance policy against workplace violence by workers. For this, the employer and the manager of an organisation need to develop a workplace violence prevention program into the existing accident presentation program. This may help in reducing the violence at the workplace and also improve the worker's performance. With this, a company can quickly establish a positive and healthy work environment that directly contributes to enhancing the marketplace's positive brand image (Brannen, 2017). In addition to this, some protection can be an offer by an employer to their workers are as follows:

Provide safety education for workers to quickly understand what conduct is not acceptable and what to do when they witness workplace violence and know how to protect themselves from the violence at the workplace (Wildemuth, 2016).

In addition to this, secure the workplace is also an effective way for an employer to protect their workers. They need to install video surveillance, alarm system, extra lighting and minimise the access of outsiders. With the help of this, the manager of an organisation can quickly secure the workplace (Tesch, 2013).

Providing drop safes is also an effective way to protect the workers from handling the cash on hand. Along with this, keeping a minimal amount of cash is also a way of reducing violence at the workplace. An employer should ensure that keeping less amount of cash in registers at the time of evening and late-night hours is also helpful in reducing the chances of any violence with workers (Dumay and Cai, 2015).

Furthermore, instruct workers not to enter any location wherein they feel unsafe and unfavourable. For this, introducing a buddy system is also a part of protection in which the employer provides an escort service to the workers in a complex and dangerous situation.

Development of policies and procedures that the home health care providers may help protect workers in clearly hazardous situations (Mackert and et al., 2014).

According to Julie Copeland (2018), workplace violence is a serious issue that may directly affect the worker's mindset at the workplace. The same also makes them demotivated towards the operational activities. It also may increase workers stress at the workplace, which creates a hostile work environment within the organisation. In addition to this, workplace violence is the threat, intimidation and use of weapons that cause bodily harm to the workers. In an instant, an assault can turn deadly and end in multiple homicides. In this context, some ways can help in reducing workplace violence within the company. All these can be understood by following ways or solution:

2.12.1 Identify risk factors including vulnerable employees:

In a business organisation, the manager needs to determine the potential risk facts to reduce the chances of negative aspects and prevent violence. In this context, carry out the worksite assessment is also helpful in aware workers and the work environment more positive (Mukhopadhyay and Gupta, 2014).

In this various worker are includes who:

- Deliver goods or services and passengers
- Work alone or in small groups
- Exchange money with the public
- Work in high-crime areas
- Have extensive contact with the public

2.12.2 Formulate a Workplace Violence anticipation program:

In this manager of the company establishing a zero-tolerance policy or strategies towards violence that help workers to understand the behaviour of any kind of violence at the workplace (Lather and St. Pierre, 2013). This type of policy may build a protective work environment wherein employees may efficiently perform their task and make their performance more productive or stress-free (Isaacs, 2014). This zero violence policy of the entity will help in reducing psychological stress from the mind of individuals working with

the firm. This policy will enable the organisation to gain more productive results as staff performances will induce and become more productive with eased stress.

2.12.3 Implement security measures:

It is also essential for a company manager to keep the working environment secure and protective in which they accomplished all the equipment that makes the workplace secure (Kitchin and Tate, 2013). The manager also provides guidance and instructs workers not to enter into an unfamiliar location where they feel unsafe (Riedl, Davis and Hevner, 2014). Further, providing safety and protective environment to the workers is also beneficial to building employee motivation. These security measures help the management develop a safe workplace and healthy environment within the organisation and encourage staff to speak up for change as they are well aware that the company's measures will favour the injustice happening.

2.12.4 Provide proper training and policies:

It is a crucial way to overcome workplace violence within the business environment. In this, a manager needs to educate workers to recognise, avoid, and diffuse violent situations by taking part in personal safety training programs. With the assistance of this, workers can quickly reduce their stress level and at the same time also improve their working activities at the workplace. Along with this, they alter supervisors to any situation towards safety and security (Reynolds and et al., 2014). By avoiding employees travel alone at an unfamiliar location. Make sure that employees are kept minimal money and also includes ID into community settings.

Apart from this, some motivational theories help business organisations motivate their workers by reducing their stress level and workplace violence. As a result, it helps to improve the personnel' service quality in reference to the companies' functional areas. Thus, the HR manager of a company needs to use effective and appropriate theories of motivation that might have a positive influence on the worker's performance at the workplace and at the same time also make them able to handle a complex situation that arises workplace (Reynolds and et al. 2014).

2.13 Theories to comply the issue

2.13.1 The effect of Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs

As Robert Tanner, 2019 stated the psychologist Abraham Maslow has established a theory that proposes that individuals get satisfied with five basic needs arranged in a hierarchical manner, which also acts as a motivational factor. In this, Maslow suggested that people first seek to satisfy their lowest level of need, motivating them to work toward satisfying each higher level of need. Hence, Maslow's hierarchical need theory is considered a most essential and straightforward motivational tool for a manager to apply and understand the

behaviour of employees and keep them motivated toward their work. With the implementation of this theory manager of an organisation will leads to a positive impact on the behaviour of its employees at the workplace. The main reason behind this is that need of employee's changes constantly with time, and changes happen at the workplace.

Hence with the implementation of this theory, managers of an organisation become able to analyse the need of employees and the reason behind their changing behaviour. With the help of this theory, it can fulfil the need of the employees by aligning with the objective over which they perform work; as a result, the employees get motivated toward work to fulfil their objectives and satisfy their need by working well over the objectives. This, in turn, also helps improve employees' behaviour as they started focusing on their work despite comparing appreciation and opportunities gained by others. This reflects the positive behaviour of employees at the workplace, with their fellow members, and the accomplishment of their work. These all contribute toward improving the performance of employees and developing job satisfaction among them by reducing the stress of the workplace (Robert Tanner, 2019).

The Hierarchy of needs are as follows:

Physiological Needs: It is an essential human requirement in survival as they cannot without meeting these types of needs. Thus, the company's manager is responsible for providing these types of needs to make them able to survive. Mainly, it includes food, clothes, shelter, and water. All these are essential needs; thus, managers need to provide them adequate wages to efficiently fulfil their needs and reduce their stress level at the workplace. To perform their best in the job, employees must fulfil all these needs to become more productive and cheerful. The theory is of motivation and best relates with keeping staff highly motivated, in regards to which fulfilling basic needs will enable people to work with a positive attitude and make sure to develop and safe environment around themselves.

Security Needs: This level of Hierarchy is related to protection from the elements, absence of violence and financial security at the workplace.

If these types of needs are not fulfilled, workers feel stressed and demotivated towards the job responsibilities at the workplace. Thus, a manager needs to provide safety needs like adequate medical and retirement benefits to prevent stress and workplace violence. With the assistance of this, employees are easily retained in the organisation for a more extended period and at the same time also loyal to their job activities. Once the employee feels safe and secure, then only they can develop a surrounding like one. Thus, the security need fulfilment enables the workforce to ensure their safety and render others the same sense of feeling, which encourages them to stay productive and work with people in the best way possible by taking humble approaches to communicate and develop relationships.

Social needs: This type of needs is related to friendship, trust, acceptance and many other social needs. At the workplace, nobody is social as all these are silently work. This may reduce the interaction among employees, which may reduce motivation and at the same time

also increase the job stress at the workplace. Here, the supervisor of the company will be responsible for promoting and providing friendly and collaborative culture at the workplace in which workers spend a little time together and share their views and opinions. By this, they easily maintain better relationships and also reduce their stress level at the workplace.

Esteem Needs: It is related to the confidence, self-esteem, respect of others, and achievement at the workplace. All these types of needs help workers as they can play a pivotal role. It is also helpful in motivating employees by providing them awards, promotions and prizes to acknowledge the job responsibilities. If these types of needs are satisfied, workers then feel motivated toward the company and its activities.

Self- Actualisation Needs: This is the last level of motivation in which employees desire to accomplish everything they can motivate. It defines workers potentials, growth and experiences that directly contribute to making them unable to perform their duties effectively and, at the same time, also may aid in reducing the stress level at the workplace.

All the stages of motivation theory will help the organisation, management, and leadership be most effective. As they fulfil their needs, they will be kept motivated and encouraged to work most productively. This also influences their behaviour and working attitude. People do not just make sure to develop a positive environment amongst themselves but also make the best of their talents to keep others on the upbeat track, automatically reducing violence and a hostile competitive environment within the firm (Author 2021).

2.13.2 The effect of Theory X and Theory Y

As per Tushar Bhatia's (2016), Theory X and Theory Y are considered to be some of the best employee motivation theory which helps in organisational behaviour analysis so that human resource practices can practice. In this theory, there are two different attitudes defined toward how the workforce can be improved. A company that deals in cutting and shaping up tyres or wheels to make them better for getting them attached over vehicles reduce accidents. In such kind of work, the pressures over employees are relatively higher in both term, i.e. physical as well as mental pressure that they get from their seniors. This is happening because to give a proper shape to wheels employee has to put more efforts into their own work as a result of which it creates stress at their job that can also be seen in their behaviour toward work.

Hence, to overcome this, the manager of an organisation can implement Theory X and theory Y at the workplace to keep its employees motivated and reduce work stress. This will create a positive result within the employee's behaviour, and it provides a platform to understand the changing dynamic of employee behaviour at the workplace.

Both theories seem to represent some unrealistic extremes, and it has been assumed that most of the employees fall between these poles (Author 2021).

According to Nathan A. Heller, PhD (2020), the McGregor's X-Y theories serve as a strategic concept for continuous processes that facilitate organizational growth. It is a combination of procedures that guarantees a harmonious coexistence of the system and independence at work, both of which are likely to contribute to employee motivation. This, have a positive influence on the behaviour of an organisation's employees as to when they get a place where they can work freely without any pressures then they will be able to put more efforts toward the accomplishment of work. In addition to this, it also helps in bringing coordination among employees as a stress-free environment helps in improving their relationships with other fellow partners.

As a result of which employees prefer to work coordinate as a team with others. This, in turn, also help an organisation to enhance their productivity by getting a highly motivated workforce that contributes to accomplishing organisational goals (Author 2021).

As per the viewpoint of Herzberg, 2017, job stress is considered a factor that creates dissatisfaction among employees regarding their job, which also affects the performance of an organisation. In addition to this, it also creates conflicts among employees, which created negative behaviour among workers at the workplace, affecting their performance. Hence it is essential to remove the job stress from the workplace environment to keep employees motivated and align toward the organisational goals.

According to Rabiah Yusuf 2020, The organisation that deals in the banking sector are one of the most competitive and innovative sectors where players always bring up a new service or method to create value in front of their customers and defeat their rivals. This creates pressure over higher management people as they started trying to bring innovation in their practices to attract a more significant number of customers. This pressure of winning the race leads top management to pressure their employees working over lower levels to perform well to achieve higher targets. As a result, it creates mental pressure on employees as they have to face voice violence from their superiors in terms of their work and practices. This directly influences their behaviour at a workplace that gets hostile toward superiors and other fellow partners at the workplace, which creates dissatisfaction related to work and job.

Furthermore, McGregor theory X and theory Y play a substantial role in motivating workers in the workplace (Loewenson, 2021). Using this theory, the company manager quickly makes their workers motivated towards the job activities at the workplace as it is based on the individual behaviour at working activities which may contribute to enhancing the overall productivity level of the workers.

Theory X: This theory assumes that employees have little ambition like dislike, avoid responsibilities, and require close supervision. As workers do not like to work hard and also tries to avoid it. In this, workers are responsible for handling this type of issues or threaten to motivate people to work hard. The main reason behind this is that employees generally dislike taking responsibilities. Furthermore, workers resist changes. With the assistance of this, workers feel motivated and encouragement towards the functional responsibilities at the

workplace and, at the same time, also make them unable to put their best (Samira Soheili Rad 2020).

Theory Y: In this, workers can distinguish their work activities as calming and regular mode. As they prefer their mental and physical effort while performing their job activities. Along with this, they can use their self-direction to attain their organisational objectives. In this, individual are internally motivated to attain their set objectives. For this type of employee, the company manager prefers democratic management (Karamolla Daneshfard 2020).

Both theories are influential as they help in motivating workers towards the set goals and intentions and consecutively also make them able to handle any situation at the workplace. In this context, Theory X and Theory Y are more effective for a business organisation that help in motivating workers to manage their working activities and attain their set target effectively. Alternatives for individuals to contribute to the company's overall success should be provided. Additionally, it promotes cooperation among team members and involves them in judgement call so they may effectively and methodically achieve their goal. This theory of motivation is used for keeping people more engaged within the firm. Once they are involved with the work and majorly connect with the company's agendas, the workforce makes sure to work in the best environment, which needs to be provided by management. However, on their part as well, they make efforts to keep violence low and make sure to encourage their colleagues to work with positive and harmless attitudes and competitive minds.

2.13.3 The positive and negative impact of motivational theories upon behaviours of employees.

Motivational theories play a crucial role in shaping employee behaviors within an organization, influencing their attitudes, performance, and overall job satisfaction. Understanding the positive and negative impacts of these theories can provide valuable insights into how to effectively leverage motivational strategies to foster a productive and engaged workforce while mitigating potential drawbacks.

Motivational theories, such as Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs and Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, emphasize the importance of addressing employees' intrinsic needs and providing meaningful work experiences. When employees feel their needs are met, they are more likely to be motivated, leading to increased productivity and higher levels of engagement in their tasks and responsibilities.

Motivational theories that focus on factors such as recognition, responsibility, and achievement can contribute to higher levels of job satisfaction among employees. When employees feel recognized and valued for their contributions, they are more likely to

experience a sense of fulfillment and purpose in their roles, fostering a positive work environment and reducing turnover rates.

Implementing motivational strategies that prioritize a supportive work culture and provide opportunities for skill development and career advancement can significantly boost employee morale. By fostering a sense of belonging and investment in the organization, employees are more likely to demonstrate commitment, loyalty, and a proactive attitude toward achieving organizational goals.

As per the viewpoint of Russell Huebsch, 2019, stress at the workplace not only affect employee morale and health. A stressful workplace manifests employees in the form of usual behaviour and ailment which come up from them. This work stress can only be reduced by making the working environment motivational and more comfortable by educating management about how employee stress can be reduced. It is essential to reduce the employee's stress at the workplace as it has a vast influence over employees' performance and leads to creating several issues within an organisation.

According to Annie Høgh 2020, The main issues created due to work stress in organisations are increased absenteeism and turnover within the workplace. This happens when there is a favouritism factor present within the organisation which create clashes between the employees. In addition to this, it also creates disputes among employees, which creates dissatisfaction among other workers who do not get a promotion or another appraisal opportunity, which in turn affects their performance and behaviour at the workplace. In order to overcome this issue of job stress, an organisation can implement motivation theories to keep its employees motivated toward their work and hence reduce the stress at the workplace.

In addition, the organisations can reduce the stress at the workplace by evaluating the performance or organising informal meetings for determining the opinion of employees regarding their job security, the overall effectiveness of management and advancement. Apart from this, the social involvement of employees with their fellow workers can support in reducing the level of stress (Noel Carrol 2020).

According to Marwa Moses Siruri 2020, this behaviour can also be improved with the help of motivation at the workplace, which influences employees to work toward accomplishing their job targets to achieve more. Hence, being a bank, the organisation has to face several issues regarding its employees' negative behaviour and job dissatisfaction due to work pressure or stress among employees. Therefore, to overcome such issues, the banking organisation must implement Herzberg's theory of motivation, which is also called the two-factor theory, which relies on the principle of job satisfaction and dissatisfaction that act independently from each other. This theory divided factor present into two parts which lead to job satisfaction as well as dissatisfaction. By separating these two factors, the banking organisation manager can focus on improving their relationships with employees and developing a positive environment at the workplace, motivating employees to work

effectively. The implementation of Herzberg's theory of motivation will have a positive impact on the behaviour of employees in the following ways:

Job enlargement:-

Under this section of enlargement, Herzberg brought an idea of removing the control from the employees and at the same time asked to increase the accountability as well as responsibilities of employees at their job. This will create a positive influence on the presentation and behaviour of personnel by getting opportunity over the workplace, and employees feel more motivated toward new task as well as they started feeling favourable toward the management (Humphries, 2017).

This, in turn, helps develop their positive attitude toward management and other employees, which also contribute toward improving their performance within the workplace. This, in turn, helps develop their positive attitude toward management and other employees and contribute toward improving their performance within the workplace and reducing cases of violence and conflicts between employees or maybe even in teams(Humphries, 2017).

Job rotation:

This section discusses the ability of employees to create new projects and units that work toward pressing the problem. Under this, Herzberg suggests encouraging a proactive attitude toward solving problems instead of being delegated to it by the supervisor. This will help keep the employees motivated toward their work as their issues are resolved at the workplace, which creates a positive image of management in front of the workforce. This brings positive result at a workplace where employees try to take the risk despite avoiding it which help in improving the performance of employees and organisation as well along with keeping them in the safe, positive environment where everyone gets the chance to grow and less possibility of people being jealous of one another (Novikov and Novikov, 2013).

Job enrichment:

It refers to the process where employees get direct and regular feedback over their productivity and job performance. This also helps an organisation motivate its employees, as by adding this feature within their process, the company would be able to keep its employees motivated (McCusker and Gunaydin, 2015). This is because by getting regular feedback on their performance, employees would realise the importance of their work in their management. It will further support in creating a feeling of intrinsic interest and fulfilment of employee need or expectation through their work itself. Hence it helps in bringing a positive impact over the performance and help people in working with positive work attitude making their behaviour, in the same manner, to keep the best of their personality ahead and keep their violent and unfair actions out of the entity's work environment as well as the behaviour of employees at the workplace.

As per the viewpoint of Anar Nasibov, 2015, motivation refers to inspiring people to perform actions toward achieving specific goals and objectives. With the implementation of motivational theory, organisations will reduce their employees' work stress and

psychological pressure at the workplace. Hence, motivational theories positively impact the employee's behaviour within the organisation, which in turn help create a positive environment at the workplace. The following points describe the positive impact of motivational theory on the workforce:

Employee performance:

Motivation act as a promoter that influence employees to perform confidently. By motivating employees, the organisations will keep their employees happy, which creates an inner urge to perform better and achieve something while working effectively (Smith, 2015).

This is because by using extrinsic and intrinsic factors, an organisation can inspire employees to remain motivated toward their work and job. This, in turn, creates more job satisfaction among employees and hence they put more efforts into their task to achieve the best result. It further supports the company in developing a loyal base of employees at the workplace who work toward accomplishing organisational goals and objective.

Productivity:

Motivational theories help in improving the working environment of the company, which in turn, works toward influencing the employees to work more effectively to achieve something. A better relation and attractive incentives over the achievement help employees remain happy and be able to accomplish their goals or objective. This, in turn, also contributes to improving their working capability, which results in increasing the productivity and performance of the organisation (Gioia and et al., 2013). This is because happy and satisfied employees are more productive than dissatisfied worker.

2.13.4 McClelland's Theory of Needs

This theory is basically evolved by Sir David McClelland in 1960s. He stated in his theory of motivation that the three core emotional needs of an individual are generally acquired by them in their life journeys. These particular demands also evolve and change over time. Most of these requirements are categorized as affiliation, power or achievement. Any person's motivation, effectiveness and vision is generally influenced by these three given factors as per their life experiences. McClelland's theory is also known to be three needs theory or as the learners needs theory. As per him, we always have three motivating factors, amongst which one is always dominant motivating factor for us regardless of gender, caste, culture, or race. This depends upon the life experiences of the individuals that which factor would be his dominant factor amongst others (Chen and et. al., 2020). Therefore, this theory is actually dependent on the life style followed by the persons and experiences he had over the years from such experiences and styles.

2.13.5 Hans Selye Stress Theory: Selye's Syndrome

General adaptation syndrome (GAS), commonly referred to as Selye syndrome and first recognized in 1936, is an adverse physiologic reaction to stress. Dr. Selye found that attention alters the body's biochemistry in GAS, a three-phase hormone-mediated physiological

reaction to stress that ultimately results in sickness and death. He did not just assert that stress causes illness in his view. He instead based his theory on sound biological principles.

The Three Stages of General Adaptation Syndrome:

- i. Alarm reaction: The HPA's immediate initial response to stress is the alarm response. Two crucial stress chemicals, cortisol and adrenaline, are dramatically increased during this phase by the adrenal glands. Because of this, the body and brain detect impending danger and enter "fight or flight" mode. The short-lived symptoms of an alert reaction include a rapid heartbeat, heart palpitations, migraine, and digestive problems. Typically, alarm reactions don't last more than a day or two.
- ii. Building resistance: The second phase of the PhD. Selye's GAS and fresh scientific findings is building resistance. This stage of symptoms is known as the non-specific stress response, according to Dr. Selye. It cannot be quantified, hence it is non-specific. Therefore, it cannot be identified with a blood test. Three indications of increasing resistance, according to Dr. Selye. The first is how stress affects an individual, and the second is how the body reacts to stress. Third, these reactions can eventually affect the interior organs. Following the conclusion of the alarm reaction, the resistance-building process begins and can last anywhere between months and years.
- iii. Exhaustion: The last stage of Dr. Selye's GAS is exhaustion. The exhaustion phase was a brand-new scientific finding, just as the resistance-building phase. As shown by the harm brought on by persistently high stress hormones, a person is susceptible to fatal illnesses at this point. In this final stage, signs and symptoms may include high blood pressure, ulcers, heart disease, kidney disease, a higher risk of cancer, infections, anxiety, or depression.

2.14 Justification or key findings

From the above mentioned literature review this is being analysed that workplace stress and violence are two major aspects which are seen within business due to which employee feel demotivated and acquire higher earning as well. In order to deal with such situations motivational theories are required to be used so that organisation may overcome with such threats and possibilities. For overcoming these barriers such theories are required to be inhaled so that to develop appropriate insight and to manage such threats in proper manner. Besides this in order to develop appropriate motivation this is mandatory to provide such type of motivation to employees so that they can gain benefits in context of personal and professional aspects. Employee performance is the major aspect which is required to be provided by the business so that to have their employees and their skills at similar manner. On the other hand performance appraisal is the aspect which is needed by the organisation in order to develop their employees and their skills as well. The ultimate focus of all commercial ventures, both large and small, in the current marketplace is to improve their

efficiency and activities in order to achieve more expansion and success in the industry (Melé, 2021). Training is also creating value in adding higher experience in the capability enhancement of the employees which will be significant for them in achieving growth and success in their future. ChopCut Limited and ABC Limited are two medium size businesses that has its major concern over becoming the large business and wants to operate at international level, and for this, they are effectively concern over implement best and suitable innovation tools that are effective for the firm in developing their operations via reducing the stress among the employees. Therefore, it is crucial for the company or its executives to include the workforce in decision-making since they are intimately familiar with the operations of the firm and are able to provide wise recommendations for improving those operations.

Psychological violence is a growing big issue around the globe that impacts not only the well-being and health of workers, but also the performance and productivity of company. Work-related stress develops when an individual has the right and aptitude to cope with the expectations and necessities of their job are exceeded. There are different number of factors such as management style, work hours and interpersonal relationship can impact an employee's stress levels at work. Dangerous stress's level often show physical warning signs, such as heartburn, tension, headaches, fatigue and occurrence in body weight.

Therefore, psychological stress and violence are also influence upon employee's productivity. Decreased efficiency and effectiveness are two of the key repercussions and impacts of work-related stress on businesses. It may also happen when a workforce is under adverse or aggressive stress or anxiety brought on by their jobs. Employees who are experiencing psychological stress are more likely to invest their energies in ongoing improvement projects and original problem-solving activities. Therefore, less productive employee is not beneficial and effective for the growth and development of company within given time duration. In order to overcome and reduce such type of problem, company should provide accurate consideration to the workers and develop a cordial environment or surrounding that may need them to be productive and responsible.

The reason why these specific two organizations were chosen was to analyse the current situation regarding psychological stress and violence in workplace. The two organizations are very different in terms of operations. One is a complete professional and official environment other one is more of a manufacturing business. The business modalities are very different. The reason behind choosing two complete different approaches was to identify if two different organizations have similar pattern of performance effect after facing psychological stress.

2.15 Research Questions:

There have been many researches on the issue stating more or less similar outcomes of stress in workplaces. All the researches were previously done in educational institutions, health care institutions or corporations. Most of the researches were done in the United States. To understand the effects of workplace stress and violence in the United Kingdom, it was necessary to come along a working organization. Also after the pandemic, the work environments have changed a lot. The effects of leadership and communication has taken a turn. In my research, I have worked to shed light on two organization running in the UK to analyse the current scenario. In my research, three additional questions that provide focus on the topic are used to support one key research question.

The Main research question in my research is,

- How workplace stress and violence does effects on employee's performance in an organization.

While researching that, I came across a few more questions to resolve like,

- What are the kinds of stress and violence?
 - Who are the common victims?
- And,
- What is the role of the management in resolving the whole issue?

2.16 The researches that were considered are consolidated in below table.

Type	Title	Author's Name	Publishing Year
Book	Nielsen, M. BPost-traumatic stress disorder as a consequence of bullying at work and at school. A literature review and meta-analysis. Aggression and violent behavior.	Nielsen, M. B	2015
Journal	Consumer aggression and frontline employees' turnover intention: The role of job anxiety, organizational support, and obligation feeling.	Raza, B., St-Onge, S. and Ali, M.	2021
Book	Bullying in the workplace: An occupational hazard.	Richards, H. and Freeman, S.	2012
Journal	Managing traumatic stress responses among clinicians: Individual and organizational tools for self-care	Sansbury, B. S., Graves, K. and Scott, W.	2015
Journal	Unhealthy work: Causes, consequences, cures.	Schnall, P. L., Dobson, M., and et. al.,	2018
Book	Qualitative psychology: A practical guide to research methods	Smith, J. A. ed	2015

Journal	Workplace violence and self-reported psychological health: coping with post-traumatic stress, mental distress, and burnout among physicians working in the emergency departments compared to other specialties in Pakistan	Zafar, W. and et. al.	2016
Online Journal	Stress and violence in the workplace	Johnson, P.R. and Indvik, J.	1996
Online Journal	The Cost of Violence/Stress at Work and the Benefits of a Violence/Stress Free Working Environment.	Hoel, Helge & Sparks, Kate & Cooper, Cary	2000
Online Journal	Workplace Violence Due to Job Stress	Adele Burney	2019
Online Journal	What to Do When Your Job Is Seriously Stressing You Out.	LAURIE ERDMAN	2015
Online Journal	Workplace Violence 2: The Impact on Business	Bob Turner	2016
Online Journal	WORKPLACE VIOLENCE: KEYS TO PROTECT YOUR EMPLOYEES	Copeland., J,	2018
Online Journal	Impact Of Stress On Employee Productivity, Performance And Turnover; An Important Managerial Issue.	Imtiaz, S.	2018
Online Journal	Preventing Workplace Violence.	Roberts. M	2019
Online Journal	Violence in the workplace	Heliyon	2019

List 2.16 List of Books and Journals that are reviewed

Chapter 3: Research Methodology

This research is playing significant role in providing work-life balance to employee so that they can minimise such practices which lead them to face workplace stress and minimises their productivity and involvement. This research is executed for the major purpose of developing understanding within individual so that they can recognise such aspects and factors which are causing them stress and work related issues. The present study will examine how stress and violence in the workplace affected employee behaviour.

3.1 Research Approach

This study uses a qualitative, descriptive method to achieve its goals. In order to better comprehend the essence of respondents' true experiences from their standpoints, phenomenological approaches are utilized to interact intimately with participants in their natural contexts, (Rossman & Rallis, 2017; Seidman, 2013). While studying issues or particular demographics for which only a limited amount of prior research has been done, phenomenological techniques can be effective (Creswell, 2014). There are also other

practical methods required by a researcher, such as analytical techniques and data presentation techniques. All these are significant and effective methods that will support an investigator to gather appropriate and relevant information about the field of study (Helen Kara 2020). However, to gather the real evidence, I have conducted a survey and arranged focused group discussions from where data were gathered to analyse a scenario. As the research does not completely depends on the gathered data, this is a miscellaneous approach combined with both qualitative and quantitative research method.

I have outlined the significance and importance of the data in this chapter with regard to each objective and research question. Various techniques have been used to gather information about the effects of emotional stress and violence in the workplace on a firm's performance. Among these are research methodology, research design, strategy, data collection techniques, research design, data sources and research instruments, i.e. interview, questionnaire, observation, group discussion Etc.

3.2 Role of the Researcher

The researcher serves as the instrument for data collection and analysis in mixed methods (Rossman & Rallis, 2017). It is crucial that the researcher identify any potential biases one might introduce to the study (Rossman & Rallis, 2017). I assisted as a professional for 9 years, and I supervised several teams for more than six years with following the experience. I believe my own experience in the industry by working with different people and observing workplace stress and violence helped me build a rapport with the participants of the questionnaire and Focused Group discussions. It helped me understand their experiences hence build a conclusion on the scenarios. However, I personally made sure that my personal experience does not by any means inspires or affects the understanding of other participant's experiences in the same issue. At the end of the research I added strategies to enhance the quality of data processing in the whole research outcome.

According to my personal opinion, stress and violence are frequent descriptors in any sector that might eventually develop, and the working environment significantly contributes to this issue. Last but not least, I consciously used a realist viewpoint as a theoretical lens through which to analyse research components and in the meaning-making process. I introduced this worldview to the design and process of this study. As a result of this philosophy, I had the epistemological conviction that knowledge is socially constructed and contextualized between individuals (Jones, Torres, & Arminio, 2014). In terms of ontology, I think that by examining these common knowledge constructions, it is possible to see reality as a construction (Jones et al., 2014). In terms of approach, my objective is to uncover significance in participants' accounts of their own experiences in order to foster the emergence of fresh perceptions of a phenomenon in a particular setting (Jones et al., 2014; Rossman & Rallis, 2017). I describe this worldview's significance on this study on purpose so that readers can comprehend the guiding principles of my choices, the analytical strategy I used, and how I made meaning of the findings (Jones et al., 2014).

3.3 Research Design:

It refers to a structure or plan for a study or a list of procedures and specifications for organising and monitoring a research project. In addition, research design can be identified as a master plan which shows the strategies of doing a research activity. Research design serves as a practical and helpful master plan of different methods and processes that should be applied to accumulate and evaluate information required by decision-maker makers (Cronje, Johannes C 2020). In this research, I have followed a combination of case study method following a pragmatist theory.

Case Study Method: Yin claims that in order to perform a case study, you must first consider the subject you are motivated to investigate (such as a fascinating disorder, initiative, community, or event), and then think about the concerns you want to address, (Yin2003).

According to Flyvbjerg, case study technique was initially employed largely for data exploration, and some academics still only utilize research papers for this purpose (2007). When the generalization of the circumstance or phenomena is unimportant, it is also employed for descriptive reasons. Although the separation of elements may present a challenge, case studies may be employed for explanatory objectives, such as in discontinuous standard statistical design (pre- and post-event investigations). Confirmatory studies are used to test the validity of current theories in this. As mentioned earlier, case studies conducted in the field of software development frequently adopt an improvement methodology, akin to action research; an example of this is the Quality assurance research, (Andersson and Runeson 2007b).

Case studies are very helpful when a number of conditions are met, as Yin suggests. "The study will analyze the phenomenon in context—and will study this context in detail," is one of the criteria. The place, conditions, and relationships all fall under the category of context in this type of inquiry. "The study will use and integrate multiple types of evidence to characterize the phenomena and context," is another need. Case studies efficiently combine qualitative and quantitative information in such a situation. One of the few methods that allows researchers to essentially convert some of their statistical data, such survey results, into narratives that are more qualitative is the use of case studies.

3.3.1 Justification to select a Case Study Method

The foundation for selecting a case study design will support portraying a good profile of respondents, events, and circumstances while gathering both type of data, Primary & Secondary. To study an issue that is already in the society, descriptive or qualitative design is more appropriate and accurate but a quantitative approach with a survey will support the current scenario of the issue as well. It also allows for a more accurate and in-depth evaluation of the people to be designed as variables, as well as the assortment of more data in a cost-effective manner. It allows for the collection of realistic research data. Supporting an

investigator in developing the origin based on facts or quality, supported by descriptive interpretations of archival data and material, is critical (Author 2021).

The case method in legal education, according to Christopher Columbus Langdell, Dean of Harvard Law School (1870–1895), was designed as a technique to systematize and simplify legal education by focusing on prior case law that advanced ideas or concepts. This project is based on case studies of two organisations. The first one is Chopcut Ltd. This is a tire producing company where all product of the company is made from advance technology and adequate quality of raw material. These products are available in different sizes and shapes in the market. In this organisation, some employees face psychological stress and workplace violence, which will highly influence the company's performance. It is a significant problem in a working environment of an organisation and highly impacts its performance in the marketplace. Another organization is a commercial Bank named ABC Bank where there are 1100 employees working in different but interrelated departments. Many of the employees in the bank are facing stress in the work environment everyday which results in their daily KPI. Recently, they face some issues related to psychological stress and workplace violence. It is a most significant issue that reduces motivation levels among employees. It will also influence the performance of the bank, which further results in low market share and poor image in the market. Therefore, to overcome this type of issue, both organisations need a market research, which will help them identify effective ways to reduce this issue? Companies should use different motivation theories and techniques that will support them in overcoming psychological stress and violence effectively (Author 2021).

As this issue is directly related to human behaviour and perspective of the employees, qualitative research supported by survey data seems to be the perfect way to gather and analyse data.

3.4 Philosophy of the Research

A research philosophy is defined as a set of beliefs and values that correspond to the nature of the reality that is being investigated. It has something to do with knowledge's nature. The assumptions formulated in research philosophy will provide adequate justification for how research is conducted. The three types of research philosophy include- pragmatist, interpretivism, and positivist. For this specific research, I have followed the Pragmatist philosophy as the research outcome is relying on a social reality but the actual consequences can be measured by the accumulated data. Pragmatist philosophy allows researchers to quickly gather relevant data and information in order to arrive at a valid conclusion that supports the social reality as well.

3.4.1 Justification behind choosing pragmatist philosophy

I chose the pragmatist philosophy for this research because it helped me to achieve better results by combining different research methods. Previous researchers used combined and multiple research designs, such as quantitative and qualitative, in this case (Walter and

Andersen, 2013). The focus is on challenging the value and significance of research data by consideration of its real-world implications, even though this approach is compatible with qualitatively dominant interpretive interpretations of socially created reality. In ChopCut and ABC Bank, where practice is tightly entwined or monitored, this is especially useful. In order to explore and comprehend the linkages between knowledge and action in context, I stepped beyond objectivist conceptualizations, which have dominated study in the field of quality management, employing pragmatism.

By eliminating different facets of the research topic at the design stage, pragmatism played a crucial role in guiding me toward selecting the right methodological options. A methodology that went beyond organizational paperwork to record employees' actual experiences was necessary for the investigation. Pragmatism assisted in identifying the necessity of deeply interacting with staff at the workplace in both firms. To augment the scant official record, a qualitative method including participant observation of the environment was necessary. Furthermore, pragmatism influenced my sampling techniques by assisting me in identifying information-rich respondents who were most likely to discuss their professional experiences and offer practical, practice-based insights.

3.5 Collection of data for the study

The research depends on both primary and secondary data sources to come up with proper and objective findings.

3.5.1 Primary data source:

Primary data introduces as data or information originated first hand by the investigator via direct experience and efforts, generally for the motive of addressing research issue (Walter and Andersen, 2013). It also identifies as the raw or first-hand data. Given that the study is conducted by the company or agency, which requires a variety of resources, including human resources and investment, the collecting of primary data is highly expensive. The researcher has direct oversight over and control over the information gathering process. The information can be gathered via different methods like mailed questionnaires, observation, surveys, physical testing, personal interviews, focus groups, telephonic, case studies and focus groups, Etc.

As followed a pragmatist design, this research is mostly depended on the primary data collected from Chopcut ltd and ABC Bank's work environment through surveys and focus group discussions.

3.5.1.1 Justification:

As following a pragmatist theory, the role of primary data was very important in this research. Primary data was helpful because it provided an accurate information straight from the organizations. The existing employees facing the problem in workplace were surveyed and observed in a group discussion. Those methods shed light to some real data directly derived from the area of the problem. A survey was taken to find the exact dominance of the

problem and the focus groups were created to observe the psychology and understanding of the participants on the issue.

3.5.2 Secondary data source:

It is another necessary data collection that implies second-hand information about the topic. This type of data already gathered by someone other than the consumer for a motive, not linked to the actual research issue. It is readily acquirable from the information gathered from a different number of sources like government publications, censuses, internal records of the company, books, reports, websites, journals, articles and so on (Bauer, 2014). Secondary data provide different benefits as it is easily accessible and saves the investigator's cost and time. However, I have analysed few different publications on the issue. All the publications has some descriptive methods followed to sum up a solution to the problem. Journals were found online while researching. I have attached the references of the writing in the appendix part of the research.

3.5.2.1 Justification:

Applying secondary data saved my cost and time since the activity has already been completed to gather the information. It avoided issues associated with the collection process of information or data. The published documents on the issue also provided me with the research question. In this research, mentioned 5 sources were studied specifically because of the relativity of the subject. Journal i & v are about the workplace violence in business world. Journal iii & Book reference is about the ways on overcoming the problem associated with many real life examples. And the Book numbered as ii is a complete guide of Managing the workplace violence. The first journal's writers, Jennifer Loh and Robyn Snyman, present empirical proof that cyberbullying in the workplace can be a gendered occurrence. Trevor Hicks' book, "msherry," The purpose of Caroline is to serve as a toolkit for people who could experience workplace abuse. Using the knowledge gained from Nicole Cvenkel's research, new policies, instructional tools, and resources can be created to promote workplace practices that lessen the elements that lead to violence or abuse in the workplace and promote a more respectful environment for workers.

3.6 Sample Selection

Sampling introduces as an effective process of choosing a part of the population. In my research these are basically the employees of ChopCut ltd. and ABC Bank. It was not possible to examine the entire employee base due to lack of relevant resources e.g. cost, energy and time. Therefore, I chose a group of 100 people in Chopcut ltd and a group of 200 people in ABC Bank from different departments. It made my research convenient yet accurate. The chosen sample acted as a representation of the original scenario in the companies. The entire population of the organizations were studies from the evaluation of the data I received from this sample.

3.6.1 Sampling techniques

My research was done following the **Non-probability sampling technique**. It is another form of sampling approach which is used to select sample out of total population. This method is reliant on an investigator's capability to choose members at random. This type of sampling method is unfixed or pre-defined selection activity which create it difficult for entire components of a population to have equal chances to be included in sample (Vaiioleti, 2013). There are certain form of non-probability sampling method like quota sampling which I divided the full employee base in demographic criterion first to make sure employees from every department, race, background or sex has an opportunity to participate. As the ratio was not equal in the workplace, the small departments had the most chances to participate hence the large departments had less chance.

3.6.2 Participants

The participants were seated in six sessions over the course of six months in my presence. All sessions were on same questionnaire to check the accuracy of the data and to observe any change in their working environment. The raw data for analysis was typed transcripts. The participants confirmed that the process and learning categories mirrored their own experiences. Peers, participants in a qualitative research study group, and professional colleagues also weighed in on the data and the findings' plausibility.

For the survey part, from ChopCut ltd 100 participants were chosen where 20% were fixed as women and rest 80% were men from manufacturing unit, logistics unit and marketing unit. In ABC Bank among 200 employees as samples, 20% were from customer service and rest 80% were from conventional banking.

Selection of Participants for Survey from ChopCut

	Participants	Total
Women	20	100
Men	80	

Selection of Participants for Survey from ABC Bank

	Participants	Total
Customer Service	40	200
Conventional Banking	160	

For the focused group, 60 participants among that group were taken demographically for several sessions.

Selection of Participants for Focused Group from ChopCut

	Participants	Total
Women	20	30
Men	10	

Selection of Participants for Focused Group from ABC Bank

	Participants	Total
Customer Service	10	30
Conventional Banking	20	

3.7 Data Collection Tools

As it effectively provides a methodical direction to obtain accurate and pertinent information, this is the most crucial part of my research. These two are acknowledged as the main areas of investigation because they are effective at creating a developed theoretical framework to guide the overall process in the proper manner. This part of the research includes both primary and secondary sources of information, making them the main areas of investigation. Data for the study has been acquired for the current investigation using both primary and secondary sources. Primary research is being conducted through developing group discussions as an instrument which covers aim and objectives of the research. There were 12 close ended questions to be filled by all 300 participants. There were 13 open ended discussion topics where participants were seated in a focused group of 10 people in each group to discuss the topics. 6 separate groups were seated over six months as focus groups and the conversations were observed closely. The discussions were closely monitored and data were documented for the study.

3.7.1 Data analysis tools & techniques

It introduces as an effective and significant portion of present study which will help an investigator to analysis accurate and reliable data and resources about the study. There are different types of data analysis techniques which is followed in this research.

3.7.2 Techniques for primary source

Focus Group Session: Data collection was aided by conducting 6 Group discussions consisting 10 participants in each group. I have followed the group discussions method to get most convenient data to analyse from. Because the less the options of outcome were, the accuracy was established in the researches. It was conducted in a semi structured manner with pre-determined questions/topics from a 13 open ended question set. With no

confirmation or a neutral comment, I acknowledged the participant's response. This non-structured discussion protocol provided an objective standardized method for data collection. The 60 participants divided in 6 focus groups were chosen demographically as per below:

Participants from Chopcut ltd	Gender		Age	Earning (Monthly)	Job Designation
	Male	Female			
Group 1	3	7	20-30	<700 Pounds	Labours in ChopCut
Group 2	3	7	31-40	1000-1500 Pounds	Logistics Support in ChopCut
Group 3	4	6	40-50	1600-2500 Pounds	Line Managers in Factory of Chopcut

Participants from ABC Bank Ltd.	Work area		Age	Earning (Monthly)
	Customer service	Conventional Banking &		
Group 4	3	7	20-30	<700 Pounds
Group 5	3	7	31-40	1000-1500 Pounds
Group 6	4	6	40-50	1600-2500 Pounds

Survey Session:

For the survey part, from ChopCut ltd 100 participants were chosen and from ABC Bank 200 employees were chosen following a non-probability quota based technique.

Selection of Participants for Survey from ChopCut

	Participants	Total
Women	20	100
Men	80	

Selection of Participants for Survey from ABC Bank

	Participants	Total
Customer Service	40	200
Conventional Banking	160	

All three hundred participants had fill out the survey form (appendix) individually without any outside research or motivation and under so absolute obligation.

Group Discussion topic & Questionnaire: It was an effective instrument of my research which consists 12 survey questions and 13 discussion topics related to the issue. The key intention of this technique was to gather accurate and reliable information about the influence of work-related violence and physiological stress on performance of company within a working environment of Chopcut and ABC Bank. This method helped me to see the actual scenario with proper quantitative data.

Questionnaire development process

The questionnaire is designed according to Cognitive Response Theory. This theory emphasizes the cognitive processes involved in respondents' interpretation and response to survey questions. When designing a questionnaire, I considered the cognitive abilities, language comprehension, and memory limitations of the target population is crucial. I used clear and concise language, avoiding complex or ambiguous terms, and structuring questions in a way that minimizes cognitive load can enhance respondents' understanding and facilitate accurate responses.

Certainly, when embarking on the process of developing a questionnaire for my research, I followed a systematic approach that encompassed several key steps to ensure the effectiveness and relevance of the instrument. Here's an overview of my approach:

- **Defining My Research Objectives:** To begin with, I clearly outlined the specific objectives and research questions that my questionnaire aimed to address. This step was crucial in ensuring that the questionnaire would be tailored to gather the precise information needed to meet the research goals effectively.
- **Identifying My Target Respondents:** I carefully identified the target population or sample group for my research, taking into consideration various demographic factors such as age, gender, and occupation. Understanding my target respondents helped me develop questions that would resonate with their experiences and perspectives.
- **Conducting a Thorough Literature Review:** I conducted an extensive review of existing literature, studies, and relevant research within my field of study. This process allowed me to gain valuable insights into the topic and identify key variables or factors that should be included in my questionnaire, ensuring that it would be comprehensive and aligned with established research.
- **Generating an Initial Question Pool:** Based on my research objectives and the insights gleaned from my literature review, I developed an initial pool of questions. This pool encompassed a mix of open-ended and closed-ended questions, ensuring that my questionnaire covered a broad range of perspectives and dimensions related to my research topic.
- **Defining the Structure and Flow:** I carefully organized the structure of the questionnaire, ensuring a logical flow of questions that progressed from general inquiries to more specific ones. I included clear headers, subheadings, and instructions to guide respondents seamlessly through the questionnaire.

- **Crafting Clear and Concise Questions:** I paid particular attention to crafting questions that were clear, concise, and easily understandable for my target respondents. I avoided technical jargon and ambiguous language, ensuring that the questions were unbiased and did not lead participants toward specific responses.
- **Choosing Appropriate Response Scales and Formats:** I selected appropriate response scales of multiple-choice options, that aligned with the nature of my questions and the type of data I aimed to collect. I made sure that the response options provided a comprehensive and balanced representation of the respondents' perspectives.
- **Piloting the Questionnaire:** Prior to the full implementation of the questionnaire, I conducted a pilot test with a small group of respondents to identify any potential issues or ambiguities. The feedback I received from the pilot test allowed me to refine and fine-tune the questionnaire for optimal clarity and effectiveness.
- **Ensuring Ethical Compliance:** Throughout the development process, I prioritized ethical considerations, ensuring that my questionnaire respected the principles of informed consent, confidentiality, and privacy protection for all respondents. I communicated the purpose of the research transparently and assured participants that their information would remain confidential and secure.
- **Finalizing the Questionnaire:** Integrating the insights from the pilot test, I finalized the questionnaire, ensuring that it fully aligned with my research objectives and would effectively capture the necessary data. I conducted a final review to guarantee the clarity, coherence, and consistency of the questionnaire before its full implementation in the research study.

3.7.3 Techniques for secondary research

There were various techniques of secondary research method which are determine as under:

Information available on the internet: As internet is considered as the best technique which hold lot of data used by an enterprise according to their research needs. Nevertheless, company should be cognisant that authentic data can only be accumulated from trusted websites.

Literature Review: It is also identify as an effective and best source for collecting secondary information about the influence of work-related stress and physiological stress on performance of ChopCut Limited & ABC Limited. These sources helped me in gathering in-depth and appropriate information about the study.

Books/Journals/Articles: Books were the best sources for accumulating in-depth and proper information about the study. All these sources gave accurate and reliable information in form of numbers, figures, facts etc.

3.7.4 Data Security

Printed focused group transcripts, researcher field notes, and analysis notes were kept with proper safety. Informed consent and participant information forms with participant names were kept separately from the transcripts. Focused group recordings were kept on a password protected desktop computer and digital media drive.

3.7.6 Data Analysis

Analysis of data in descriptive research requires an open-minded, inductive exploration, which allows themes to emerge rather than be prescribed. Data analysis was conducted in three phases. First, I prepared the data for analysis. Second, I analysed the data using Microsoft Excel. Finally, I determined how to report findings. Preparing the Data Recorded discussion outcomes were recorded to reflect participants' exact words in response to the questions. Participants were given the opportunity to review their transcripts for correctness, and six participants returned these to me within one week.

3.8 Research ethics:

I received the ethical approval from the university. As research involves secondary information so it is very essential to ensure that the findings of investigation must be relevant and robust. For qualitative research, ethical principles are usually defined as a moral stance which includes security as well as respect of people which are actively consenting to be studied. Therefore, it was very essential for me to use authenticated sources only in order to present the more reliable as well as accurate information to a reader. This is because outdated and unauthenticated source may include false information regarding a particular event as well as a company. As a result of which this false information may mislead the readers which is an unethical practice as it may result into promotion of an organisation's negative publicity which also influences their performance. In addition to this an investigator must also focus toward presenting more accurate and correct information through their research and must not try to manipulate the information in order to make their investigation more attractive as it can mislead the readers and also practitioners also who can use the content of investigation in their future research.

Research ethics is defined as the set of provided guidelines which instruct an investigator to perform their work in ethical and reliable manner without breaching any sort of ethical rule or principle which may create any negative impact over person or other (Furnham and MacRae, 2017). Therefore, ethics is basically defined as an application of moral principles in planning, executing and reporting the findings of an investigation that has been performed by a researcher (Patten and Newhart, 2017).

Apart from that, this research also includes primary data where research ethics applied extensively to ensure that data gathered and presented throughout the research must be authentic and collected in ethical manner (Gabriel, 2015). The ethical principle utilised within the research generally includes informed consent, confidentiality and anonymity. The

principle of informed consent states that I must present the real information and aim behind conduction of its research in front of participant and must not try to cheat them for collecting information. In addition to this it must also provide them an option of opt in or out of participating in primary investigation as per their own choice. Hence, prior to investigate through structure questionnaire with participants I presented a structured detail about the purpose of investigation and manner in which it will be used so that they can make their perception regarding whether they have to participate or not in this research.

Apart from this, according to the principle of anonymity, I have not disclosed the personal detail of participant in its research and have not linked it to any part of its investigation result, as it is an unethical practice. The privacy of participant was obeyed while the development of report and research did not violate these ethical considerations in term of participant anonymity through investigation and publishing of research. This is because the primary focus of any research does not provide a scholar a distinctive right for intervene on a participants' privacy. At last the confidentiality principles of this research work over the fact that I have kept the findings of its investigation confidential and have not shared it with everybody. I must only be sharing the result of research with the persons who have stake in the result as well as finding of investigation such as my academics.

3.9 Researcher Reflexivity

Throughout data collection and analysis, I kept notes about participant comments and the research process. These papers gave me the chance to consider my own presumptions and prejudices and how they affected the way I conducted and analyzed my research. One significant reflection that surfaced repeatedly was how tough it was for me to switch from my supervisor lens to my researcher lens. This manifested itself in a desire to provide participants comments or encouragement as well as in judgment of participants who recounted workplace behaviors that I would have thought wrong as a supervisor, as an individual who had previously supervised people in their profession. Because I was aware that I couldn't set these ideas aside, I refrained from sharing them with the participants.

3.10 Research reliability and validity

The invention of the measurement tool, also known as the survey questionnaire, is largely responsible for the study's dependability. It serves as an effective and crucial tool for the primary researcher since I was able to collect accurate information about the effects of stress response and workplace violence on the productivity and success of Chopcut and ABC Bank with their assistance. This instrument was piloted across different potential participants to check that the knowingness of the questionnaire was conformable across various participants.

3.11 Data Presentation Techniques

Most data analysis involves applying percentages to the collected data. In addition to analyzing the data using statistical techniques, interpretations are done using the data that has been analyzed. A specific chapter contains the analysis, interpretation, and conclusions of the compiled information data. Each part analyzes and discusses the data that was acquired to meet the objectives. Analysis and interpretation are also done on the analysis's results. Graphs, diagrams, and graphical representations are utilized to properly analyze data, making them useful for assisting scientific study of data and for properly presenting the analysis and findings portions of analyses.

Tables:

This method is significantly applied to present an extensive range of data through the help of labelled rows and columns. I used the tabular form to present the frequency of participant's answers in Close ended Questions.

Pie charts:

I applied this technique for showing data that is to be appropriately compared. Thus this tool was effective in making comparison among the collected data through showing percentage regarding the options which are required to be compared in the questionnaire. The primary reason behind using a pie chart was that it is easy to understand and quick to interpret.

Gantt chart

Gantt chart is identified as a horizontal bar chart that facilitates a researcher in determining the beginning and end times for performing research operations. In addition, it is a useful graphical tool that displays tasks or activities performed against time (Wildemuth, 2016). Therefore, it is essential and valuable for the researcher to ascertain accurate and proper time for completing each activity or sub-part of research more effectively.

3.12 Research limitation

One of the main limitation of this research was time because for completion of each activities accurate time period was needed. However, the limitations faced were:

Lack of available and reliable data: In this research, sample size was a significant obstacle or issue in analysing a trend and an essential relationship. As a result, it is also recognized as a major obstacle to the investigator conducting research tasks in a methodical and efficient manner.

Scope of discussion: The depth and scope of the discussion in my research paper are compromised in many ways as compared to the work or activities of seasoned academics because I haven't had a lot of experience planning researches or generating academic documents of this size independently. So, it had an impact on the study.

Sample size: The sample size chosen for the present study was little in comparison to the actual population of both the companies. However due to inability to gather more sample the accuracy of the study might be hindered.

Therefore, the key limitation of the research is the time duration for completion of the activity and my capability to consist a large sample size for the primary research. Another biggest limitation of this research was the extent of information available in UK relating to the influence of physiological stress and workplace violence on performance of a company. While there was accurate information or data available publicly from the yearly reports, the organisation websites and other work-related stress of physiological violence related reports from the organisation. It is likely that there are many other information and data that I was not capable to approach as these were not available in publicly. Therefore, I did not have organisation access to information and data that were nor given publicly by an enterprise.

Chapter 4: Data Analysis

This analysis has been done with the help of qualitative as well as quantitative analysis. Therefore, in this group discussion and questionnaire, both are applied to gather appropriate information to draw actual results.

Furthermore, the investigation area is vast. The overall discussion is based on determining the influence of psychological stress and workplace violence on the performance of SME. Thus in this information is accumulated through an interview and questionnaire. However, thematic analysis has been applied as it is the most effective way to conduct appropriate examination because these approaches are established over the queries of questionnaire and group discussion.

Data analysis is the most vital area of an examination as it effectively assists the overall examination adequately to a drawn valid and reliable outcome. However, to analyse the data, the results from the questionnaire have been analysed using pie chart in this research.

Depending on the Focused group discussions, thematic coding technique have been applied. By examining meaning of words and grammatical structures, thematic coding—also referred to as thematic analysis—a type of qualitative data analysis, locates themes in text. It is a great way of understanding qualitative data as there are many way to determine the tone and usability of certain words.

4.1 Thematic Analysis

This is considered to be the most crucial component of an examination because it is useful in guiding the total inquiry in the right direction to get at the desired conclusion. Thematic analysis is refers to be the most efficacious aspect which helps the overall investigation in analysing the information in appropriate manner to draw valid and reliable outcome. The

methodology used in this phase of the study is analysis supported by the development of themes from questionnaire questions. Thus, this article's ideas are explored over questionnaire questions. Thematic analysis, a method for evaluating qualitative data, entails searching through a data collection to identify, investigate, and report recurrent themes, (Braun and Clarke 2006). It is a method for collecting information, but it also involves interpretation when selecting codes and developing themes.

A combination of qualitative data, such as interview transcripts, social media profiles, or survey responses, can be used to do research on people's perspectives, views, facts, experiences, or values using thematic analysis. In my research about workplace violence and stress, I have found this to be the most accurate method to interpret my case study data.

There are 5 simple steps that I have followed to develop the study with data from my focused group discussion and Close ended questionnaire.

Step 01	Step 02	Step 03	Step 04	Step 05
Any qualitative analysis starts with reading and rereading the transcripts or repeatedly listening to the conducted discussion to identify the main subject of the data that was gathered.	Identifying the first codes in the data is the second stage. This is crucial to comprehending the response's general pattern.	Once codes are generated I developed themes on those codes, some positive, some outrageous, some negative and so.	In fourth step, I reviewed those themes and connected the dots with survey question answers based on that theme.	Finally, to interpret, I have tried to focus light on to the exact "essence" of the data.

Table 4.1 Process of thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke)

4.2 The Qualitative Analysis

4.2.1. Focused Group discussion: Theme 1:

“Effect of workplace-violence and psychological stress on employee's productivity of an organisation.”

According to the manager, workplace violence is a significant concern for every business organisation and its workers. As it negatively impacts the efficiency level of workers and at the same time also demotivate them towards operational activities. Additionally, stress is also known as the unfavourable psychological and functional responses that develop in a person's mind as a result of that person's incapacity to manage any demands or circumstances. Mainly, it is a tension that arises from the extraordinary demand of workers at the workplace. It does not have to be wrong: it can be an opportunity when it provides potential gain to individuals. Apart from this, violence in the workplace directly affects the individual and their mind set. It reduces productivity, low morale, and negative publicity.

All these negatively influence the overall performance of the company and its workers as well. For employees, violence is considered a complex or heterogeneous phenomenon that intentionally uses physical force or power against oneself, threatened, and many more that negatively influence workers' behaviour at the workplace or working activities. Sometimes, employees do not realise the actual influence of stress on workers presentation that eventually results in arising administrative dilemmas at the workplace. In this regard, some essential factors may increase stress, such as poor time management, unclear job descriptions, inequality, lack of communication, negative personal relationships, the complexity of task activities and many more.

In theme 1, the words “negatively impacts”, “demotivate”, “low morale” “managerial dilemmas” were the key words that brings out the scenario.

All these issues adversely affect the employee's performance and at the same time also make them demotivated towards the operational activities. As per today's work life, generally, employees working for a more extended period required more responsibilities to improve their performance at the working area. As stress is considered a complex and dynamic concept that affect the performance of the company. Thus, the workers need to get the work done effectively. This manager is responsible for managing the level of stress by providing them with better guidance and support. In this regard, job stress has become a key challenge in front of employees because it has a strapping influence on the efficiency level of the company and its workforce as well.

If employees are stressed, it increases undesirable issues like low productivity, less motivation, increased absenteeism and so on. One of the significant impacts of stress is increased turnover rates of business organisations. This includes situations in which work pressure exceeds the employee's ability to cope, and wherein knowledge and abilities are not effectively utilised. This is the reason that stress arises in employees mindsets. It also causes an imbalance of individual life that leads to depression, which changes the employee's attitude and work behaviour. Thus, management must take care of employee's productivity and provide them flexible working environment so that they can efficiently perform their tasks and at the same time also advance their performance level.

4.2.2. Focused Group discussion: Theme 2:

“Government has a role in overcoming workplace-violence. Do you agree or disagree? Please justify”

As per the Manager's perspective, to maintain adequate working conditions, the government plays an essential role because they have developed several rules and regulations that help them overcome workplace violence effectively. They mentioned about the acts related to the violence at workplace. They brought up the public order act, Sex discrimination act, Harassment act and Disability discrimination act. The managers of Chopchut and ABC Bank believe that the harassments or violence at workplace can be controlled with proper

application of the acts in workplace. Some of them pointed out that because of not having these implied properly, the employees has no answerability to the organization. They are suffering from low morale and ethics.

From this discussion, The key words “rules and regulations”, “acts” and “answerability” are the words that brings up light to the fact that government can imply the rules to organizations that can reduce these behaviours.

Some major acts that can be implied are discussed as below:

Public Order Act 1986: According to this legislation, there are several activities or functions which leads to workplace violence, such as threatening, insulting words or behaviour, beating a person at the workplace and many more. In respect of Managers, they generally adopt respective rules when such situations occur at the workplace and adopt this law. Management can take action in verbal, physical or written form.

Sex Discrimination Act 1975: This act is amended in the year 2008, and it is developed for one of the significant reasons for workplace violence. It is generally developed for situations when there is discrimination is done based on gender. According to the Manager, this is one of the primary reasons for violence at the workplace. Some male employees consider female employees not much effective due to violence take place, and to resolve it; they generally adopt respective legislation.

Protection from Harassment Act 1997: This act covers situations related to assault and a battery that is generally considered a condition when an individual intentionally or rashly incept another person. This may cause physical as well as mental harm to a person who is a victim. In respect of Manager, their management generally adopts this legislation to protect employees from any illegal activities and workplace violence.

Sexual offences Act 2003: This act includes several situations that may occur at the workplace and lead to violence, such as sexual abuse, generally non-accordant sexual activities, etc. In this respect, managers adopt respective legislation to avoid such kinds of sexual abuse or violence effectively. This will also help them in supporting those people who go through such kinds of activities.

Disability Discrimination Act 1995: This legislation is generally adopted by peoples when there is discrimination occur with disable people (mental or physical disable). In Manager's context, they generally adopt this rule and regulation when anyone at the workplace misbehaves with a disabled person. By this, they can encourage their disabled employees or customers impressively and help avoid the situation that may occur workplace violence.

Employment Equality Regulation 2003: This legislation is generally adopted by the company to protect its members from discrimination based on age, gender, skin colour, language, culture, values, beliefs and many more. In respect of Manager, they adopt this rule to avoid the situation that leads to workplace violence. This is so because when someone abuses a disabled person, it is high that violence will occur.

These are some of the significant rules and regulations that Manager will adopt to avoid and overcome workplace violence situations.

4.2.3 Focused Group discussion: Theme 3:

“Discuss some ways to overcome from workplace-violence and psychological stress by use of motivational theory.”

According to managers' perspective, there are several ways to overcome and avoid workplace violence and psychological stress, such as they generally adopt motivational theories for respective situations. Motivational theory can lead to stimulation, direction, development strategies for attaining goals, and many more. This will also describe why and how the behaviour of humans will be activated and through what plan of action management can avoid workplace violence and psychological stress. The managers believe that, if the need of the employees like psychological need or self-actualization need are served well, they will definitely be focused on their work and have less interest in violence.

The key words in this discussion “stimulation”, “direction”, “development strategies for attaining goals”, “psychological need” and “self-actualization” lead to the effectiveness of motivational theory application in workplace.

Some primary motivational theory which manager can adopt in order to avoid and overcome workplace violence, as well as psychological stress, are mentioned below:-

Maslow's Hierarchy of need theory: According to this theory, people are motivated to fulfilment of goals and objectives of the organisation through fulfilling their needs in a hierarchy format. There are five primary needs of human beings that are followed systematically and adequately. The primary purpose of implementing such a theory by the manager is to provide job satisfaction and fulfil the basic needs of employees to avoid workplace violence and psychological stress. They are described below:

- **Physiological Needs-** All the employees are working in an organisation should be provided with basic needs by their manager. These are the fundamental basic requirements of individuals, such as food, shelter, air, water, sleep, warmth and sex.
- **Safety and Security Needs-** The working force should be provided with safety and security needs to feel safe and comfortable at the organisation. This includes security, employment, stability, health, law & order.
- **Social Needs-** This need includes love, affection, belongingness with family, friends, colleagues. The employees who are performing work in an organisation have to be loved to get motivated for better work performance.
- **Esteem Needs-** When all these above needs are fulfilled, another need rises is self-esteem needs. In this need, individuals develop positive feelings and want high value and recognition at the workplace. It includes self-confidence, recognition, achievement, respect, status.

- **Self-actualisation Needs-** It is the highest level need of this theory. Here, all needs of individuals are fulfilled, and they are in search of improving their potential capacity by doing those things they like the most. It includes pursuing talent, peak experiences, creativity and personal growth.

Herzberg's Two factors theory: According to this theory, there are generally two factors that motivate employees at the workplace. It will help avoid violence and psychological stress among the employees. The motivation factor will encourage staff to work hard for attaining goals and objectives, which will also help them avoid a stressful situation that leads to workplace violence. On the other hand, a *hygiene factor* in two factor theory is defined as a situation related to the environment or surroundings of the workplace. This will also lead to avoiding violence and psychological stress at the workplace because if their ineffective environment, then employees get irritated, leading to violence and stress.

By adopting Maslow's Hierarchy of needs theory and Herzberg's Two factors theory, managers can avoid situations of workplace violence and psychological stress ineffective and impressive manner.

4.2.4 Focused Group discussion: Theme 4

“Does employee motivation has any impact of workplace-violence and psychological stress? Discuss in general”

As per the manager's point of view, employee motivation is an essential factor that directly influences individual needs and desires. As it positively impacts workers behaviour by motivating them towards the set goals and objectives as well. The managers believe, motivation is based on employee’s emotions and achievement of related goals and objectives. If employees are motivated enough, they quickly reduce their stress and make the working area positive and healthy. They also believe that this will improve their efficiency level to perform their best at the workplace as employee motivation is one of the critical aspects of the workplace, which directly leads to the company's overall performance and its workforce. It may directly improve employee engagement at the workplace through which every worker may positively share their relationships and build a positive work environment. It also allows the managers to meet their set goals and objectives by removing any issues or risks at the workplace. The managers from ABC Bank believe that in a business organisation, motivated employees lead to increased overall productivity that allows a firm to attain a higher output level.

In the discussion the words “positively impacts”, “emotions and achievement”, “directly leads” and “positive work environment” portray that motivation can directly and effectively reduce workplace stress that results to a zero violence organizational environment.

The manager of the organization makes use of a number of motivational theories, including Herzberg's two-factor theory and Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory, in order to achieve the same. With the use of this, the manager can motivate and encourage them towards the

operational activities. If they are motivated towards their goals and activities, they do not feel any stress at the workplace. This is why management of the company may use better motivation at the workplace to make them productive and efficient towards the goals and objectives. As a result, they will be more productive and achieve their set goals and objectives. In this situation, one of the ways a manager of a company might inspire their employees is by meeting their basic needs and demands at work, according to Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs theory. It may help them in improving their engagement with organisational objectives and at the same time also attain their target in a stipulated time frame. By providing them with all the necessary resources and a positive work environment, they can easily manage their stress and workplace violence. With this assistance, a company can easily enhance their performance.

Furthermore, motivation is also considered as a powerful tool that refers to reinforce behaviour and also triggers the attitude to continue by reducing the chances of arising any issues at the workplace as motivation is an internal driver that used to satisfy an unsatisfied need that may support them in attaining specific aims and goals. One of the primary advantages of using motivational theories is developing employee's engagement, maintaining better coordination among team members, providing better satisfaction towards the job activities, and so on. All these positively impact job satisfaction and also prevent low performance at the workplace.

4.2.5 Focused Group discussion: Theme 5

“Identify some types of motivation that are used for overcoming psychological stress and workplace-violence within your organization”

As per the manager's point of view, motivation is one of the important aspects for workers because it benefits to recover their performance and at the same time also influence individuals to provide needs and desire that strongly impact on the overall behaviour of workers. Mainly, it includes needs, ambitions, desires and many more. Achievement motivation is also based on attaining success at the workplace. In this regards, there are different type motivation that used by ABC Limited and ChopCut ltd for overcoming psychological stress and workplace violence within the company are as follows:

Extrinsic Motivation: It refers to those things based on external rewards in which employees get incentives, expectations, and many more. It is related to the money, fame, grades, praise and so on. All these may aid in motivating workers at workplace that may support them in reducing their stress level. With the assistance of this, employees enhance their performance level within the organisation.

Reward based Motivation: Incentive motivation is type of motivation that used when employees feels that they will be a reward once and goals is achieved. Thus, it is crucial for management of company to provide rewards to their workers as per their performance. This improves their performance level of the employees at workplace. The managers from ChopCut ltd highlighted this type of motivation mostly.

Achievement based Motivation: For every workers, titles, positions, roles towards the jobs is important. As it is important for company to provide incentives motivations that is based on the rewards that is come after a set goals is met. It will contribute in enhancing chances of developing motivation towards the company and its set activities as well. Managers from ABC Bank mentioned that they apply this type of motivational theories to their front sales team.

From the above discussion key words identified are “Achievement motivation”, “rewards”, “goals” and “incentives”. These words refer to an interrelation of motivation and better performance. Along with these applied tactics there are some more type of motivational aspects that can be practiced in these two organizations.

Intrinsic Motivation: It is one of the important type of motivation in which employees being motivated by internal desires. Thus, it is important for individual to get a better promotion because self-improvement is one of the effective and major joy of learning. Along with this, it is also engage in a behaviour that arise from within the individual or workers as well.

Fear based Motivation: This type of motivation can be negative but not every time. In this regards, when employee set goals and achievement knows that accountability is consider as a huge role in attaining the same. Mainly, this type of motivation is extremely powerful as it strong enough to prevent them from quitting. This will improve their productivity level and also eliminate issue related with the stress and workplace -violence.

Attitude Motivation: This type of motivation is effective as it help employees to recover and move forward properly. Because it also affects people who have a strong desire to alter their behavior. Along with this, attitude motivation of employees will directly meet goals related to self-awareness and self-change. For this, a supervisor of the company is in responsible for providing them with superior direction and fostering their capacity to operate at their peak at work.

4.2.6 Focused Group discussion: Theme 6

“According to you, psychological stress and workplace violence impacted on performance of ChopCut Limited and ABC limited? If yes, how?”

According to the manager's point of view psychological stress and workplace violence are directly impactful on the overall performance of the company because it is related with the employees and their performance as well. If workers are less motivated and also face workplace violence then they fail in attaining their set goals and objectives. This has negatively impacted on the overall performance of the company and its employees activities as well. One of the managers from ABC Bank Ltd mentioned that there were some employees in the retail banking who believed not to be paid according to their job role in 2019. It was the year when, the bank had least credit accounts opened. In 2020, many of the factory

workers of Chopcut ltd were fired to minimize cost. This decision resulted in stress in the other workers. Upon doing a Quality Check, most of the tires were faulty that year.

From the above discussion, words like “impactful”, “fail in attaining” and “resulted in stress” points out to a relation between stress and performance in both organizations.

Mainly, psychological stress is related to signs to look for, ways to help in managing stress of employees. It is based in the feeling of strain and pressure that faced by workers at working area. Employees may experience a decline in motivation as a result, which will have a detrimental impact on their performance level. This the major reason that it affect efficiency level of workers in which they perform their task activities.

As an overall image of the company is highly based on employee’s performance. If they do not perform well and feel stressed at the workplace, then it adversely impact on overall image of the company and at the same time, reduce its performance level as well. Thus, it is necessary for employees to keep their mind calm and think positive towards their activities so that they can easily enhance their efficiency level. With the help of this, they can improve the possibilities of attaining best suitable results in most effective manner. On the other side, workplace violence is relate to the act or threat of physical violence, harassment and another disruptive behaviour that faced by employees at workplace. It directly affect the involvement of workers and at the same time also make them demotivated towards the working area and activities.

Additionally, it is a situation when employees are mistreated or threatened by both internal and external parties to the business. This will increase employee’s dissatisfaction of employees towards the job post. It is consider as one of the major issues for a company and its workers that negatively influence their working abilities within the firm. Due to this, a company fails to attain their targets and reduce their performance level at the marketplace. Both issues are make workers less efficient towards their goals in which they fail in attaining the same to improve their performance. By this, employees face issues related to the negative working environment and create conflicts among all the workers present at the workplace. Thus, business organizations need to provide a positive and safe working area so that employees can easily perform their tasks. It helps them in maintaining better relationship with staff members. The main advantage of managing psychological stress and workplace violence is to develop positive relationships with the workforce that may positively impact on increasing performance level of the company in the marketplace. It also may help in retaining workers within the firm.

4.2.7 Focused Group discussion: Theme 7

“Discuss the role of your organization (ChopCut Limited and ABC limited) in overcoming impact of psychological violence and workplace stress.”

In the present investigation, the overall investigation is conducted to determine the role played by the ChopCut Limited and ABC limited in overcoming the influence of

psychological violence and workplace stress. Therefore, it has been determined that there are several roles from the managers' viewpoint analysis that are performed by the ChopCut Limited and ABC Limited in overcoming impact of psychological violence and workplace stress.

Employees in the Focused group believe that psychological abuse and workplace stress are recognized as the critical issues that have a wider impact on the operations and development of the business. As a result, in today's modern business environment, increasing performance is determined to be the major concern area of the business and the organizations are primarily concerned over enhancing employees performance, so employees are the key aspect of business, thus businesses are focuses over improvising the operations of employees via reducing psychological violence and workplace stress and providing them an effective environment to work effectively and efficiently.

However, there are some major roles which they believe can be performed by the businesses are Workplace-violence policy development. Threat Assessment, Security surveys and measures, Incident management, Crisis response plan, Whistle blower programs, Employee Training and so on. Therefore, these are the major role which can be mainly performed by the ChopCut Limited and ABC limited in reducing the effective of violence and workplace stress. ChopCut ltd.

The key words in the above discussion are, “assorted roles”, “contribution of employees”, “Threat Assessment”, “Security surveys and measures”, “Incident management”, “Crisis response plan”, “Whistle blower programs” and “Employee Training”.

In addition to this, both the companies are also performing vital role in developing, Workplace-violence policy, therefore, the policy implementation is recognised to be an effective action which are taken for the businesses to follow and execute business operations in appropriate manner.

Furthermore, Threat Assessment is also an effective role performed by the businesses in analysing the threat that has a direct impact over the business's operations and affects the performance and functionally of the enterprises. Surveys and measures or the Incident management are also termed to be the key role performed by the business.

Therefore, these are imperative in determining the need and potential of employees and assign them on a right place to effective execution of business operations; furthermore, incident management is effective in managing misshaping at workplace and provide a direction to execute business operations in viable manner. Therefore, these all roles that the ChopCut Limited or ABC Limited performs are significant in attaining higher growth and success via reducing psychological violence and workplace stress.

4.2.8 Focused Group discussion: Theme 8

“Performance appraisal system can help your organization (ChopCut Limited and ABC limited) to overcome impact of workplace stress. Do you agree or disagree? Justify”

In the present dissertation work, the analysis is being executed for determining the implementation of a performance appraisal system that help ChopCut Limited and ABC Limited overcome the impact of workplace stress. Therefore, this analysis has been executed among the managers of the firm, as per their views this analysis has been evaluated that, the implementation of performance appraisal system helps the ChopCut Limited and ABC Limited to overcome the impact of workplace stress, therefore, this the best and effective step which is taken by the businesses to sustain employees at workplace. Stress at workplace is determined to be a crucial challenge which affects the overall functioning of the business via affecting the morale and enthusiasm of working. The definition of workplace stress is a detrimental physical and emotional reaction that can occur when there is a contradiction between the demands of the job placed on the employee and the level of control the individual has over meeting those demands.

The managers of the company claimed that the performance appraisal system is unsuccessful at motivating employees at the workplace and decreasing tension among them. Workplace stress has a strong adverse impact on the activities and growth of the business. Thus performance appraisal is defined as a regular process of an employee's job performance and overall contribution to a business. In addition to this, performance appraisal is efficacious in evaluating an employee's skills, achievements and growth which is in turns in guiding them to appraise an employee on a right place. Performance appraisal is also effective in providing opportunities for the business or its employees to getting opportunities at workplace and reduces the stress. Although, stress has adverse influence over the working and the physical as well as mental condition of an individual therefore, performance appraisal is efficacious for the business in providing suitable opportunities which encourages people to put their substantial efforts in the growth and success of the business.

From the above discussion words like "implementation", "regular process", "providing opportunities" points to appraisal systems to be a regular system to increase the employee performance.

In the implementation of the performance appraisal system, ChopCut Limited and ABC limited are concerned about providing higher opportunity, promotions, incentives, compensation, rewards, etc. Thus, it is effective in declining the stress among the employees so that people can be able to execute business operations in a more effective manner. Therefore, performance appraisal is recognised to be the most suitable way for a business to reducing work stress, thus it is essential for the administration of the business to reduce stress in respect to improvising the operations and performance of the business. Performance appraisal is also recognised to be the most effective and applied strategy which is beneficial for the business or its management to reduce employees stress and develop the overall performance of the business. Therefore, managers of ChopCut Limited and ABC limited are in favour with this argument that, performance appraisal system is being implemented by the businesses to develop employees performance and reducing the workplace Stress, which in turns in creating value in the growth and development of the overall business operations.

4.2.9 Focused Group discussion: Theme 9

“Role of training and development in reducing stress within working environment of ChopCut Limited and ABC limited.”

In this existing evaluation work, the study has been executed over the area of analysing the influence of training over developing and supporting the business in reducing stress, therefore, the study is mainly conducted among the managers of ChopCut Limited and ABC Limited in providing suitable information in effective manner. Thus, majority of participants of the group are in favour with the statement that, training and development support in reducing stress within working environment of ChopCut and ABC limited.

The employee group in the discussion group believe that training and development are recognised to be a subsystem of a business that in-consist over the improvement of the performance of peoples and groups. Therefore, training is defined as an effective educational procedure that includes the sharpening of skills, concepts, changing of attitude and gaining more knowledge to develop the performance of the employees at workplace.

They mentioned that training is recognised to be the most effective aspect which is efficacious in developing the performance of the employees, therefore, training is effective in enhancing the morale of employees working. In addition to this, majority of ChopCut Limited and ABC Limited managers are in favour with the statement that training and development sessions support the firm in reducing the stress from the working environment.

The words to be selected from above discussion are “analysing”, “subsystem”, “enhancing the morale”

In the context of organisations, training is imperative in providing significant direction to the employees to conduct all business operations in appropriate manner with the suitable guidance of their employees. In today’s modern business environment, the key motive of each small and large business enterprise is to attain higher growth and success at market place via enhancing their performance and operations. However, training is mainly categorised among on the job training and off the job training; therefore, these two are significant for providing the suitable assistance to the employees to perform business operations in effective manner.

Therefore, from the opinion analysis of the managers it has also been evaluated that, in the workplace environment of ChopCut Limited and ABC Limited, mainly on the job training is provided by the business or its management as it recognised to be the most appropriate way to develop the skills and ability of employees at workplace and enhance their operations and functions. Majority of managers stated that, on the job training is effective for the organisational employees to develop the skills and ability to conduct all the business operations in effective manner, thus each business is based on their own way of conducting operations, so it is quite mandatory for the businesses to provide effective training sessions to

their employees in respect to train them and enhance their capabilities to work with more coordination and collaborations. As the study also evaluated that, training is important for an organisation to provide suitable knowledge and also explains in regards to their role and responsibilities, thus this might provide a better way to conduct their own job roles in viable manner which in turns in effective for the business or its employees to attain their own as well as personal objectives. Training is also creating value in adding higher experience in the capability enhancement of the employees which will be significant for them in achieving growth and success in their future. As per the views analysis of the manager's individual, it has been found that, training and development support in reducing stress within working environment of ChopCut Limited and ABC limited.

4.2.10 Focused Group discussion: Theme 10:

“Innovation and its role in overcoming psychological stress and workplace-violence in working environment of ChopCut Limited and ABC limited”

According to the study conducted over the area of evaluating the analysis of implementation of innovation helps in overcoming psychological violence and workplace-stress in working environment of ChopCut Limited and ABC limited. Thus, this execution is mainly conducted among the managers as the managers of ChopCut limited and ABC Limited are very effective in providing suitable information regarding the business's internal and external operations. Thus, as the managers mainly stated that, innovation is defined to be the most effective aspect in today's business environment, therefore, the key concern of each small as well as large business enterprises is to improvising their production and operations and for this they are focuses over implementing high tech and innovative technologies at work place.

In addition to this innovation also helps in reducing psychological violence and workplace stress, thus the managers has stated that, innovation in technologies like CCTV camera, video recorder, GPS system, computer system, stress relieving gadgets etc. are needed to be implemented by the businesses as these are effective in reducing the violence. For example setting up CCTV camera in the manufacturing area of Chopcut turned out to be an effective option that was beneficial for both employees and the business. Therefore, if in the case there is kind of misshaping happens with the employees like sexually abuse at workplace, sexual harassment, bulling etc. the camera is significant in record all the activities and helps the individual in getting justice. According to the managers, this created answerability among the employees. Also it created a faith in employees resulting in reliability.

The words like “suitable information”, “high tech”, “answerability” and “faith” points out the effectiveness of modern technologies in small businesses.

In addition to this, businesses are also needs to provide playing zone for making employees relax within the working hours, thus some time people get pissed off and needs break than innovation in paying gadgets and other relaxing aspects are effective for the employees to reducing workplace stress, as stress has become a major issue which creates physical and

mental illness. As per the detailed analysis of manager's opinion it has also been evaluated that, innovation is required for each business as it basically helps the business to grow as well as strengthen the workforce via developing stress free environment and reducing physical violence. ChopCut Limited and ABC Limited are two medium size businesses that has its major concern over becoming the large business and wants to operate at international level, and for this, they are effectively concern over implement best and suitable innovation tools that are effective for the firm in developing their operations via reducing the stress among the employees. Companies are focuses over emerging, high tech machinery, computer system, data base system, communications aspects, etc. That is effective in reducing human efforts and enhancing the operations of the business and reducing the level of stress and violence. In the working environment, management of a business are liable to provide suitable work to the right employee and use the capability and skills of individual in right manner, but some time people are violated through the management and higher authority as they are threaten by the owners or the other higher authority and forces to do more work and some time they are also facing the issue of physical voidance just because not accomplishing the targets of the business, so the emergence of advance technologies are effective in reducing human efforts and making business free from violence and stress. However, the study has also stated that, the majority of managers in ChopCut limited and ABC Limited are in favour with this argument that, innovation help in overcoming psychological violence and workplace-stress in working environment, which is supportive for the business in implementing the efforts of employees in right manner to attain higher growth and success.

4.2.11 Focused Group discussion: Theme 11

“What are the ways used by your company to maintain positive relation among employees at workplace?”

The managers from ABC Bank ltd. in the focused group mentioned that, the ABC Bank is currently imposing techniques of team building once every two weeks by job rotation. Every other week, the managers ask the employees to do cross functional works. Thus, the relationship between employees grow and results in organizational empathy. In Chopcut limited, managers are trying to mitigate boundaries between the line managers and the factory workers. The sales team are also involved in the manufacturing in recent days. They believe this step helped them understanding the team operations as a group.

In this discussion words like, “rotation”, “cross functional”, “mitigate boundaries” and “group” reflects to the effect of positive relationship in work environment.

From the views analysis of the managers it has been evaluated that a good relation implementation among organisational employees are significant for a business to attempt business objectives in more effective manner, therefore, good employees interrelationship are helpful for the businesses in execute business operations with more coordination and collaboration. Therefore, there are assorted ways like team building, employees training, share information, effective participation in decision making, providing direction, initiate repeat interaction, be positive, manage boundaries etc. Are effectively implemented by the businesses to maintain positive relationship among employees at workplace.

Thus, these significant ways are effective for a business to build effective relationship among employees. Business now a day's are majorly concern over establishing good relation ship among employees as better relationship initiates the business to conduct complex task in appropriate manner via the collaborative efforts of employees. Thus, workplace with high coordination and collaboration are effective in attempting business objectives in more effective manner. From the analysis of the opinion of manager, it has been evaluated that, team building is recognised to be the best way for a business to execute all the operations in appropriate manner and enhance collaboration among employees, thus team building mainly initiates to work people in a team and coordinate with each other for the purpose of attaining the common objectives, Therefore, this recognised to be the best and effective way for a business to attain growth and success via enhancing the relationship among employees. However, workers are recognised to be the key asset of the business as they are plays a vital role in the growth of business, therefore, the ultimate progress of an organisation is mainly based on the efforts of the business.

It is quite important for the business or its management to make their employees involve in the decision making process as the employees are very much close to the operations of the business and liable in providing god suggestions in regards to the betterment of business operations. Thus, this is also a best way to develop better relationship among employees and moreover, they are feel confident and motivated to put their coordinative efforts in the growth and progression of the business. In addition to this, it has also been analysed that, positivity is also a better way to spread coordination and collaboration among the employees. Thus, in the workplace environment managers are needs to keep a positive attitude and trying to develop positivity among their employees. However, a positive leader is also good to encourage people to work with more collaboration and coordination. Businesses should initiate repeat conversation as it is effective for the business in exploring their operations in more effective manner as this is an easy and best way by people can easy get involve in the process and execute operations in more viable manner as the old relations are effective in helping people to work with higher coordination as the recognition about each other's skills are effective for a business or its management to gain growth and success.

4.2.12 Focused Group discussion: Theme 12

“External factor of business organisation helps to reduce your stress within working environment of company. Do you agree to the statement?”

The execution into consideration is based on determining the external factors of business organisations that helps employees to reduce their stress within working environment, therefore, as per the views analysis of the chosen respondents it has been raised as majority of managers said that, the reduction of workplace stress is the imperative area of a business as it is a major consideration of a business to reduce stress from their working environment and develop a better working place where individual can work with more coordination and collaboration. According to managers, it is a well acknowledged problem that work - related stress has a considerable impact on the routine activities and growth of the company. Therefore, workplace stress and violence are needs to be reduced for the purpose of building

an effective and positive working environment where productivity of employees can be enhanced. In contrast the employee group in the focus group mentioned that, there are assorted external factors of business like external environment, market competition, advancement in technologies, others job role, working zone, and so on are helpful for them to reduce their stress with working environment of business. The external environment is a major aspect which influences the working of employees as the people are mainly influenced through the external environment, so it is quite important for the businesses to enhance their operations through providing them a comfort zone, healthy working place, friendly environment etc.

From the discussion above, key words like “market competition”, “advancement in technologies”, “others job role”, “working zone” and “influenced” turns light into the effectiveness of positive external environment.

Therefore, in today’s modern business environment people are very much attracted towards the external environment in which fun, entertainment, party and so on are keeping their priority and people are considering to get involve in the social life, so it is also required for the businesses on small, medium or large level needs to provide break to their employees to reduce workplace stress. Additionally, the assessment of the study indicated that, businesses are also needs to be focus over emerging effective technologies for the purpose of making business projects more easy and appropriate.

4.2.13 Focused Group discussion: Theme 13

“Provide any recommendations to ChopCut Limited and ABC limited about how to overcome Employee's workplace stress and psychological violence.”

From the analysis of the discussion, it has been recommended by both employees and managers from ChopCut Limited and ABC Limited to implement suitable strategies and models that are effective for the businesses to develop motivation and encourages employees to conduct effective business operations. They mentioned that the company should also concern over implementing suitable workplace-violence policy for the purpose of implementing an effective working culture, where the stress is less and businesses or their employees can work with more potential and enthusiasm. In addition to this, it has also been suggested to the businesses to conduct appropriate threat assessment for the intention of reducing the issues that are impacting over the operations and progression of the business. Therefore, the assessment of risk is required for the businesses to assist overall business operations in effective manner. They prefer the company should also hire experienced people in their management segment as it is right for businesses to do, they should support their staff members at work and help them grow in their excitement for their jobs. This will help the businesses expand and succeed at work. Additionally, it has been recommended that ChopCut Limited and ABC Limited offer incentives and awards to its staff in order to motivate and inspire them to work hard because their increased efforts will help the companies' growth and success. Thus, incentives and rewards are effective for the employees in developing their

morale of working and enhancing their operations level which in turns in creating value for the business in achieving higher growth and success.

The key words in the discussion like, “suitable strategies”, “policy”, “threat assessment”, “risk assessment” and “rewards” claim to be the most effective solution to get the best output from the existing employees in Chopcut ltd and ABC Bank ltd.

In the process of conducting this evaluation, research has been done to identify the strategies that ChopCut Limited and ABC Limited can use to reduce psychological violence and workplace stress among their employees. ChopCut Limited and ABC Limited have been advised to enhance their operations in order to achieve higher growth and success, in accordance with the project's extensive analysis. It has also been recommended to the both the organisations as they are operating at medium level and businesses should implement appropriate strategies for reducing workplace stress, therefore, stress is a significant problem that directly affects the company's functioning and development. The ChopCut Limited and ABC Limited both are operating at medium level and very much concern over attaining higher growth and success and for this company should provide appropriate training to their employees for the purpose of improvising their operations and performance for the purpose of developing the overall functions of the firm in appropriate way.

Furthermore, business should also follow government legislations that are implemented for reducing psychological violence from the work place environment as these sorts of issues affects the emotions and sentiments of employees and affects their working capabilities. So it is also required for the businesses to employ appropriate measures that are significant for overcoming the issue of violence at workplace and trying to build an effective and positive working environment.

4.3 Qualitative Data Analysis

4.3.1 Survey Question 1: The individual knowledge about the concept of workplace stress

Do you have knowledge about the concept of workplace stress?	Frequency
a) Yes	250
b) No	50

4.3.1 The individual knowledge about the concept of workplace stress

Interpretation:

In this present analysis the study is being executed over analysing individual's understanding in regards to the knowledge about the concept of workplace stress. Therefore, workplace stress is recognised to be a major stress which in turns affects the overall operations of the business. As a result, the survey is being conducted among 300 respondents who have substantial expertise of the study area in question. So, out of those 250 persons, 250 are in favor of this statement because they understand the meaning of workplace stress and believe it to be the main problem that employees of the company confront as a result of intense job demands and the empowerment of higher authority. From the opinion examination of the respondents it has been examined that, they are having suitable knowledge about the same as they are having suitable interest in the same field and idea about the similar field is required by the individual to develop appropriate business practices. Additionally, the remaining individuals are against it since, in their perspective, they do not really have a good notion of it. They believe it is not very vital to acquire knowledge of workplace stress because they do not have any substantial ideas or knowledge in this area.

4.3.2 Survey Question 2:

The individual are having appropriate idea about the psychological stress within working environment of an organisation.

Do you have any idea about the psychological stress within working environment of an organisation?	Frequency
a) Yes	260
b) No	40

4.3.2 The individual are having appropriate idea about the psychological stress within working environment of an organisation.

Interpretation:

In the present evaluation the study is being performed over the range of determining the appropriate idea about the psychological stress within working environment of a business. Therefore, the proper analysis is mainly executed with the support of 300 responsive and out of that 260 people are having appropriate idea about the psychological stress within working environment of a business. Therefore, in their perspective, psychological stress is also a significant problem that directly affects the business's operations and growth. Therefore, psychological stress and violence is a significant problem that affects employees' feelings and sentiments at work and prevents them from contributing their fair share to the development of the company's operations. However, psychological abuse is defined as the appropriate and organized use of deceptive manipulation through non-physical acts against a close partner or dependent adult. Psychological abuse can happen prior to sexual, physical or many other abuses. Violence against female can cause long term mental and physical health issues. Abuse and violence affect not just the female involved but also their families, children and communities. These impacts cover harm to a person health, possibly long term injury to children, and harm to societies such as homelessness and lost work. The remaining

population opposes it because they don't comprehend the concept of mental distress in the context of a workplace. As per their opinion it is not important for people have idea about the area of psychological violence.

4.3.3 Survey Question 3:

Assorted causes of workplace violence.

What are the causes of workplace violence?	Frequency
a) Lack of Pre-employment Screening	100
b) Lack of Employee Assistance Program	70
c) Stress	130

4.3.3 Assorted causes of workplace violence.

Interpretation:

According to the opinions analysis of the participants, it has been identified that there are various reasons of violence in the workplace in the study being conducted in this exploration work. 300 participants were chosen to participate in order to acquire useful information. Therefore, out of that, 100 respondents are in favour of lack of pre-employment screening therefore, as per their perception this recognised to be the key aspect which cause workplace violence, thus pre-employment screening is essential for a business to develop their operations as pre-screening helps a business to assist their employees in right manner via their performance analysis and suggest them the significant measures to make appropriate changes in their operations and attempts. Moreover, 70 respondents expressed concern about the absence of an employee support program, which is, in their perspective, another significant problem that impacts how well the company runs generally and increases workplace stress. However, the management and the higher authority of the business are not really concern over providing assistance to their employees in the manner of directing them to moving ahead in right manner to completion of the business operations in appropriate way. Furthermore, remaining 43% of the sample is is in favour of stress as per their opinion; workplace stress is also terms to be the key cause which creates stress and violence at

workplace. Thus as they have stated that stress is a major issue which cause workplace violence as people are facing multiple issues in relation to the work. According to the respondents' opinions, it has been determined that these are the main factors contributing to workplace violence and having an impact on the general functionality of the company.

4.3.4 Survey Question 4:

There are assorted physiological and behavioural indications of stress within working environment of ChopCut Limited and ABC limited.

What are the physiological and behavioural symptoms of stress within working environment of ChopCut Limited and ABC limited?	Frequency
a) Depression or anxiety	150
b) Feeling overwhelmed, unmotivated, or unfocused.	70
c) Psychosomatic issues	130

4.3.4 there are assorted physiological and behavioural symptoms of stress within working environment of ChopCut Limited and ABC limited.

Interpretation:

In the present dissertation, the study has been performed over determining the assorted physiological and behavioural symptoms of stress within working environment of ChopCut Limited and ABC limited. Therefore, the study is being conducted among 300 participants who are having significant knowledge in relation to the similar study area. Therefore, out of that 150 people go with the option of depression or anxiety, thus as per their opinion depression and anxiety are the major behavioural and psychological aspects that affects the working environment of both ChopCut limited and ABC Limited. However, depression and

anxiety are the major issue which create stress among people and this significant affects the functionality of the company.

According to the opinion analysis of the respondents, depression, also defined as depressive disorder or clinical depression, is recognized to be a mood disease that results in a continuous feeling of despair and loss of enthusiasm. It affects individual, thinking, behaviour and attitude and leads them towards stress and mental issue. In addition to this 70 responsive are in favour of feeling overwhelmed, unmotivated, or unfocused, therefore, these are also the psychological and behavioural symptoms of stress within working environment of ChopCut Limited and ABC limited. Therefore, these are the major aspect that affects the overall operations and functions of both the business and employee performance. Unmotivated and unfocused are the major reasons that decrease the operations and progression of the business. From the detailed study executed over the analysis, it has been also been evaluated that, remaining respondents are in favour of psychosomatic issues. So it is a condition that affects both the physical and the mind. There are several physical conditions that are thought to be especially vulnerable to being exacerbated by mental factors like anxiety and stress. Thus as per their opinion analysis this is the major aspect which has affect the business environment of business, thus, ChopCut Limited and ABC Limited are two medium size business which are mainly focuses over attaining higher growth and success at market place and these above mentioned are the key symptoms that affects the overall operations and functions of the business.

4.3.5 Survey Question 5:

There are consequences of workplace stress.

What are the consequence of workplace stress?	Frequency
a) Physical problem	100
b) Emotional problem	100
c) Behavioural problem	100

4.3.5 There are consequences of workplace stress.

Interpretation:

It has been determined that there are several effects of workplace stress that have an impact on the operation of the business, in accordance with the thorough study carried out in the area of identifying the various repercussions of workplace stress. This survey is being conducted among 300 respondents, and 100 of them are in favor of physical issues, therefore in their opinion, this is recognized as one of the major factors contributing to workplace stress, therefore, physical issue involves any sort of physical disability, physical issue and so on. Another 100 people are in favour of emotional problem, therefore, emotional recognition is a key factor which also distresses the overall activities and operations of the business. Emotional issues mainly cause panic attracts, mental disorder and stress and these all affects an individual’s contribution to work in more effective manner. Therefore, remaining individual are in favour of behavioural problem, thus this is also a major consequence which develops workplace stress. Thus behavioural issues involves the attitude, behaviour, perception of people that affects the operations of the business.

4.3.6 Survey Question 6:

There are multiple effects of workplace stress on employees of ChopCut Limited and ABC limited.

What are the effects of workplace stress on employees of ChopCut Limited and ABC limited?	Frequency
a) Impact on health	60
b) Impact on mental alertness	90
c) Impact on personal and professional relationships	150

4.3.6 there are multiple effects of workplace stress on employees of ChopCut Limited and ABC limited.

Interpretation:

In the present study, the study's focus is on examining the impacts of workplace stress on ChopCut Limited and ABC Limited personnel. In the current analysis, 300 employees participated in the survey, and 60 of them were concerned about the influence on their health, this is the major issue which is being faced by the employees at workplace. Both ABC Limited and ChopCut Limited operate at a high level. The main goal of all small and large commercial enterprises is to achieve greater advancement and success, and for these companies, improving performance is achieved by lowering workplace employee stress. Workplace stress mainly influences the health condition of people, thus stress within people develops health issues which influences the enthusiasm to work within workplace and affects the overall operations adversely. Another 90 respondents are select the option of impact on mental alertness challenge Therefore, with the high level workplace stress individual are facing mental issues, as mainly people feel depressed, high pressures and non-appropriate concentration over organisational working. Thus workplace stress cause high mental issues and people feel depressed and facing various health dieses which influences the working of people within an organisation. But the majority of the respondents which is 50% settles on one opinion that workplace stress can effect on personal and professional both relationships that one can maintain. It alters behaviour and thus results to stress. These are the most significant issues that ChopCut Limited and ABC Limited employees primarily deal with at work, according to a thorough examination of the survey, therefore, for considering these major issues it is essential for the businesses to implement efficient measures in respect to assisting the overall business operations in effective manner to better execution of their operations and gain higher growth and performance.

4.3.7 Survey Question 7:

There are different types of violence that are found in workplace.

What are the types of violence found in workplace?	Frequency
a) Criminal Intent	120
b) Worker-to-Worker	80
c) Ideological Violence	100

4.3.7 There are different types of violence that are found in workplace.

Interpretation:

From the in-depth study conducted over the area of analysing the types of violence that are found in workplace, therefore, the study is effectively conducted among 300 respondents for the intention of accumulation of valid and reliable results that are significant for a study. According to the project's descriptive analysis, various forms of violence have a negative impact on business operations; as a result, 120 out of 300 respondents support criminal intent, which they believe to be the most prevalent form of violence with a significant impact on the operations and growth of the business, thus criminal intent is mainly caused due to the non-authorized activities implemented by the employees as the employees get harassed or bullied or isolated by the other employees or the top department of the business, therefore, these are recognised to be the issues that are involved in the criminal intent. Additionally, 80 additional respondents supported violence between employees, making this another significant form of violence that affects business operations and growth. Employees at work, however, are also dealing with the problem of violence towards other employees since they are impacted by their team members, office politics, favoritism, prejudice, etc. These are also directly influencing the motivation of people to work within an organisation and influence their ability to work. Additionally, the majority of individuals support ideological violence.

Violent extremism is described as a type of extremism that endorses and practices violence with ideological or intentional aim, including political and religious violence. Violent extreme ideas can arise in relation to a variety of problems and disputes involving gender, politics, and religion. As a result, this is another serious form of violence that primarily affects workers. From the detailed analysis of the dissertation these all recognised to be the major violence which influences the working of employees at workplace and also affects the overall functioning of the company. Personnel are considered to be the principle asset of business as they are mainly concern over providing effective working environment which is free from stress and violence for the purpose of maximising their working ability and performance states at workplace. As it is fundamental for the management of business to reduce violence in respect to assisting the overall processes in accurate manner to gain higher growth and success via the suitable execution of business operation. .

4.3.8 Survey Question 8:

In which manner psychological stress impact on health of employees.

How does psychological stress impact on health of employees?	Frequency
a) High blood pressure	120
b) Heart disease	80
c) Obesity and diabetes	100

4.3.8 In which manner psychological stress impact on health of employees.

Interpretation:

In the current study, it has been investigated to see how different types of psychological stress affect workers' health. However, in this existing work study has been executed among 300

respondents, thus 300 people are appropriate to execute the investigation in appropriate manner to develop their operations and progression. From the analysis of the project it has been evaluated that 120 out of 300 people are in favour of high blood pressure, thus this is recognised to be the most important influence which is implemented due to psychological stress. However, high workplace stress creates the issue of high blood pressures as people are not feeling good and high thinking develops blood pressures which also creates high health issue. Therefore, 80 respondents are in favour of heart diseases, thus high psychological pressures and stress also generates heart disease which is generating assorted cardio issues among individual and people are no longer able to work with high collaboration and coordination. Therefore, heart issue cause low morale of working and also decreases the encouragement of people at workplace. In addition to this, remaining people are in favour of obesity and diabetes, thus it also generates high body fat and diabetes, which also creates various health issue as people with high diabetes are feeling low and they also weak from insight and people with low power are not able to put their significant efforts in the growth and success of the business. In addition to this obesity is also a major issue which also affects the operations of the business, thus, obesity creates high body fat which make individual lazy and people are not able to operate their operations in effective manner. As per the evaluation of the project it has been identified that, these above mentioned are the key affects that are associated through psychological stress at work place.

4.3.9 Survey Question 9:

There is assorted impact over the physiological violence on employees.

What are the major impact of physiological violence on employees?	Frequency
a) High absenteeism	70
b) High labor turnover	50
c) Poor time keeping	50
d) Poor performance and productivity	70
e) Poor motivation	60

4.3.9 there is assorted impact over the physiological violence on employees.

Interpretation:

As per the in-depth analysis executed over the area of determining the assorted impact over the physiological violence on employees. Therefore, in this study 70 out of 300 people are go with the option of high absenteeism therefore, as per their opinion analysis they think that, absenteeism is a major issue which is caused due to psychological violence at workplace, thus people are not feeling safe and it also affects the sustainability of the employees which affects the overall operations of the business. High absenteeism is also creates adverse impact over the operations and progression of the business as organisations and their management are not able to plan effectively due to lack of high employees engagement and it is affecting the operations of the business in adverse manner. Out of 300 respondents, 50 people are in favour of high labour turnover, thus this is also a major issue which is faces by the businesses due to psychological stress and violence. High employee turnover decreases the performance of the business as the organisations are not able to retain their employees for long time and not able to conduct effective business operations which in turns in generating bad impression over the operations of the business. In addition to this poor time keeping is also evaluated to be the key aspect which is mainly generated through the psychological violence and stress. Therefore, high psychological violence and stress generates high pressure over the business and its management and individual are not able to manage time for executing their operations in proper manner. Furthermore, in this particular analysis 70 people are in concern of poor performance and productivity is also a major issue which is mainly faced by the businesses and its employees due to stress and psychological violence, Therefore, individual at workplace are not encouraged to put their efforts and are not really interested to execute suitable business operations, thus it generating adverse influence through reducing the

productivity and performance of the employees at workplace. However, people with high suffering with stress and violence are not able to conduct appropriate business practices which in turns in moving the business towards loss and lower productivity. Leftover individuals are in favour of lower employee motivation, thus this also recognised to be the key influence which is generating through violence and stress at workplace. Thus, lower employee motivation also generates low morality of individual working and affects the operations of the business. However, these entire major issues which are faces by the businesses due to psychological stress and violence.

4.3.10 Survey Question 10:

There are different main factors that contributes towards employee stress and violence.

What are the main factors which contributes towards employee stress and violence?	Frequency
a) Excessively high workloads	70
b) Weak or ineffective management	80
c) Bullying or harassment	80
d) Poor physical working environment	70

4.3.10 there are different main factors that contributes towards employee stress and violence.

Interpretation:

In this present dissertation work the study mainly executed to determining the main factors that contributes towards employee stress and violence. Thus in this study has been executed among 300 respondents and they said that here are different main factors that contributes

towards employee stress and violence. Therefore, 70 out of 300 people are in favour of excessively high workloads; therefore, this is the key factor which generates high stress among employees and violence as well. High workload at workplace creates issue in the operations and progression of the business. In addition to this, another respondents are in favour of Weak or ineffective management, therefore, this is also a major reason which creates stress at work place, thus businesses are not focused towards effectively management of operations thus, it is essential for the businesses or its management to effectively manage their operations to create high growth and success at market place. Another 80 respondents are in favour of Bullying or harassment, therefore, these are also considered to be the major issue which are plays an effective role in generating higher stress and violence. Therefore, employees at workplace are mainly facing the issue of bullying and harassment as people are harasses for gaining good opportunity and bully by the others on the basis of their different culture, ethics and norms and this creates bad impression over the operations and progression of the business. Leftover respondents are in favour of Poor physical working environment; therefore, this is also a major factor which influences the operations and progression of the business. Therefore higher stress and violence at workplace.

4.3.11 Survey question 11:

There are assorted impacts of workplace stress and violence on the performance of the organisation.

What are the impacts of workplace stress and violence on the performance of the organisation?	Frequency
a) Positive	10
b) Negative	250
c) Neutral	40

4.3.11 there are assorted impacts of workplace stress and violence on the performance of the organisation.

Interpretation:

According to the detailed analysis executed over the area of determining the impacts of work related stress and violence on the performance of the organisation. The survey has been executed among the 300 responsive and they are suggested that, here are different impacts of workplace stress and violence on the performance of the organisation. In this particular analysis majority of respondents are in favour of negative impact as per their opinion, workplace stress and violence has direct negative impact over the operations and progression of the business. Workplace stress and violence are the key issue which are mainly faces by the employees at workplace. Workplace stress is recognised to be a harmful physical and emotional response which can happens when there is a conflict among job demand on the employees and the amount of control an employee has over meeting these demands. In addition to this, workplace violence is defined to a violence which is usually in the form of physical abuse or threat, which generates a risk to the health and safety of an employee or multiple workers. Thus, workplace violence and stress are the key issue which affects the overall functioning of the business. However, due to high stress and violence people are not able to work with more potential and collaboration, thus it is important for the businesses to implement effective practices related to workplace violence and stress in respect to reducing the issue which has influence the operations and development of a business. In today's modern business environment, individual are seeking for running behind power and for power the higher authority and management are putting higher pressure over the employees which creates high stress among the employees and they morale of working has decreased. In addition to this 10 people are in favour of positive impact as per their opinion, workplace violence and stress does not affects the operations of the business and remaining people are not in concern with the same as they are not providing any opinion on the same. However, workplace violence and stress are the major issue which are affecting the morale and encouragement of the business at market place.

4.3.12 Survey question 12:

There are assorted impact of workplace stress and violence in ChopCut Limited and ABC limited.

What are the impact of workplace stress and violence in ChopCut Limited and ABC limited ?	Frequency
a) Staff turnover, recruitment and training	80
b) Productivity and efficiency	70
c) Communication and relationships	70
d) Business and financial performance	80

4.3.12 There are assorted impact of workplace stress and violence in ChopCut Limited and ABC limited.

Interpretation:

According to a thorough investigation of the project, it has been determined that workplace stress and violence have a variety of effects on ChopCut Limited and ABC Limited. Therefore, in this analysis is being performed among 300 respondents and out of that, 80 are in favour of Staff turnover, recruitment and training, thus as per their opinion, it has been evaluated that, workplace violence and stress creates high staff turnover at work place which is effective in decreasing the operations and progression of the business. In addition to this, violence has also create new recruitment for the business and also generates higher training for the employees which is quite time consuming for the business, as these issues are affecting the overall functionality of the business. 70 people are in concern of productivity and efficiency, thus these are also facing by the ChopCut Limited and ABC Limited due to high stress and violence. The both the companies are operating at leading basis and for the sack of generating higher growth and success both the organisations are concern over creating higher pressures and also making employees pressurised to put extra efforts which creates adverse impact over the operations and progression of the business. Furthermore, another 70 people are in favour of Communication and relationships, thus these are the also major influence that is generated through workplace stress and violence. But for the aim of achieving greater growth and success, organizations must be concerned with putting in place effective communication channels. In addition to this remaining respondents are in favour of Business and financial performance, therefore, as per their opinion analysis, due to high stress

and violence the financial performance of the business at workplace. High financial performance is required for a business to assist their operations in right manner and it is the fundamental need for a business to develop their financial operations in respect to reaching higher development and success at market place. As per the analysis of the research it has also been analysed that, these above mentioned are the major influences which are affecting the operations and progression of the both ABC Limited and ChopCut limited at workplace.

Chapter 5: Findings and Recommendations

5.1 Findings

From the above report, it has been find out that there are twelve themes from where the data is collected and analysed in a proper questionnaire form. Individual records are gathered so that each and everyone's opinion should be evaluated and interpreted. Theme one states the individual knowledge about the concept of workplace stress where two fifty people were having the knowledge and fifty people were unaware of workplace stress. Theme two states the individual who are having appropriate idea about the psychological stress within working environment of an organisation where two sixty people were having the idea and forty people were unaware. Theme three states the assorted causes of workplace violence where hundred responses were of the lack of Pre-Employment Screening, seventy responses were of the Lack of Employee Assistance Program and one thirty were of stress. Theme four states the assorted physiological and behavioural symptoms of stress within working environment of ChopCut Limited and ABC limited where one fifty people has responded depression or anxiety, seventy people Feeling overwhelmed, unmotivated, or unfocused and one thirty people Psychosomatic issues. Theme five states the consequence of workplace stress where each of the hundred responses were of physical and emotional along with the behavioural problem. Theme six states the effects of workplace stress on employees of ChopCut Limited and ABC limited where sixty people says impact on health, ninety people says impact on mental alertness and one fifty people says impact on personal and professional relationships (Korbi, Ben-Slimane and Triki, 2021). Theme seven states the types of violence found in workplace where one twenty people says criminal intent, eighty people says worker to worker and hundred people says ideological violence. Theme eight states the psychological stress impact on health of employees where one twenty people prefers high blood pressure, eighty people prefers heart diseases and hundred people prefers obesity and diabetes. Theme nine states the major impact of physiological violence on employees where seventy responses says high absenteeism, fifty responses says high labour turnover, fifty responses poor time keeping, seventy responses poor performance and productivity and sixty responses poor motivation. Theme ten states the main factors which contributes towards employee stress and violence where seventy people says excessively high workloads, eighty people says weak or ineffective management, eighty people says bullying or harassment and seventy people says poor physical working environment. Theme eleven states the impacts of workplace stress and violence on the performance of the organisation where ten people says positive, two fifty says negative and forty were neutral.

Theme twelve states the impact of workplace stress and violence in ChopCut Limited and ABC limited where eighty people says staff turnover, recruitment and training, seventy people says productivity and efficiency, seventy says communication and relationships and eighty says business and financial performance. Therefore, these are the findings of whole report of primary data collected with the discussion of secondary data which is analysed for better understanding and study of the psychological stress and violence in the working environment on firm's performance in order to find out an appropriate conception of the research topic.

5.2 Recommendations

By considering the experience, it is recommended to both the organisations, I have developed a set of recommendations to both ChopCut and ABC Limited. I believe When someone is under stress, they often feel intimidated or uneasy. As a result, they work to develop coping mechanisms that will help them acquire the assistance and care they need to get rid of their symptoms and emotions of stress. Furthermore, people frequently experience powerful reactions to a stressful occurrence. The most appropriate occasions frequently involve environmental and personal problems that represent a threat from an assault. Disbelief, numbness, unhappy emotions, frustration, difficulty making decisions, headaches, stomach issues, smoking, or using alcohol or drugs are appropriate symptoms. There are various methods for dealing with this hazard and removing stress from the overall routine. It is accordingly advised that companies look after their employees by raising their level of motivation and looking after their health by paying attention to their nutrition, getting enough sleep, and providing them a break if they need to feel stressed out.

Additionally, students must express their emotions to their parents, friends, doctors, etc. in order to communicate their practical issues. They must also refrain from using narcotics, which only serve to exacerbate existing problems and make people feel more stressed and afraid. Finally, in order to avoid violence and tension, employees should speak with their professional counselor, social worker, and psychologist.

Additionally, in order to manage stress, people need to simplify their lives by making the right changes that will effectively enhance their health and reduce stress. Regarding this, a number of methods and strategies are beneficial in tense circumstances to keep people's stress levels down. There are several strategies to reduce stress, control its effects on health issues, and even completely eradicate it. People must strike a balance between the vital factors of time management and undertaking the working component so that they can operate effectively and efficiently.

In order to achieve a positive response from their employees, employers must be considerate of their employees' stress levels. They must also rely on people's trust by addressing the stress levels of their families and coworkers and encouraging them to express their worries in a way that will reduce their stress. Additionally, discrete behavior and the appropriate pattern help to manage the responses by successfully describing things in various ways while reading the

literature. For this, the study illustrates how young people create the controllability of complex events by describing the coping mechanisms they release in response to stressful and other obstacles of emerging occurrences.

Besides, they can oversee their push by having appropriate nourishment and not skipping their meals, which leads to keeping up their blood sugar and avoiding a person from their discouraging temperament. It makes a difference and prevent a few activated and strongly sentiments of outrage and disappointment.

Additionally, workers must engage in regular physical activity that lowers stress levels and enhances their general health. They feel good about this because their hormones can decrease the signs of anxiety and depression. It efficiently assesses a person's capacity for stress management and aids in removing the causes of their fatigue. Employees are advised to get seven hours of sleep per night in order to reduce stress. Nobody is immune to difficult conditions, thus stress is a normal part of life. They don't want to get rid of it all at once, and they need a certain level of stress to energize and inspire workers to do the right measures.

Employees that are under stress express appropriate symptoms in a variety of ways, including weight loss, sleep disturbance, easily irritated, negative self-statements, under- or overeating, extended workdays, etc. As a result, when ChopCut and ABC Limited employees experience stress at work, they always look for coping mechanisms, such as taking medicine and seeking medical attention. Contrarily, some people have strategies for ignoring the larger context, such as avoiding situations, obsessively thinking about things, smoking or drinking, overeating, etc. In order to do this, it illustrates the appropriate tactics that, while temporarily relieving the perception of stress, ultimately make things worse. To do this, employees of the relevant organization must reduce any unneeded stress in their lives by getting rid of as many stressors as they can. At both a personal and professional level, they must learn to say no occasionally. They must be more proactive by dealing with issues that can directly contribute to their stress-inducing recipe.

Additionally, the staff members of the organization must evaluate their schedules and prioritize assignments based on urgency. They also need to spend less time with people who stress them and are mindful of their reactions. Along with this, they must also determine the maximum amount of stress that can be tolerated in the given circumstance and change the circumstances that make it impossible for them to do so. In addition, ChopCut and ABC Limited, the employees' employers, can help reduce stress in the workplace.

By engaging in physical activity, which helps people sleep better and handle stress better since sleep renews the body and the brain and also takes care of things with the help of appropriate exercise that some people find does not disturb their sleep. The practical component that aids in removing stress factors is exercise. It causes the body to release a number of substances, including as endorphins and endocannabinoids, which aid in reducing pain and promoting restful sleep.

Regarding this, the staff members of the specific company should exercise and meditate often as doing so makes them feel less worried and promotes happiness. With the aid of adequate activity, such as jogging, swimming, dancing, cycling, and aerobics, their bodies feel fantastic.

Additionally, the staff members of the respective company must follow a diet plan that is effective because the benefits of eating well-balanced meals go beyond mental health, as a healthy diet helps people reduce the effects of stress, strengthen their immune systems, regulate their moods, and lower their blood pressure. Employees still need to create a good plan to pinpoint the right causes of stress in their lives. They begin by ignoring their tension and engaging in appropriate thoughts, feelings, and behaviours as they begin to investigate the causes. They need to do a thorough analysis of key issues, such as defining stress factors as aspects of their personal or professional lives. They often successfully identify the recurrent stressors in their lives to cope with by keeping a stress journal.

Along with this, they must also accept the regular things that employees cannot change, such as their employer's behaviour because they must adapt to their supervisor's behaviour, and they must also accept the situations that they cannot control because they are out of their control, such as changes to policies and systems. Additionally, they must schedule appropriate time for pleasure and leisure that encourages initiative, boosts morale, and encourages a good outlook. Employees of the respective companies must choose a healthy lifestyle that improves their physical health and increases their resistance to stress. Physical activity is essential for minimizing the effects of stress, therefore employees must schedule enough time for exercise and meditation. Additionally, removing the sugar and caffeine from their edible products causes a slump in energy.

Additionally, cutting out the quantity of coffee, soda, sugar, chocolate, and other foods from their diet helps employees unwind and improves their sleep. There are many different methods to comprehend the situation, but one effective way is to speak with a legal adviser and assume that a mental condition may be a crucial component in analysing violent behaviour before subjecting employees to disciplinary action. They must also confirm that their laws and those pertaining to human rights are being followed. Along with this, unresolved workplace conflicts between co-workers also lead to a hazardous and unpleasant work environment.

Additionally, they must ensure that the policy clearly states what the staff must do in dire circumstances, including hostage-taking and the use of force. Furthermore, there is less evidence that life skills are actually necessary for social development programs, whose goal is to foster emotional, social, and behavioural traits that will reduce teenage violence. Most studies on life skills programs are conducted in high-income nations, particularly the United States and the United Kingdom. For this, unaddressed badgering gets to be the essential calculation for having appropriate viciousness in a few zones of the company, driving to creating savagery and stretch among them. With respect to this, both the companies ChopCut and ABC are constrained to have to be created noticeable approaches to kill stretch and

savagery among their workforce by characterizing acts of viciousness that attempt threat of violent activity against the property of the company and people. Moreover, bosses of a few wards too got to take each sensible precaution in terms of securing laborers against household viciousness.

To do this, leaders must uphold their moral and legal commitments to provide a safe workplace while upholding their standards of performance by having well-known procedures that work for successfully addressing issues. Additionally, it is advised that managers and leaders follow company policies, including the safety and health standards, in order to understand and enforce appropriate policies for reducing violent incidents that result in making the workforce safer and secure and help the company reduce litigation costs. Additionally, employees are able to find balance in everyday situations to accommodate new situations. For this reason, ChopCut and ABC Limited employees must pay close attention to instilling a holistic culture in the workplace. Organizational culture is based on tolerance and equal opportunity to subsidise the development of a job environment in which violence and stress play no significant role. Therefore, companies and employers must have effective policy statements with appropriate initiatives to raise awareness among company management and employees. This impacts stress and violence in terms of benefits and stress relief.

ChopCut and ABC Limited are given some advice on how to prevent or prevent the workplace violence from their office environment because it is becoming more frequent day by day. Because violence is a problem that is becoming more common in society, organizations must exercise caution and take action to prevent violence in the workplace so that workers' safety can be guaranteed.

ChopCut and ABC Limited are advised to take the following specific actions, which are detailed below:

- **Background checks on employees:** Preventing workplace violence begins with the employment process. Companies should thoroughly investigate potential candidates' backgrounds. A background check indicates whether or not a prospective employee has a history of violence. To prevent workplace violence, the applicant should not be chosen if something emerges, a suitable explanation should be sought, and if that kind of violence cannot be prevented.
- **Establishing laws to stop violence:** Bullying and harassment are two behaviours that make people angry. Because of how insulting this makes the workplace, businesses must develop procedures to reduce the likelihood of violence. The policy comprises of guidelines that aid in discreetly resolving disputes. Additionally, it is important to inform everyone about the new policy and make sure that each employee is familiar with it.
- **Establish an anti-violence policy:** Prevent workplace violence by establishing a policy that immediately encourages teams to report violent behaviour. This type of policy helps

eliminate unwanted employee behaviour and leaves no room for favouritism. Managers should punish employees who try to break policy rules. Employees should be informed of the consequences of policy violations so that no one complains about not knowing the consequences.

- **Motivating the workforce to accept diversity:** It is common knowledge that there is a potential of conflict and disagreement wherever there are employees. These difficulties can lead to sadness and lead to violence if they are not resolved. Managers should make an effort to plan events that foster employee interaction and a positive appreciation of differences. This would help students comprehend how these distinctions can be used as a team's assets.
- **Prevent disputes from turning violent:** Stressful situations such as unjustified layoffs and terminations can provoke anger. Leaders must prevent conflicts from escalating into harassment by warning employees. This enables managers to monitor employees who leave the company uninvited and be prepared to take action if necessary.
- **Determining risk factors specific to an organization:** Managers should pinpoint any possible hotspots for workplace violence. Employees occasionally combine personal and work-related difficulties together, which makes them hostile and haughty. Managers should consider issues including insufficient security, workers' perceptions that violence would be permitted going forward, or the situation where workers are unable to report violence.

Chapter 6: Conclusion

From the prior data, it has been concluded that psychological stress occurs when a person encounters a scenario that requires more than their normal coping mechanisms. Threats of violence made against employees who are employed by an organization are referred to as "workplace violence." This violence has the potential to occur both internally and externally of the company. This study addresses objectives and questions pertinent to the subject matter. Researchers gathered pertinent and in-depth data on themes including psychological stress and workplace violence. Feeling stressed and inactive is referred to as psychological stress. It is a pain that influences a person's productivity and thinking since excessive stress raises the threat of illnesses including strokes, heart attacks, and depression. Stress is brought on by problems with marriage, the unexpected death of loved ones, medical conditions, and a lack of money. Due to the unfriendly environment, the person experiences psychological stress, which lowers the organization's productivity and performance when those people work there. Employee stress and tension in the work are caused by a toxic and immoral workplace environment. A person's behaviour, which includes killing and inflicting harm on others, is referred to as violence. The two things that have an impact on both the organization and the employees are violence and psychological stress. The study comes to the conclusion that these characteristics are unfavorable for the business and the employees since they have a

negative impact on the productivity of organizations with employees. This study was done to better understand and pinpoint the effects of psychological stress and workplace violence on business performance. The research theme is to investigate the influence of psychological stress and violence in the workplace on organizational performance. Because these are aspects that also negatively affect the turnover rate of the organization.

I tried to shed light on the difficulties experienced by workers through this subject and identifies the causes of persistent problems with stress and aggression. Violence and psychological stress at work lower morale and drive employees to put in extra effort to accomplish goals and objectives. These kinds of pressures raise employee turnover, which has a detrimental effect on sales and performance. I have developed strategies to lessen pressure and stress in the workplace with the aid of this investigation. This research study will assist other companies in their efforts to reduce stress and increase productivity. Psychological stress and violence are problems and problems because they reduce the productivity and turnover of companies. These issues negatively impact brands and organizations. This stress and violence directly affect morale and motivation. Because they are already filled with feelings of pressure. Employees and employees who are stressed do not communicate effectively and efficiently, and inaccurate or incomplete information is communicated. These employees usually speak angry or annoyed, making others uncomfortable. This study describes different ways to reduce the threat of workplace violence, cheating, stress relief, and decompression.

These are the elements that have a detrimental effect on employees' motivation and encouragement levels. Giving workers the right education to help them understand what they can and cannot do as well as how to protect themselves from violence is one of the strategies. A excellent technique to secure the workplace is by installing CCTV, additional lighting, and other security measures. They are creating regulations that will safeguard workers. This document also identifies the application of motivational theories to alter employee behaviour for the better. Reduce work stress by creating a rewarding and comfortable work environment. This can be achieved by educating management on how to reduce stress in the work environment. This research shows that we need to reduce stress. Otherwise, it will affect you negatively. Work stress is causing employees to take more time off, leading to an increase in corporate absenteeism. The study found that employee stress stems from prejudice and favouritism. It is also a cause of fights among employees, believing that they cannot be promoted because of their favouritism. Motivation theory is a method for keeping employees motivated. Organizations can reduce organizational stress by examining each employee's performance in informal meetings and hearing their views on matters such as job security.

The motivational theory of Herzberg is applied to promote constructive behaviour in workers. According to this hypothesis, employers have no control over employees' work lives, which raises workers' accountability for their work. Employees are given the opportunity to participate in new projects and units through the application of theory, and it is recommended

that difficulties be resolved internally rather than passing them off to their superiors. The fact that they are taking on and managing the risk rather than delegating encourages employees.

Organizations apply motivational theory to proactively improve their work environment. These theories coordinate employees to work more effectively and efficiently to achieve personal and professional goals. Employees are provided with good compensation and incentives. Workers and employers can maintain good relationships within the organization as they are the primary resources to carry out activities to achieve goals. Employers are the ones who connect directly with workers, so they can quickly de-stress workers through conversation.

Organisations use another theory mentioned in this research to reduce stress, any workplace violence and improve motivation.

Organizations' human resource managers build a good work atmosphere and teach employees how to deal with risky and unforeseen circumstances by implementing Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory. It is a concept that helps employees stay inspired about their jobs. This hypothesis lists five different needs in order of higher to lower needs. Using this principle, managers and other leaders can stop workers from taking on too much stress and experiencing it at work. This increases productivity and boosts the organization's brand image. The first need, also referred to as physiological needs, is crucial for human survival, and managers are responsible for meeting it. It has clothing, food, shelter, and water. Having all these managers provides the right amount of wages and compensation for employees. When this need is met, employees become more energetic, motivated, and productive to the organization. The second need is security needs. Financial security and job security are provided by employers for their employees. The third is social needs such as trust among employees, friendship, and warm human relationships. Employees are motivated to allow maximum interaction between colleagues and promote a friendly culture in the work environment. The next need is the need for appreciation, called proper recognition, awards and prizes for the excellent practical work of employees. All of these motivate employees to do their jobs effectively.

The final requirement is referred to as self-actualization needs, and it is what all driven employees want to achieve. All of these actions help businesses and management to inspire workers and get the most performance out of them. Additionally, this helps to lessen workplace violence, employee stress, and environmental stress. Stress is characterized as a harmful phenomenon that compromises the well-being and morale of the organization's personnel. Therefore, it becomes important to decline stress in the workplace in order to lower staff turnover and absenteeism within the company. Associations require motivational theories to prevent workplace violence, conflicts, and stress. Assessing employee performance and organizing informal gatherings to learn what the staff thinks about their work, management, and administration are other ways to minimize anxiety.

The problem of violence in the workplace has an adverse effect on employees' attitudes, which makes the working environment worse. The use of force or the threat of force against other employees is referred to as "workplace violence", these actions can result in dangerous circumstances and have numerous negative effects.

In this study, some strategies for reducing workplace violence in an organization are discussed. These strategies include identifying risk indicators that enable the organization to anticipate potential risks early on and implement violence-prevention measures. Because employees engage in activities like trading money with the public, working in areas where there is a high crime rate, and many other activities, assessment of the workplace by employers helps to create an informed workforce and a happy atmosphere.

Another method is to start a program to avoid violence, where rules like zero tolerance are implemented and a safe workplace is provided. This policy also lessens the psychological stress experienced by the company's and organization's workers. Implementing security measures that help to maintain a secure work environment is another option. Managers give staff clear instructions not to approach uncharted territory or dangerous areas. These steps help create a secure workplace and motivate employees to work in a flexible setting.

Based on this research, it has been shown that workplace violence occurs when an employee is subjected to abuse, harassment, assault, or threats from other mentally unstable workers. Employees, employers, and organizations are all negatively impacted by workplace violence, which lowers their productivity and effectiveness levels. The government also makes steps to improve the working environment in order to keep a regular check and lessen workplace violence. The government provides a legal framework so that businesses may function effectively. Regular inspections are also conducted so that records of injuries can be kept and tips can be given to assist avoid injury scenarios. Organizations participate in government monitoring programs so that they can carry out their functions and acquire a competitive edge.

Even the government can step in to change an organization's procedures to shield its employees from violence, which would work to their advantage should a violent incident arise in the future. Government policies are designed to prevent employees from taking unfair deductions from their pay and salaries, preventing stress from such occurrences. The government also creates teams and support groups that assist workers who have experienced violence and difficult circumstances on the job site. The research method used in this study helps to gather data and achieve the study's goals. It includes sources like publications, group discussions and surveys, which help in collecting relevant and reliable data.

Various methods such as research approaches, research philosophies, data collection, and research tools such as group discussions, observations, and questionnaires have been adopted by researchers according to the demands of current research on the effects of psychological stress and violence on organizations.

Other methods, such as data presentation and analytical techniques, are also used to present the collected data in an understandable and appropriate manner. All of these methods are important in research as they help identify, select, analyze and process data on specific topics. These techniques assisted in analysing the data's applicability and dependability in achieving the research's predetermined objectives. Because they are the ones most closely connected to the organization and have a deeper awareness of its environment. Open-ended and closed-ended questions are posed to ChopCut Limited and ABC Limited personnel in order to gather data and information. Employee assistance allowed the investigator to obtain accurate and pertinent information, successfully motivating the goals of the study.

The closed-ended questions helped to understand the opinions of employees regarding mental stress at work, their knowledge of the symptoms of stress in their co-workers within the organization, consequences regarding stress in the organization, the impact of workplace stress among employers and employees, various forms of violence experienced and faced by employees, negative factors which contribute in stress and violence in the environment of the organization, and more. In order to suggest approaches, policies, and procedures for reducing stress and violence, it is helpful to have an understanding of opinions and other elements that are prevalent in the organization.

Chapter 7: Appraisal & Reflection

I am very grateful that my University of West Scotland allowed me to conduct this research. The management team was very supportive, which allowed me to have a seamless experience during this entire journey. My research is “To analyse the consequences of psychological stress and workplace violence in a company’s performance.” This was a case study research on ChopCut Limited and ABC Limited.

I will also like to thank my supervisor Dr Nazrul Islam for his tremendous mentoring throughout this journey. His support showed the actual act of kindness, and it encouraged me to complete this journey. Every action requires a plan. To complete this research, I had to plan to cover every element required for this research precisely. During this journey, many obstacles came in my way. Because of that, I had to face many challenges in various stages of this research. Everything seemed to be okay until the pandemic started.

I felt impatient when I realized that organizing all the materials would take time because of the pandemic. I had assumed that everything would be completed without a rush and before the deadline, but I soon realized that it is not a simple process. However, looking back, I am happy with the efforts I made in my work. I had to postpone my plans and obligations in order to do this study for my assignment.

On many occasions, I realised that it would be tough to complete this research before the deadline because of many limitations and restrictions during this pandemic. Though it was challenging, it helped me to improve my management skill, and I learned how to complete a

task under pressure. The completion of this research also enhanced my academic understanding, which allowed me to plan and divide work into smaller units. Every activity was divided with the needed time. It was also divided with the requirement of research and set with sequence.

Even though it took some time to finish, it was a beautiful experience that made me aware of several talents and faults that I was previously unaware of. Once I was able to showcase my research strengths, it was a very wonderful experience. My tendency to work in disciplines where I can demonstrate my talents becomes natural.

I thought revealing my strength would help me saving time while accumulating all the information before the deadline. But in reality, it has cost more time than planned and created stress mentally. In my opinion, what has created stress is not planning how to organise and arrange material in the end. I made assumptions and opinions that.

I would arrange the materials at the last minute, but it had given me learning that things should never be left for the end because it creates mental stress. During dividing tasks and activities, I learned that it should be planned how each section should look because if it is planned, it becomes easier to organise all the materials at the end without taking any stress.

Furthermore, while planning, I have learned that everything should not be just based on assumptions and should consider facts and figures so that planning becomes reasonably practical. Moreover, I learned to face new areas that have some challenges and risks. In future, when I would work on such type of research, I would acknowledge my strengths and weaknesses. This will assist me in understanding the opportunities and threats while conducting the research.

Next time when I decide to divide work into more minor activities, this would assist me in giving proper time to each activity with collecting and organising all the materials before the deadline. And I would be prepared in advance to face any challenges and consequences related to the research. I would also encourage and motivate myself while researching because I want effective and efficient results within a limited period.

As per the report mentioned above, it is effectively analysed that I have taken the use of primary and secondary as data collection methods because they are a must for getting authenticate and accurate evidence related to the topic of the research. Both methods helped me understand the concept of psychological stress and workplace violence and the various measures to mitigate stress and violence from the work environment. In respect to this, I have used questionnaires and focused group discussion techniques because they both help in knowing and understanding the opinions of selected respondents or employees.

I use a number of research methodologies since they help with the correct identification and collecting of data from various sources, which is necessary for fulfilling the research's goal and objectives.

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Appendix:

Gantt chart

Psychological Stress and Violence in workplace

Level	Name	Start	Completion Date	-
1	Selection on appropriate Topic	02/26/2019	11/03/2022	
2	Setting aims and objective	04/23/2019	11/03/2022	
3	Developing Introduction	05/21/2019	11/03/2022	
4	Developing Literature review	06/18/2019	11/03/2022	
5	Research Methodology	08/13/2019	11/03/2022	
6	Conducting focus group discussion	04/20/2020	11/03/2022	
7	Conducting Survey	01/10/2020	11/03/2022	

8	Analysing data	06/20/2020	11/03/2022
9	Developing thematic model	12/01/2020	11/03/2022
10	Developing results	07/11/2021	11/03/2022
11	Redevelop introduction	11/01/2021	11/03/2022
12	Developing recommendation	01/01/2022	11/03/2022
13	Developing conclusion	03/15/2022	11/03/2022
14	Referencing and Compiling the report	05/10/2022	-

Close-ended Questions Questionnaire

Q1) Do you have knowledge about the concept of workplace stress?

- a) Yes
- b) No

Q2) Do you have any idea about the psychological stress within working environment of an organisation?

- a) Yes
- b) No

Q3) What are the causes of workplace violence?

- a) Lack of Pre-employment Screening
- b) Lack of Employee Assistance Program
- c) Stress

Q4) What are the physiological and behavioural symptoms of stress within working environment of ChopCut Limited and ABC limited?

- a) Depression or anxiety
- b) Feeling overwhelmed, unmotivated, or unfocused.
- c) Psychosomatic issues

Q5) What are the consequence of workplace stress?

- a) Physical problem
- b) Emotional problem
- c) Behavioural problem

Q6) What are the effects of workplace stress on employees of ChopCut Limited and ABC limited?

- a) Impact on health
- b) Impact on mental alertness
- c) Impact on personal and professional relationships

Q7) What are the types of violence found in workplace?

- a) Criminal Intent
- b) Worker-to-Worker
- c) Ideological Violence

Q8) How does psychological stress impact on health of employees?

- a) High blood pressure
- b) Heart disease
- c) Obesity and diabetes

Q9) What are the major impact of physiological violence on employees?

- a) High absenteeism
- b) High labor turnover
- c) Poor time keeping
- d) Poor performance and productivity
- e) Poor motivation

Q10) What are the main factors which contributes towards employee stress and violence?

- a) Excessively high workloads
- b) Weak or ineffective management
- c) Bullying or harassment
- d) Poor physical working environment

Q11) What are the impacts of workplace stress and violence on the performance of the organisation?

- a) Positive
- b) Negative
- c) Neutral

Q12) What are the impact of workplace stress and violence in ChopCut Limited and ABC limited?

- a) Staff turnover, recruitment and training
- b) Productivity and efficiency
- c) Communication and relationships
- d) Business and financial performance

Open-ended Discussion topics

- Q1) Effects of workplace-violence and psychological stress on employee's productivity of an organisation.
- Q2) Government has a role in overcoming workplace-violence. Do you agree or disagree? Please justify
- Q3) discuss some ways to overcome from workplace-violence and psychological stress by use of motivational theory.
- Q4) Does employee motivation has any impact of workplace-violence and psychological stress? Discuss in general
- Q5) Identify some types of motivation that are used for overcoming psychological stress and workplace-violence within your organization
- Q6) According to you, psychological stress and workplace violence impacted on performance of

ChopCut Limited and ABC limited? If yes, how?

Q7) Discuss the role of your organization (ChopCut Limited and ABC limited) in overcoming impact of psychological violence and workplace stress.

Q8) Performance appraisal system can help your organization (ChopCut Limited and ABC limited) to overcome impact of workplace stress. Do you agree or disagree? Justify

Q9) Role of training and development in reducing stress within working environment of ChopCut Limited and ABC limited.

Q10) Innovation and its role in overcoming psychological stress and workplace-violence in working environment of ChopCut Limited and ABC limited

Q11) What are the ways used by your company to maintain positive relation among employees at workplace?

Q12) External factor of business organisation helps to reduce your stress within working environment of company. Do you agree to the statement?

Q13) Provide any recommendations to ChopCut Limited and ABC limited about how to overcome Employee's workplace stress and psychological violence.

Frequency Table

<u>Questionnaire</u>	
Q1) Do you have knowledge about the concept of workplace stress?	Frequency
a) Yes	250
b) No	50
Q2) Do you have any idea about the psychological stress within working environment of an organisation?	Frequency
a) Yes	260
b) No	40
Q3) What are the causes of workplace violence?	Frequency
a) Lack of Pre-employment Screening	100
b) Lack of Employee Assistance Program	70
c) Stress	130
Q4) What are the physiological and behavioural symptoms of stress within working environment of ChopCut Limited and ABC limited?	Frequency
a) Depression or anxiety	150
b) Feeling overwhelmed, unmotivated, or unfocused.	70
c) Psychosomatic issues	130
Q5) What are the consequence of workplace stress?	Frequency
a) Physical problem	100
b) Emotional problem	100
c) Behavioural problem	100
Q6) What are the effects of workplace stress on employees of ChopCut Limited and ABC limited?	Frequency
a) Impact on health	60

b) Impact on mental alertness	90
c) Impact on personal and professional relationships	150
Q7) What are the types of violence found in workplace?	Frequency
a) Criminal Intent	120
b) Worker-to-Worker	80
c) Ideological Violence	100
Q8) How does psychological stress impact on health of employees?	Frequency
a) High blood pressure	120
b) Heart disease	80
c) Obesity and diabetes	100
Q9) What are the major impact of physiological violence on employees?	Frequency
a) High absenteeism	70
b) High labor turnover	50
zc) Poor time keeping	50
d) Poor performance and productivity	70
e) Poor motivation	60
Q10) What are the main factors which contributes towards employee stress and violence?	Frequency
a) Excessively high workloads	70
b) Weak or ineffective management	80
c) Bullying or harassment	80
d) Poor physical working environment	70
Q11) What are the impacts of workplace stress and violence on the performance of the organisation?	Frequency
a) Positive	10
b) Negative	250
c) Neutral	40
Q12) What are the impact of workplace stress and violence in ChopCut Limited and ABC limited ?	Frequency
a) Staff turnover, recruitment and training	80
b) Productivity and efficiency	70
c) Communication and relationships	70
d) Business and financial performance	80